

LECTURERS' AND STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES TOWARDS
STRATEGIES USED IN ORAL PRACTICE AND ASSESSMENT IN
LIBYA

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Abstract

The study aims to identify strategies used for oral practice and assessment in Libyan private language centres from the perspectives of teachers and students working/enrolled in these centres. Within the Libyan higher education context, students and graduates seek learning opportunities in private centres to improve and consolidate their English language oral skills, including listening and speaking, knowing that their school/university education is not sufficient for effective, real-life communication skills in English. Drawing on principles from Assessment for Learning (Black and Wiliam, 1998) which emphasise the dynamic connection between assessment and learning as well as Social Learning theory (Bandura, 1977, et seq.), the study sought to examine to what extent teachers' and students' perspectives towards oral practice and assessment supported the learning process. Using a lens of power, the paper critically examined these strategies for English language learning and assessment in the Libyan context. Education in general, and English Language Teaching in particular, are influenced by an array of power relations (Foucault, 1980). The Ministry of Education controls examination policies and teaching/assessment timetables in Libya. The Departments of Educational Inspection and Examinations are examples of such power relations. Additionally, MacLure (2006) argues that education workers, including students and teachers, are confined by coursebook materials in which they have pre-determined goals, activities, and time plans of units and modules. The teacher's book may as well instruct the teachers what to do, when and how long to do it, and furthermore what to say in the process. To this end, the current work adopted the qualitative mode of investigation, using

semi-structured interviews. Twenty semi-structured interviews were conducted, nine with teachers of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) working in private language centres and eleven with students enrolled on EFL courses in these centres. The participants were asked questions related to their perspectives and attitudes towards oral practice and the strategies used for oral assessment practice. One of the findings was that, generally, teachers and students had positive perspectives towards oral teaching/assessment practice in private schools, unlike in government-led schools, where they argued that forms of power such as school administration, inspectors were seen as interfering in a negative way in that they encourage memorisation over oral practice arguing that oral practice was 'too hard' for the learners and that covering the syllabus was a priority over language attainment. However, in their attempts to promote practising oral skills, teachers stated that they use scores as incentives. Students also stated how they were penalised for making mistakes in oral practice. Foucault (1977, p. 183) discusses how reward and punishment have become habitual in disciplinary institutions in a practice which compares, excludes, and thus normalises. It has become a power structure which leaves little room for agency or resistance from those under it. These findings indicate that private language centres in Libya provide more effective practice of oral assessment that supports learners in developing authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya compared to their experience in government-led institutions. However, there remains room for improvement, particularly with regards to motivation strategies, feedback and audio-visual teaching aids.

Dedication

To my mother, Fatma and my late father, Bashir.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The importance of English, as a Lingua Franca and a Global language (Graddol, 2006), and its vital role in breaking linguistic barriers between countries around the world has been long recognised. Global English is a rather loaded term. It has to do with historic interventions, specifically colonialism. The term stems from the communicative function of English as a common language especially amongst speakers who do not share a native language or culture (Firth, 1996). Thus, Brown (2014) argues that the use of English as a Lingua Franca entails that it can no longer be claimed to be “the property of the countries where it is spoken as a native language”. Nonetheless, he adds that the English language teaching business is not only standardising the *product*, that is the materials content but also standardising its *delivery* including global institutions and teacher training qualifications in a process that he refers to as the “MacDonaldization of private language schools”. Teacher training qualifications delivered by certain organisations entered the global market convincing consumers that a few weeks of training are sufficient to teach English to any student anywhere irrespective of their first language background or their historical or cultural context (*ibid.*). Moreover, these global English language teaching courses favour native speakers over non-natives (Richardson, 2016). This means that these organisations have the upper hand in dictating what variety of English to be taught (Canagarajah, 2006), who to best teach it (Richardson, 2016), how it is taught and assessed (Brown, 2014). These teacher training courses rely on very rigid sets of techniques and restrictive features. Brown (*ibid.*) points out two limitations of such pedagogical style: a) that language learning is non-linear and that individual differences in learning require different students to work on materials differently according to their learning preferences and needs (Larsen-Freeman, 1997), b) empirical evidence suggests that the use of L1 inside EFL classrooms has a facilitating effect. Not only do

research findings argue that translation is an inevitable aspect of foreign language acquisition (Hentschell, 2009), but they also point out its potential as language teaching tool (Zojer, 2009; Stiefel, 2009).

Apart from the product and its delivery, English language international tests, such as TEOFL (Testing of English as a Foreign Language) and IELTS (The International English Language Testing System) are designed by individuals who come from the dominant culture and as such, reflect the values, cultures, and experiences of their designers (Gipps, 1999) who have little regard to social inequalities. It is not because they know better, it is because knowledge is defined by them and thus such tests obscure such inequalities by normalising them (*ibid.*). For example, tasks as simple as expressing an opinion in one context could exert cultural pressure in another. Additionally, communicative cues vary cross-culturally leaving learners from certain cultural backgrounds less advantaged. In Asian cultures, for example, Khan (2006) argues that modes of interaction are quite different from those in Western societies. Or and Shohamy (2017) draw further attention to inequalities based on issues of (in)accessibility. Different English language learners worldwide have varying degrees of accessibility to English. This situation creates inequality of opportunities and discriminates learners from various linguistic and socio-economic backgrounds based on the learners' government policies such as that noted between Palestinian learners and Israeli learners. In a related vein, despite the proposition of a new orientation, that is new norms of proficiency (Canagarajah, 1999), there is a debate about whose norm to use, that is the choice between Standard English (Davies, Hamp-Lyons, and Kemp, 2003) and World Englishes (Lowenberg, 2002).

Despite the inevitable power embedded in Global English and due to its vital importance (Graddol, 2006), special attention has been paid to different aspects of English language (for example, grammar, vocabulary, writing, and speaking) in secondary schools, language centres and universities worldwide, especially

communication skills. Therefore, oral assessment has been given great attention, since not only does it provide a way of testing students' knowledge about a particular topic, but also improves their verbal communication skills (Bygate, 1987). Specifically, oral assessment is usually administered to assess students' ability to produce words and phrases through the evaluation of their fulfilment of different tasks, such as engaging in minialogues, performing roleplays and discussing a given theme. It has been observed that teaching English as a foreign language, especially oral skills, may differ drastically between schools, universities and language centres in Libya. Orafi and Borg (2009) report on the gap between the planned outcome of the Communicative Language Teaching curriculum policy and its implementation. One of the main reasons for this gap is the incompatibility of education policy with assessment methods on the whole and oral assessment in particular Orafi and Borg (*ibid.*, p. 252).

1.2 Context of the study

Due to the importance of Global English as a precursor to admission to overseas undergraduate and postgraduate and higher education studies for Libyans, various, competing private language centres have been inaugurated in Libya. These centres argue to provide quality English language teaching services. Additionally, the tendency to use English as the language for many subject matters is increasing in Libyan universities, implying the need for the students to learn English and have good language skills, especially oral skills (Omar, 2014). This tendency has added extra importance to that of the private centres, given that there are few opportunities for Libyan students to learn English at university (for example Najeeb, 2013).

English is the language of instruction in many university subjects, especially in scientific disciplines mainly because the content materials are only available in English (Khalid, 2017). The Arab League Educational, Cultural and Scientific Organisation has given rise to the integration of English language especially in

teaching scientific subjects (Abuklaish, 2014; Asker, 2012). University educationalists realised the inability of Arabic language to compete with the fast evolving English language terminology in science and technology (Asker, 2012). Moreover, there is a demand for international students – including Libyan students – seeking postgraduate studies in countries overseas to gain high scores on international tests such as TEOFL (Testing of English as a Foreign Language), GRE (Graduate Record Examinations) and GMAT (Graduate Management Admission Test) if they were to be accepted on a higher degree programme (Abuklaish, 2014; Omar, 2014). Libyan students in particular, struggle with oral skills the most compared to writing and readings skills (Ahmad, 2001). The inadequacy of Libyan students’ oral and communicative skills is believed to be partly rooted in their history of colonisation and as a result of the former leader’s ideologies (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017).

During the King Idris Sanusi’s ruling in Libya, in the 1950s, petroleum and gas reserves were discovered (*ibid.*). This led to having over 2000 international companies investing in Libya (Bayoud, 2013; Najeeb and ELdokali, 2012). At the time, the Libyan government realised the importance of developing foreign language education, especially English language to improve the country’s economy (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017). Oil revenues accelerated economic growth in the 1960s allowing the country to be more financially independent (Blanchard, 2016). However, in September 1969, the Libyan economic development changed when Moamar Qaddafi overthrew King Sanusi in a military coup (*ibid.*). At the time, Qaddafi was influenced by the ideologies of Gamal Abdel Naser, president of Egypt in the 1970s, who advocated the union of Arab countries and resistance of Western colonialism (*ibid.*). During the 1970s, Qaddafi supported, “revolutionary, anti-Western, and anti-Israeli movements across Africa, Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. These policies contributed to a rapid souring of U.S.-Libyan political relations that persisted for decades” (*ibid.*, p. 24). The U.S. imposed sanctions on Libya, which lasted 20 years, as a reaction to Qaddafi’s

support to anti-Western movements and terrorist attacks (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017; Blanchard, 2016). These negative attitudes held by Qaddafi led to Libyan civilians sharing similar views and attitudes towards the West (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017). By the end of the 1980s, use of any foreign language was banned in Libya (*ibid.*). It was illegal to use any foreign language, English included, in private or state schools, in hospitals, or in universities (*ibid.*). This situation of banning English for approximately six years contributed to the present state of poor English proficiency of Libyans (*ibid.*). With the introduction of Libya Tomorrow project by Qaddafi's son, Saif Al-Islam, who was part of Gaddafi's inner circle, and in charge of diplomatic roles and public relations. One of the major aims was to restore relations with the West by re-introducing foreign language education, including English, in Libyan schools and universities (Gheblawi, 2011). Several political measures were taken, not only with the international community but also with Libyans in exile (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017). Saif Al-Islam, who speaks English proficiently and holds a PhD from the University of Eastern London, called for international companies to invest in Libya in order to improve the country's economy (*ibid.*). Consequently, this had prompted the need to develop better foreign language curricula and teaching practices especially in English (*ibid.*). However, since the ban on English language was lifted by the late 1980s (*ibid.*) and according to Najeeb (2013), English language teachers required to teach English were poorly qualified despite years of effort (Omar, 2013) and several attempts to reform English language education. The initial attempts involved using the grammar translation method for teaching English (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017). Because this method focuses chiefly on grammar and reading, the Libyan Ministry of education, by the end of the 1990s, introduced a curriculum reform, which utilised the communicative language teaching approach (*ibid.*). Nonetheless, and despite all the attempts and investment to improve the state of English language teaching in Libya, the objectives of the curriculum reform intended by the authors of the new syllabus

were not met, be it on schools level (Orafi and Borg, 2009) or university levels (Alloreibi and Carey, 2017). This issue is a result of how the curriculum is delivered by teachers and managed by the Libyan government (*ibid.*). In addition, attitudinal, economic and socio-cultural constraints, which are rooted in the colonialism eras, Qaddafi's policies (both as mentioned above) and Libya's societal structure play a crucial role (*ibid.*). According to Youssef (2012), Libyans show a negative attitude towards English language or anything of a Western origin, which can most likely be attributed to the American military actions targeting Muslim countries worldwide making them a threat to peace and democracy.

1.3 Significance of the study

Motivated by this state of affairs, the present research explores lecturers' and students' perspectives towards the strategies used in oral practice and assessment, a less investigated though significant aspect of English language teaching and learning. Surveying the related literature, it is quite clear that few studies have addressed students' and lecturers' perspectives towards certain issues in learning and teaching in Libya, my home country. This research thus aims at bridging this gap through bringing in students' and lecturers' perspectives towards the strategies used in oral practice and assessment to the fore. It is important to address this gap, given that students' and lecturers' perspectives are of paramount importance to produce a concise picture of how English is taught at these centres and the proficiency of the assessment used (McKay, 2002; Biggs and Tang, 2011). The current thesis set out to determine how students and lecturers conceive of the role and effectiveness of oral assessment practice in developing authentic spoken English in private centres. In a related vein, this research aims to find out whether students hold the same views as their lecturers and how such differences, if any, can be accounted for within the related working theories and the two-way communication between

teachers and students. With this background in mind, the importance of the proposed research emerges. This research attempts also to bring to the fore how the students consider oral skills, the pertinent problems that they face and how assessment methods and preparation can be enhanced from their own perspectives. Similarly, it delves into the lecturers', perceptions attempting to identify the problems and, thus, the best solutions for them. Accordingly, this research aims to find out what participants consider effective or not effective, and how they would prefer to learn (for the students) and teach (for the lecturers). Additionally, this research attempts to investigate differences between lecturer and student perspectives. In doing so, it will add significantly to the literature on English language teaching, learning and assessment. Specifically, the research will investigate the role, impact and significance of oral assessment in this field, and draw implications for how English language is taught, learned and assessed. It is expected that the findings will be applicable to English language teaching and learning not only in Libya but internationally.

1.4 Thesis structure

The subsequent chapters of the present study are divided as follows. Chapter 2 discusses the theoretical framework that underpins the current study and reviews the literature on English language assessment in general and in Libya in particular. The chapter also presents literature on teachers' and learners' perspectives on assessment and its impact on learning as well as oral practice and assessment. Chapter 3 presents the research design, methodology, philosophy, the research questions, and methods including data collection, sampling, procedure and some ethical considerations. The chapter also explains data coding procedure and addresses issues of validity and reliability. Chapter 4 presents the results and concludes with a discussion. Chapter 5 summarises the findings from Chapter 4 in relation to the research questions and discuss these findings in the light of AfL approach and SCLT theoretical framework. It presents the

implications of the findings, addresses some limitations, provides an autobiographical reflection and concludes by presenting recommendations and areas for further research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Learning English in school and university does not yield satisfactory communicative and/or academic results for the students (Ahmad, 2001). Libyan students struggle with utilising their English language knowledge in functional situations despite their university education, which involves English as a compulsory subject (Abu Srewel, 2002). This applies to English language majors alike (Shihiba, 2011). According to Orafi and Borg (2009), the curriculum reform introduced in Libya in 2000, presents not only pedagogical demands for teachers but also challenges their communicative skills in delivering its content in English. This, they argue caused graduates having “undeveloped spoken communicative skills in English” (*ibid.*, p. 251).

Graduates/students are faced with the need to learn English communicatively and have good language skills, especially oral/aural skills (Omar, 2014) to enable them to use English proficiently in the real world. This tendency has added extra importance to that of the centres to train Libyan students to effectively and successfully communicate in English (Najeeb, 2013).

Oral skills both listening and speaking emerge as the skills with which Libyan students face problems (Ahmad, 2001). This being the case, special attention must be paid to the reasons why the students find oral skills difficult to learn (Ibrahim, 2015). Some studies attribute this weakness to the strategies used by the teachers to teach students, others highlight the involvement of the assessment methods and how students prepare for the exams (Saleh and Zakaria, 2013), while others attribute the issue to the lack of consistency in oral assessment of English language learning (Duff, 2001). Finally, as mentioned earlier, Orafi and Borg

(2009) attribute this to the lack of communicative abilities amongst the teachers.

To investigate this, I will be asking those involved, that is students and teachers, about their perceptions of how best practice in English language learning and assessment is understood in the Libyan context and what the role and effectiveness of oral assessment is in teaching English in private language centres in Libya.

This review of the literature draws on principles of Assessment for Learning approach, and concepts of Bandura's social learning theory to inform the status of oral practice and assessment in English language teaching in private language centres in Libya. The theoretical underpinnings are examined from a perspective of power relations.

2.1 The Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework underpinning the analysis of the current study is drawn from a) the principles of the Assessment for Learning approach by Black and Wiliam (1998), which stresses the influence of formative assessment on learning, and b) Bandura's Social Cognitive Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977, et seq.). In the light of this theoretical framework, the present study seeks to analyse to what extent teachers' and students' perspectives towards oral practice and assessment support the learning process and prepares learners for real-life demands of the target language.

Using a lens of power, the study interrogates the factors, which impact English language teaching within the Libyan education system. It also seeks to explore the influence of political, socio-cultural, economic, and attitudinal constraints on the Libyan society. Most importantly, it analyses if and how this may impact oral practice and assessment in private language schools.

The theoretical framework adopted for this study is based on two learning theories, namely Assessment for Learning (Black and Wiliam, 1998) and Bandura's social learning theory (Bandura, 1986). While the first theory is specifically designed for pedagogical purposes and relates to classroom practices,

Bandura's theory applies to learning as a human psychology. First, Assessment for Learning is discussed. The theoretical underpinnings are examined critically.

Bandura's social learning theory is explored. Elements of agency including intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness and self-reflectiveness (Bandura, 2006) are examined. In addition, the role of lack of confidence and agency in social learning is discussed. Finally, the relationship between the two theories to each other and the study is explored.

2.1.1 Assessment for Learning (AFL)

Assessment for Learning (AFL) (and its alternative term formative assessment) has been embraced by educational institutions across the world (Klenowski, 2009; Stobart, 2008). It is argued to be supported by empirical evidence in Black and Wiliam's (1998) seminal work and that of others following it (see Harlen and Deakin Crick, 2003; Stobart, 2008). AFL has been repeatedly reported to have positive effects on student motivation, engagement, and self-confidence (Hayward and Spencer, 2010; Black, Harrison, and Lee, 2003).

Black and Wiliam (2009, p. 7) disseminated five key practices for AFL. These are sharing success criteria with learners, questioning, feedback in the form of comment-only marking, peer- and self-assessment, and formative use of summative tests. Three crucial processes that serve as a unifying basis for the above practices was drawn (Wiliam and Thompson, 2007) from model of learning and teaching by Ramaprasad (1983) as shown in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Ramprasad’s model of teaching and learning.

Although not pointed out explicitly, it seems the process is socially constructed since it involves three types of agents that is the learner, the teacher and peers.

AfL has been repeatedly challenged in the literature. To begin with, I will explore commentary on formative assessment by Crossouard (2012). She commences her analysis with the following statement,

What might become of formative assessment if it was to attempt to attend more explicitly to the wider social contexts which frame institutionalised learning, and thus take on a more political guise (*ibid.*, p. 188).

Broadfoot (1996) shares similar views. He argues that the core motivation for assessment is to control mass education, its goals and rewards, thus to sustain power. Tests that are designed by individuals who come from a specific socio-economic background, ethnic group, gender, and language background, will reflect values, cultures, and experiences of their designers (Gipps, 1999). It is not because they know better, it is because knowledge is defined by them and consequently such tests obscure such inequalities by legitimating them (*ibid.*).

The Libyan EFL learner and teacher alike, in this regard, are both working from a package designed by authors from a different cultural and linguistic background and it is against this background, English language learning, teaching and assessment are formed. It is not because English language and culture is better than their native language and/or culture. It is simply because

it is the language of the globe (Graddol, 2006). It has been mentioned earlier that Libyan learners do not perform well in international language proficiency tests such as IELTS or TOEFL, for example. These standardised tests make use of standardised English such as Standard British English or Standard American English creating inequities between native and non-natives and even amongst natives whose dialect is not the standard. Performance in such tests is affected by socio-cultural factors such as poverty, allowing those financially-capable to attend training courses and the poorer less capable, and for those who have a mismatch between language and culture such as Arabic and English speakers (Gipps, 1999).

Wiliam (2011) attempts to defend formative assessment against such concepts. He notes that the purposes of formative assessment are not to be confused with those of summative assessment and observes such unplanned consequences of what he refers to as “policy diffractions” in an attempt from education policy makers to seek “quick wins”. He states that AfL has been overthrown by power and that practitioners have been applying the ‘letter’ and losing sight of the ‘spirit’ of AfL whilst at the same time acknowledging school leaders’ intentions to try their best in a culture of accountability. However, Gipps (1999) exhibits the clear and inevitable link between the two noting that assessment has been utilised to control and regulate curriculum by means of recent globalisation trends of curriculum reforms and standardised assessments across the globe. Classroom assessment, she argues, can also be used as a power structure for classroom management (*ibid.*). Perrenoud (1998) challenges this socio-cultural view of collective development by disentangling two distinct processes. The process of regulating activities that promote productive learning and that of regulating learning itself, where teachers develop an understanding of the learners’ cognitive and learning processes and the role of feedback in assisting learners to become self-regulating are two different processes he argues (*ibid.*). From this standpoint, AfL is also argued to shift power and control from a tradition where power is solely held by the teacher to a

situation where both teacher and learner share control and responsibility over the learning process (Willis, 2007), a notion that can be embraced by some teachers and impose a feeling of threat to others (Black and Wiliam, 2006). This is true for teachers who are trying to find the balance between accountability requirements and the notion of improvement (Brown, 2004).

The self-regulation of learning is further challenged by Crossouard (2012) who situates the misinterpretation of linking emancipation in association with autonomy and creativity of thought and education, which in turn led to mass schooling, institutionalised education and the emergence of what Foucault (1977) refers to as the nation-state. From this standpoint, indoctrinated institutions, she proposes result in producing disciplined and docile subjects instead of creative and independent thinkers who are able to reason and construct knowledge within and beyond the walls of such educational institutions. Foucault's analysis in respect to disciplinary institutions is that they a) treat pupils/students "as a machine: its disciplining, the optimization of its capabilities, the extortion of its forces, the parallel increase of its usefulness and its docility, its integration into systems of efficient and economic controls" (*ibid.*, p. 139), b) reside on hierarchical observation, surveillance, and normalising judgement (*ibid.*), which do not take individual differences in readiness to learn as Crossouard (2012) observes. Foucault (1980, p. 30) argues that power "reaches into the very grain of individuals, touches their bodies and inserts itself into their actions and attitudes, their discourses, learning processes and everyday lives".

What AfL does not seem to recognise is the potential undesirability of learning or consider the power relations/hierarchies involved within formative assessment (Crossouard, 2012). Omar (2014, p. 27) reports on the general consensus among Libyan EFL students about the undesirability of learning English becoming a recurrent theme, in which students reiterate, "learning English is not easy at all". Power hierarchies within peer and group assessment in the observation data by Crossouard (2012) exhibited two distinct but relevant

phenomena in this regard. The first is a form of peer and group disparagement, where she describes, “assessment hierarchies left lower-attaining pupils vulnerable to the criticisms of higher-attaining pupils and where learners had concerns about critique from their peers” Crossouard (*ibid.*, p. 194). In a related vein, and as a result of the socio-historical perception of foreign languages, Libyan learners of English are also subject to peer derision when practising English communicatively inside the classroom (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017) albeit for different reasons. They add that when they speak English, “their peers do not take them seriously. It is most often perceived as showing off, so it is therefore socially taboo to use English in public” (*ibid.*, pp. 98–9). This is arguably a result of a history of colonisation (Youssef, 2012) and an impact of the former regime’s ideologies against the West in the form of political discourse, a power structure recognised in the analysis of power by Foucault (1970). The second is that power hierarchies are also discernible when teachers appoint a group leader, who can become dismissive of ideas from other group members (Crossouard, 2012). In addition in peer discourse, Gee (2004, p. 55), notes that learners,

are less likely to simply defer to the authority of the other’s viewpoint, more likely to seek some rational way to deal with differing viewpoints and perspectives, and more likely to actually change their own viewpoint for reasons they understand.

Whilst observations by Crossouard (2012) and Gee (2004) concern children, similar social-power dynamics involved in peer-assessment can be observed in higher education. A fear of over- or under-penalising in peer-assessment as a result of personal relationships has also been reported (Topping, 2009). In addition, peer assessment was also perceived as impeding relationships among peers and criticised for lacking objectivity (Hanrahan and Isaacs, 2001; Lindblom-ylänne, Pihlajamäki, and Kotkas, 2006) as well as the students’ inability to defend their work in front of the assessor (Lladó et al., 2014). Moreover, students have expressed anxiety, stress and discomfort knowing that their work is being assessed by others (*ibid.*).

Black and Wiliam (1998) report on the positive effects from project implementations of the Formative Assessment Research Group that was applied by teachers of mathematics, science and English in both Oxfordshire and Medway (Black, Harrison, and Lee, 2003) and considerable attainment in test results within the classes involved in the study (Wiliam, Lee, et al., 2004). This raises the notion of how attainment is measured and whether it is measured in a way that reflects true learning. One of the factors that play a role in such results can arguably be the facet of sharing success criteria with the learner. But the question that arises is what educational success is and how it is measured. Biesta (2009, p. 35) challenges such practice and educational discourse based on statistics that do not “measure what we value” but instead “value what we (can) measure”. In a culture that values scores, success is contingent on how students perform in tests and how they compare to other national or potentially international institutions rather than true, reflective, and democratic learning. Performativity has been a long-standing issue in the field of education where education and educational institutions are treated like products and factories respectively. According to Ball (2001, p. 210),

[pe]rformativity is a technology, a culture and a mode of regulation... that employs judgements, comparisons and displays as means of control, attrition and change. The performances of – individual subjects or organisations – serve as measures of productivity or output, or displays of ‘quality’, or ‘moments’ of promotion or inspection.

Such measures of productivity and outcome are based on measurable criteria such as test scores, student retention, and teacher performance (Brown, 2015). The issue with such an evaluation system is that it does not account for what is ‘behind the scenes’ of success or failure: the evaluation overlooks the amount of hurdles students’ have to deal with to pass and the cultural and linguistic bias, which are an inherent part of an exam (*ibid.*). Brown (*ibid.*) explains that,

many English language assessments contain references to topics that some cultures are more familiar with than others, or expect students

to perform in a way that comes more naturally to European students than it does to students from, say, China.

Too much focus on teacher performativity can arguably shift the teachers' focus from meeting the learners' needs to focusing on meeting the evaluation criteria imposed by the education policy (*ibid.*). Ball et al. (2011, p. 612) argue that in theory, teachers are seen as "policy subjects" who do not read or write policy, or regard it as something that is predetermined. Policy reading can imply that power can be located at a macro-level and micro-level via discursive practices (Hedman and Magnusson, 2019; Pennycook, 2006). The policy makers' intervention in the education system is an implication that teachers and the teaching profession cannot be a reliable source for delivering standards of schooling (Forde et al., 2006) fostering a discourse of derision upon teachers and the teaching professionalism (*ibid.*). Biesta (2009) and Forde et al. (2006) argue that measuring learning and teaching can be hard if not impossible and, as a consequence, the focus is shifted from measuring actual learning to endorsing and applauding the measurable. Performativity is strongly manifested in teachers performing teaching practices that do not necessarily prioritise learning from their perspective or theory. Rather, they perform in such a way to comply with the educational policies, inspection criteria, and the recommendations put forth by policy agents and decision makers. To help relate this notion to the context of English language teaching, Brown (2015) listed examples where performativity can influence FL teaching practices: for example, educational policies are typically a one-for-all kind of system which is applied to all educational subjects making it too generic, lacking meaning, or in favour of certain subjects over others. Another example is generating evidence, such as pre-inspection meetings, which can come at the expense of learning and lessons, especially because they are time-consuming and teachers are pressured into cancelling a lesson to attend such meetings. Also, the urge to transfer and apply what is called 'best practices' for one college uniformly onto other colleges even if such practices are not in their learners' best interest or matches their specific needs. Another example is

the focus on student *retention*, that is recruiting students and keeping them on the course, as one of the Key Performance Indicators. This measure is rather discriminatory as it favours students who are settled, and thus likely to remain, in the country over those with a less stable residency status. This violates ethics of equality and inclusion especially against vulnerability groups such as asylum-seekers, jobseekers, students with health problems, and single parents, and teachers are forced to choose between excluding these groups and maintaining their Key Performance Indicators high or jeopardising their retention score by being more inclusive (Brown, 2015). In the Libyan context, such issues do not apply, especially in the private sector. Whilst there is a scarcity of research studies, from my experience in this context, language schools do not run background checks on the students' social, residency, or financial status. Recruitment is the school manager's responsibility. Typically, the most successful recruitment advertisements are those which indicate a native element in the teaching staff, that is either having native English teachers or Libyan bilinguals who have a native-like English accent. Language school heads capitalise on the perception that native English-speaking teachers tend to be the idea model for language intuition and pronunciation (Kirkpatrick, 2010) even in the presence of evidence which demonstrates no superior advantage of natives over non-native teachers of English (Mahboob et al., 2004). Another challenge the Libyan teacher faces in a private language centre is having to deal with mixed-level students in one course. It may be difficult to recruit a number of students which all fit in the same course level. Those students who are above or below the average level are typically combined in one course to avoid having them wait for the right number of students to fit in a homogeneous English language proficiency group level, albeit further research is required to verify this experience. Sjolie (2002) argues against placement tests altogether positing that "education is about teaching students – meeting the vital needs of students – not testing to see if students can meet the needs of instructors and administrators."

He further argues that mixed-level classes are ‘an unlikely formula for success’. One final example Brown (2015) provides is the attainment problem: in a world of performativity, teachers are pressured into passing everyone in assessments instead of utilising professional judgement and failing those who do not meet the passing criteria. Failing students reflects negatively on teachers. Such an issue places responsibility on teachers and treats teaching as the process of passing packages of knowledge onto students’ minds. MacLure (2006) explains that modern educational policies are those of ‘closure’, those which ‘repress’ and ‘control gaps’, and view teachers as means of transferring packages of knowledge into the student’s mind and expect uniform consumption amongst students.

In Libya, EFL learners do not seem to struggle with end of local schools’ test scores. Not only are Libyan students’ incapable of communicating in English successfully in real-life situations, their performance on English language international tests are reportedly low (Abuklaish, 2014; Omar, 2014). Policy decision makers and teachers focus on form because it can easily be measured compared to oral communication (Madsen, 1983).

Biesta (2009, p. 38) further expresses concerns over the rise in discourse about learning. His arguments are that learning is individualistic compared to education that involves a relationship. Learning he argues is a process that is devoid of content or direction. He argues that the problem with learning theories is that they prioritise the learner over other factors and this consequently shifts the responsibility from teacher to learner and shifts education from a right to a duty.

It seems that AfL’s approach to learning prioritises the individual’s responsibility as well his/her well-being above other external factors. The theory does not account for other factors beyond the individual such as social, cultural, or generally environmental influences on the learning process. It seems lacking an element that,

Conceives of learning not as something that happens in the heads,

minds or brains of the students, but sees it as something that happens in and ‘through’ social practices (Hodkinson, Biesta, and James, 2007, p. 22).

A theory that accounts for a socially-situated learning accounts for such shortcomings. The next section explores the role of the bidirectional relation between the individual, the environment and behaviour.

2.1.2 Bandura’s Social Cognitive/Learning Theory

Social learning theory revolves around the concept that through actions, humans “produce the environmental conditions that affect their behaviour in a reciprocal fashion” (Bandura, 2006; 1977). Bandura’s theory can be applied in pedagogical practices as it relates to both the learner and the teacher. The theory in its relation to education focuses on the idea that cognitive processes that take place during social activities in the classroom affect learners’ and teacher’s behaviour and development (Bandura, 1986). Relevant aspects in this context include observational learning, reciprocal determinism, self-efficacy and self-regulation.

2.1.2.1 Observational learning

Humans learn by observing models/modelled activities (Bandura, 1977). Models in the EFL classroom may include the teacher and/or peers who enact language behaviours and activities that demonstrate oral practice. Oral activities include listening to/speaking the language, and/or dialogues, recordings, and/or videos, from native speakers, illustrating a language behaviour/element, for example asking for directions or checking in at the airport. In Libyan schools, EFL teachers tend to ignore listening and speaking practice (Orafi and Borg, 2009; Shihiba, 2011). This has been attributed to several reasons. One reason is the misalignment between curriculum goals and assessment, evident in teachers’ perception that practising oral skills is a waste of time since exams do not test it (Orafi and Borg, 2009, p. 250). Another reason is that teachers lack the

proficiency/fluency to speak English and rely on Arabic in their instruction (see *ibid.*, p. 249 and Omar, 2014, 127, ora) thus cannot act as models themselves.

Another reason is the lack of teacher training initiatives with the introduction of the communicative curriculum reform (Asker, 2012, p. 17) and especially after English was banned for over a decade (Zainol Abidin, Pour-Mohammadi, and Alzwari, 2012; Aloreibi and Carey, 2017; Bagigni, 2016; Elabbar, 2011; Mohamed, 2014; Mohsen, 2014; Najeeb and ELdokali, 2012; Omar, 2014; Orafi and Borg, 2009; Sawani, 2009; Shihiba, 2011). Orafi and Borg (2009, p. 245) indicate that,

the new English curriculum in Libya can be described as power-coercive; that is, teachers were not involved in the design of the innovation and their role was to implement the decisions about the curriculum made by the educational policy makers.

Additionally, it has been argued that English course books are provided in incomplete packages. They lack listening materials such as CDs (Omar, 2014, p. 124). In a study of English practice in Libyan universities, listening was only practised by listening to the teacher reading aloud short texts and dialogues slowly and clearly and speaking practice was restricted to students reading ‘scattered’ dialogues and texts (Bagigni, 2016, pp. 185–6). Such manner does not reflect authentic language use (Ur, 1999).

Lack of an appropriate teaching facilities is another issue highlighted by Omar (2014). This includes technology, language labs and visual and audio teaching aids. Bandura (1977) posits that humans are active cognitive processors who link their behaviour to consequences and that cognitive processes are a crucial element for observational learning. Such agentic dynamics mediate the process of learning and Bandura proposes four mediational processes that govern observational learning. These are attention, retention, motor reproduction, and motivation. The following sections identify and discuss Bandura’s core properties of human agency in light of the English language teaching and learning in the Libyan context.

2.1.2.2 Reciprocal Determinism

Reciprocal determinism refers to the concept that personal, behavioural and environmental factors are interdependent (Bandura, 1977, pp. 194–5). The relative impact of each factor varies depending on settings and for different behaviours (*ibid.*). How learners/teachers construe the outcomes of their behaviour informs and changes their environment and their personal characteristics, which subsequently changes behaviour (Bandura, 1986). Other schools of thought argue that human beliefs, thoughts and behaviour are shaped by cultural, historical and social environments (Wertsch, Tulviste, and Hagstrom, 1993). Such environmental structures are reflected in mediational tools (Vygotsky, 1962). For this study, these can include education policy, curriculum reform, guidelines and educational standards, which evolve continuously as humans use them. Hodkinson, Biesta, and James (2007, p. 22) propose a similar, but more educationally-situated, dynamic to Bandura’s reciprocal determinism proposing a reciprocal relationship between individuals and learning cultures, which “refer to the particular ways in which the interactions between many different factors shape students’ learning opportunities and practices”. Dispositions, actions and individual histories of students are part of the learning culture (*ibid.*, p. 23) is in line with Bandura’s explanation of how personal characteristics and attitudes contribute to the learning experience.

Libyan students and teachers come with a historical baggage of foreign invasion that has impacted their attitude towards foreigners and foreign language. Motivation to learn English has not only been affected by these events but also the banning of English during the 1990s. In Libyan schools students for the most part experience difficulties with English (Omar, 2013), whether it is related to the English culture (Ahmed, 2015) learning the language (Najeeb, 2013; Omar, 2013; Youssef, 2012), speaking it (Khalid, 2017; Diaab, 2016) and/or understanding it (Khalid, 2017). Teachers also experience difficulties implementing communicative activities in the EFL classroom (Shihiba, 2011) as

part of the communicative curriculum reform. These difficulties result in low self-efficacy, which discourages them from actively participating in activities that can potentially improve their learning. Teachers' beliefs in students' inability to carry out oral tasks (Orafi and Borg, 2009) prevents students the opportunities to learn and improve. Furthermore, learners and teachers' attitudes towards the language and its culture has an impact on their behaviour (Brown, 2007). These attitudes are dealt with later in this chapter. Similarly, the environment has a negative impact on the student's ability to speak. The student is surrounded by people who only speak Arabic (Khalid, 2017). Although practising English is limited to the classroom, this opportunity is also hindered by the Libyan learner's characteristics, for example shyness to perform in group discussions or pair work as a result of a cultural tradition "where young people, in general, and students, in particular, are less open to group discussions which are usually the domain of older people" (*ibid.*).

2.1.2.3 Self-Efficacy

Self efficacy is defined as "people's judgments of their capabilities to organize and execute courses of action required to attain designated types of performances." (Bandura, 1986, p. 391). The learner and/or the teacher's perceived self-efficacy results in setting even higher goals as well as the increased likelihood of achieving these goals (Bandura, 1994, pp. 194–5) by both the learner and the teacher. Self-efficacy is manifested in confidence in participating in classroom tasks which may lead to achieving pre-set goals (Bandura, 1986). Neither the teacher nor the students believe that students are capable of carrying out oral tasks Orafi and Borg (2009, p. 249). As mentioned above, learners are shy to take part in classroom speaking practice due to cultural reasons and due to lack of ability to speak, including but not restricted to, pronunciation and understanding English. Additionally, it is argued that parents and other individuals in the EFL learner's environment tend to push them to study and

that learning English is not their choice. Rather it is something imposed by schools or university departments and they have no personal interest in learning it apart from passing exams. On the other hand, one reason for EFL teachers' lack of confidence can be attributed to inadequate proficiency (Maley and Duff, 1987). Libyan EFL teachers are neither proficient speakers nor have good English language teaching skills (Elabbar, 2011; Omar, 2014).

2.1.2.4 Self-Regulation

Self-regulation manifests itself in the process where the learner or teacher sets goals, adjusts their behaviour and strategic plan/instruction to fulfil these goals (Erlich and Russ-Eft, 2011). This can be seen in classroom learning processes including setting goals, monitoring and self-regulated learning (Caprara et al., 2008). This concept is also a key practice in AfL. Powers (1991, p. 152) challenges this concept, arguing that,

Purposive behaviour as control behavior entails neither prediction nor an impossible influence of future outcomes on present actions. Instead, it works through ... continually comparing a perceptual version of the current external situation with an inner specification for that perception. Action is driven by the difference, or error.

Bandura asserts that learners acquire self-regulatory functions by observing models. The argument that modelling supports incorporating novel strategies for teacher training is supported by research (Bandura, 1989; Caprara et al., 2008). In typical Libyan classrooms in the government-led sector, instruction is teacher-centred (Elabbar, 2011; Shihiba, 2011) and the learner does not practice listening or speaking and is, thus, not actively engaged in classroom oral activities. It has been observed that Libyan university students, and youth in general, lack a clear vision towards educational future (Khalid, 2017, p. 54).

Bandura (2006) discusses core properties of human agency, intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness and self-reflectiveness, in the light of social learning theory. He proposes that through cognitive self-regulation, human beings can

control futures, which they envision based on the present situation of events.

Intentionality is the property of creating intentions, which comprises a plan or strategy to fulfil such intentions (*ibid.*). Forethought extends from intentionality and it entails visualising goals and anticipating outcomes together serving as a motivational incentive (*ibid.*).

Bandura argues that agency is collaborative and situates this argument on the basis of control theory. Motivation is an integral property of agency. If a learner understands why a task or activity ought to be fulfilled, and the amount of effort to be invested in such task, his/her interests in performing it impacts his/her decision (Simons, Dewitte, and Lens, 2004). If no importance is seen in such task, the learner is less motivated to invest time setting goals or planning ways to fulfil them (Bandura, 2006). Libyan EFL students fall into two categories with this regard, those who view English as a tool for future career (Asker, 2012) and those who consider English to be an obstacle between them and success, an imposed subject that does not contribute to their future career (Khalid, 2017). Bandura (1989, p. 1176) argues that motivation can be measured by the amount of effort a person invests to fulfil a given goal and the amount of perseverance in the face of impediments and he incorporates principles of control theory with this regard. However, Powers (1991) observes that control theory shows that a motivating result can be achieved by applying various, not necessarily uniform, scenarios by means of varying causal reasons.

2.1.2.5 Self-reactiveness

To become an agent, in addition to the above properties, an individual must be capable of self-regulation. After creating an intent, commitment towards such intent and planning for it, it is necessary to fulfil this plan by employing the most suitable strategies as well as motivate and regulate accomplishment of this action plan. The connection between forethought and action is what is referred to as the explanatory gap (Bandura, 1991). Inside the classroom, the learner's ability to

implement various learning strategies based on different tasks and activities and regulate these strategies to accommodate progress towards his/her pre-set goals makes him/her a successful learner (Paris and Paris, 2001). The instructor's role is to model ways of using new strategies and provide the right support during practice. This can be done through constructive feedback to help learners use these strategies independently. However, Zumbrunn, Tadlock, and Roberts (2011) suggest that when instructors model novel strategies, some learners may resort to older and more familiar ones, which, in many cases, may not be the most effective. A learner may resort to flash cards, a traditional and familiar technique in learning new vocabulary, for example, merely because it is more familiar and thus easier than the one suggested by the instructor. This can lead to less meaningful learning as a result of lack of consideration for the new strategy suggested by the instructor as it can be seen as taking more time to learn and implement. They assert that monitoring and feedback from the instructor may assist learners in using new techniques with fluency when learners are particularly discouraged.

2.1.2.6 Self-reflectiveness

In this phase of human agency, an agent individual not only creates intent, forethinks, plans, and employs appropriate strategies, but also reflects on one's own performance.

It is very important at this point to understand the relationship between human agency and social learning theory. Bandura (2006, p. 165) puts forwards that, "People do not operate as autonomous agents . . . human functioning is a product of a reciprocal interplay of intra-personal, behavioural, and environmental determinants". He further posits that the majority of functioning in human beings is socially embedded. During an interaction where individuals form environments to one another, an action may act as an agentic stimulus, a reaction or an environmental product. In this sense, a learner can be more than an individual agent, and thus influenced by the social experience inside the

classroom, with which he/she interacts, allowing additional influence from the instructor and peers. This is analogous with what Bandura (2000) describes as collective agency. Working through such collaborative effort inside the classroom, the common belief in the collective capability to address and fulfil goals is essential to this mode of agency (Bandura, 2006). However, Powers (1991) challenges Bandura's view maintaining that his attempt to bring principles of Control Theory in his thoughts of human agency suffers. Powers (*ibid.*) contends that an external agency is not required to put a control system into motion. A control system is based on the idea that an internal system and external system work against an individual's tendencies to deviate (*ibid.*).

A centralised control system can be exhibited in the bureaucratic, administrative, hierarchical powers such as standards and/or policies. A strong relationship between the learner/teacher and the educational system forces them to conform to norms and standards and vice versa. According to Hirschi (2017), humans tend to make decisions based on perceived benefit/ outcome. An example of this in relation to control theory would be that students and teachers would conform to educational policies/norms because of the perceived outcome such as rewards, career requirements to name but a few. In Libya, English language classroom practice is driven by examination policies.

2.1.2.7 Lack of agency

Lack of confidence is lack of agency. Bandura (2006, p. 169) explains that children are born into the world without personal agency. However, this property is established gradually after birth through social interactions with the environment and repeated observation. The infant's self-agency progresses through three consequent states; a state where s/he perceive of one event, in their social surroundings, as causing another; a state where one action causes/can change an event within these surroundings; a state, in which the infant realises that s/he can may influence the results of an action (*ibid.*). This

development of psychological stages involves more than the ability to influence results through actions. It requires the ability to recognise/believe in the ability to influence or alter results through one's actions and ultimately consider themselves as agents of their own actions. Similarly, in classroom settings, unless the learner recognises his/her role as an agent in their own learning, they will lack the self-confidence required for setting an action plan to achieve the pre-set goals of learning.

Bandura (1977; 2006) emphasises the crucial role of believing in personal efficacy. He explains that,

unless people believe they can produce desired effects by their actions, they have little incentive to act, or to persevere in the face of difficulties. Whatever other factors serve as guides and motivators, they are rooted in the core belief that one has the power to effect changes by one's actions. (2006, p. 170).

As mentioned earlier, teachers can prepare students to become agents of their own learning in developing foreign language oral skills by explaining explicitly the properties that comprise successful communication. One way this can be achieved is through self-assessment in oral production (Kissling and O'Donnell, 2015). Repeated self-assessment, it is argued, can help familiarise the learner with these properties that exceed the mere knowledge of grammatical rules and vocabulary. McMillan and Hearn (2008) provide a definition of self-assessment, which goes in line with Bandura's properties of human agency and which specifically addresses the learning context within educational settings. They define self-assessment as the learners' ability to "judge their own work to improve performance as they identify discrepancies between current and desired performance" (*ibid.*, p. 40).

2.1.3 The relationship between AfL and Bandura's SLT

Although AfL and Bandura's Social learning theory are two independent theories, they share various aspects. AfL argues for introducing the teacher

learning objectives to learners, providing feedback within the flow of teaching, encouraging self-assessment, all of which comes in line with facets of Social Learning theory, goal-setting (as introducing learning objectives), feedback on the other hand allows the student to be either confident in continuing the path of learning (self-regulation and efficacy) as they started or gets them to alter and modify their ways. Self-assessment allows the learner to be more confident and becomes an agent of learning who owns aspects such as intentionality, reactivity, reflectiveness, motivation, performance accomplishments to name but a few. Effective collaborative learning in peer-assessment is analogous with collective agency.

The following sections discuss the literature on some factors influencing successful language attainment, language assessment, and delve into the current literature dealing with learners and teacher perspectives towards oral practice and assessment.

2.2 Factors affecting successful foreign language attainment

Various studies have investigated a number of psychological and academic factors, such as self-confidence/efficacy, motivation, anxiety and attitude, from a social-cognitive perspective (Bandura, 1977; Bandura, 2006), from an educational perspective (see for example, Black, Harrison, and Lee, 2003; Hayward and Spencer, 2010), and from an L2 learning perspective (see for example, Dörnyei, 2001b; Dörnyei and Skehan, 2003a; Krashen, 1981), as well as the correlations between these variables (Gardner and MacIntyre, 1993; MacIntyre and Charos, 1996; Gardner, Tremblay, and Masgoret, 1997; Gardner, Moorcroft, and Metforda, 1989; Ehrman, 1996). The results of the latter group of studies show that there is a negative correlation between anxiety and self-efficacy/confidence, as well as between anxiety and motivation. Motivation, however, was found to

correlate positively with attitude. The following sections discuss the variables of motivation and anxiety, how they are interrelated, and how they relate to self-confidence.

In the following sections, an attempt is also made to explore the notion of authenticity and how it affects communicative skills amongst EFL learners and prepares them for real-world situations.

2.2.1 Motivation

Motivation is the second strongest socio-psychological predictor of L2 achievement after linguistic aptitude (Gardner and Lambert, 1959). In their seminal work in the late 1950s, Gardner and Lambert argue that,

an individual acquiring a second language adopts certain behaviour patterns which are characteristic of another cultural group and that his attitudes towards that group will at least partly determine his success in learning the new language. (*ibid.*, p. 267)

To measure motivation, the researchers used a test battery which had indices of motivational degree and orientation. The former index measures the degree of effort and eagerness the learner produces to learn a language. The latter index can be one of two: either integrative orientation whereby the learner has a positive disposition towards the language group and the desire to interact with and become a member of that community, or instrumental orientation which means the learner has a utilitarian disposition, focusing on using the language as an instrument to reach specific goals or potential practical results, such as career advancement or further studies. Their findings showed that integratively oriented learners were generally more successful than instrumental learners. However, this finding is not always confirmed (see Castillo, 1972). As an affective variable, motivation is one of the most highly researched extra-linguistic factors impacting foreign language learning (Gardner, 1985; Dörnyei, 1998b; Dörnyei, 2001a; Dörnyei, 2001b; Dörnyei and Skehan, 2003a; Gardner and MacIntyre, 1991). Some of the key commonalities in these studies are that: 1) attitudes towards a

foreign language has the highest impact on motivation, which can be intrinsic or extrinsic, 2) intrinsic motivation, specifically, improves learning of a foreign language and helps the learner in keeping the effort to learn the foreign language, and 3) there is an interwoven relation between motivation, self-confidence, self-efficacy, anxiety, L2 proficiency and achievement, amongst other factors, and on persistence, language attrition, and language retention (Gardner, Moorcroft, and Metforda, 1989). Intrinsic motivation refers to the motivation to get internal rewards such as the pleasure received from performing a certain activity or to satisfy one's curiosity, whereas extrinsic motivation refers to the motivation to perform an activity to get an extrinsic reward, such as a high score, or to avoid punishment (Dörnyei, 1994). In a study on Chinese students learning English at Chinese universities, intrinsic motivation was found to negatively correlate with fear of negative feedback, communication apprehension, and summative assessment anxiety, all of which are elements of foreign language classroom anxiety (Liu and Huang, 2011). Ehrman (1996) demonstrates that motivation has a direct impact on self-confidence, self-efficacy and anxiety. Ramage (1990) shows that intrinsic motivation has a greater impact on L2 achievement than extrinsic motivation. Ghanizadeh and Rostami (2015) explored differences in foreign language motivation between the public and private EFL teaching sectors arguing that these two sectors differ in terms of their learning objectives, teaching approach, teacher-learner roles, age group of the learners, and how strict they are regarding attendance. They applied Dörnyei's L2 Motivational Self System (2005) to examine its validity in two different contexts (public and private) within a single cultural setting, Iran. The ideal L2 self reflects the learner's beliefs on how they view their future self based on their goals and aspirations towards second language learning (Dörnyei and Taguchi, 2009).

Additionally, although extrinsic goals including tests and exams may arguably be pernicious to intrinsic motivation (see for example, Brown, 1990), Bandura and Schunk (1981) posit that exams serve as a robust *proximal*

motivator in language learning. They work as markers of progress yielding an instant incentive, self-induced motivation, and feedback, all of which help the learners to build and maintain effort. Moreover, proximal goal-setting improves intrinsic motivation through the satisfaction achieved from goal-attainment, which subsequently boosts the learner's self-confidence and self-efficacy (Dörnyei, 1994) and ultimately agency to change one's outcomes and future (Bandura, 2006). The evidence however, is contradictory. For example, a study by O'Sullivan (1990) showed that teenage students found that formal tests, along controlled tasks and drills as well as separate grammar sections, were demotivators. According to Dörnyei and Taguchi (2009, p. 29), the ought-to L2 self can be defined as "the attributes that one believes one ought to possess to meet expectations and to avoid possible negative outcomes". Ghanizadeh and Rostami's (2015) findings indicate that the role of attitudes to the L2 culture in ideal L2 self were borne out in the private sector but not in government-led schools, whereby instrumentality promotion had minimal influence on the L2 self. In private language institutes, instrumentality promotion was a strong predictor of the ideal L2 self. In another large-scale study of Iranian students learning English, which examined the effect of L2 motivational self on anxiety, a positive correlation was found between anxiety and the ought-to self (Papi, 2010).

Teachers as facilitators also have a role in student motivation. According to Dörnyei's (1994) framework of L2 motivation, teacher-specific components have to do with the teacher's personality, his/her teaching style, his/her relationship with students, and feedback (*ibid.*, p. 277). The most important motive of all, he adds, is the 'affiliative drive' (Ausubel, Novak, and Hanesian, 1978 cited in Dörnyei, 1994, p. 278), which refers to the learners' need to do well for the approval of a subordinate figure they like such as the teacher or the parents. Another motivational aspect of the teacher is his/her systematic socialisation of student motivation, which entails the teacher's attempt to actively stimulate and develop the students' motivation (*ibid.*). This, according to Dörnyei can be done

by ‘modelling’, ‘task presentation’, and ‘feedback’. In modelling, the teachers, whose role is to be the class leader, represent the class conscience, and the learners’ role, as a result, is to model their attitudes and orientations after those of their teachers’, in terms of both the amount of effort and interest in the subject. In the second channel, task presentation, the teachers role is to raise the students’ interest and metacognitive awareness of a given classroom task. This is done by drawing the students’ attention to the task objective(s), practical value, potential interest, and also suggest strategies that can be used to achieve the task and fulfil the objective(s). This channel of the socialisation process is in line with Bandura’s intentionality, an agentic property which involves creating an intention which, in turn, entails an action plan/strategy to fulfil such an intention (Bandura, 2006).¹ Finally, the third channel, feedback refers to two distinct types of feedback: informational and controlling (Dörnyei, 1994). Informational feedback assesses competence, whereas controlling feedback assesses performance based on specific external criteria. Dörnyei promotes the use of informational feedback, such a praise, which links success to the amount of effort and ability, and therefore can be achievable by the learner once again in the future. Praise, Dörnyei adds, should not have the characteristics of controlling feedback, whereby teachers compare the success or failure of one student to the others (external to the learner).

It is natural to include demotivation factors when discussing motivation as these two constructs play a key role in a learner’s learning process, albeit the former construct being a relatively more recent one. A learner’s motivation can be influenced by numerous negative influences. Dörnyei and Ushioda (2011) explain that a learner may become demotivated and lose interest and commitment, after once being motivated, due to a specific reason. They, thus, define demotivation as “specific external forces that reduce or diminish the motivational basis of a behavioural intention or an ongoing action. (*ibid.*,

¹See section 2.1.2.4 above for more details.

p. 139)". It is worth-noting that not all scholars agree that demotivators are exclusively external to the learners. Some scholars (for example, Falout and Maruyama, 2004; Arai, 2004) argue that there are internal factors which can demotivate learners, such as loss of self-confidence or negative attitude stemming from the learners. Some of the other demotivating factors which relate to teacher behaviours and from the learners' perspective include discontent with grading and assignments, the teacher being self-centred, unapproachable, biased, condescending, insulting, boring, bored, unorganised and unprepared, a dislike for the subject area, and the inferior organisation of teaching materials, the teacher not being knowledgeable, or having a sense of humour (Gorham and Christophel, 1992), teacher personalities, teaching methods (Falout and Maruyama, 2004; Arai, 2004). A study by Zhang (2007) on university students from a a range of cultural backgrounds, including the USA, Japan, China, and Germany, showed that the most prominent demotivator was teacher inadequacy. That includes "teachers' indifference to the students and/or the course ... confusing and/or boring lectures, unfair testing, and information overload (*ibid.*, p. 211). Similar findings were also found in a study by Oxford (2001) which concluded that the main teacher-related demotivators were the teachers' intra-personal relationships with learners which encompasses indifference, aggressive behaviour, condescension, preferential treatment towards some but not others, and being overly criticising. Additionally, it was found that the teacher's lack of enthusiasm towards the subject, close-mindedness, unpreparedness, the irrelevance of the material, the overload, and repetitiveness were also some of the motivators from a learner's perspective." In the area of foreign language acquisition, a study by Rudnai (1996), which included students from one elite and another vocational secondary schools, found that the primary cause of student demotivation was lack of self-confidence usually caused by negative past experiences (in another study this was most prominent among lower-proficiency learners (Falout and Maruyama, 2004)), being placed in a level inappropriate for

their level of proficiency, not having free choice, teachers lacking competence and skills required for language teaching, lacking of commitment for language learning in a comfortable and enjoyable environment. Another demotivating factor which does not relate to the teacher or learner, but the learning environment is the lack of adequate facilities (Dörnyei, 1998a), lack of positive English-speaking models (Tsuchiya, 2006a; Tsuchiya, 2006b). It was also mentioned earlier that the ‘affiliative drive’ was proposed to be the most significant motivator (Ausubel, Novak, and Hanesian, 1978 cited in Dörnyei, 1994, p. 278), suggesting that students’ need to perform well to gain their teacher’s or any other subordinate figure’s approval. If a learner fails to live up to their teacher’s or parents’ expectations, his/her self-confidence will be frustrated and thus feel demotivated (Falout and Maruyama, 2004).

2.2.2 Affect

Another socio-psychological factor affecting foreign language learning is *affect*. Affect in foreign language acquisition has been defined as a subjective feeling of uneasy suspense and tension, worrying and nervousness, all of which are simultaneously activated alongside the automatic nervous system (Rachman, 1998; Zheng, 2008). Specifically, foreign language anxiety involves negative emotions and is a rather individual feature, which can heavily impact learning (Ellis, 2006). The emotional reaction can stem from feelings about the language, its native speakers and/or their culture, or about the language classroom environment (Gass, Selinker, and Plonsky, 2013). Research has shown that anxiety can have two different effects: lower levels of anxiety can have a facilitating effect and higher levels of may have an debilitating effect (Mizruchi, 1991). Anxiety “can interfere with the acquisition, retention, and production of the new language” (MacIntyre and Gardner, 1991, p. 86). It can inhibit foreign language learning especially in oral tasks Zhang and Rahimi (2014). It can be triggered by several factors including personal and/or intra-personal problems -

such as communication apprehension - student-teacher interactions, classroom procedures, fear of negative feedback, assessment, and teacher and student views about learning (Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, 1986; Zhang and Rahimi, 2014). It is not yet known whether anxiety is a characteristic of personality, an emotional reaction to a specific situation, or both (MacIntyre, 2007). Horwitz (2001), MacIntyre (1999), and MacIntyre (2002) distinguish L2 learning anxiety from other types of anxiety including academic anxiety (Cassady, 2010). Anxiety can also be influenced by the specific situation a learner is in. A foreign language learner seeks to avoid or escape a situation which may cause discomfort or distress which thus leads to having lower amounts of the target language input and less interaction. A model which incorporates the affective factors of motivation and anxiety is Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis. According to this model, foreign language learning can be influenced by motivation and personality (Krashen, 1981): the affective variable anxiety correlates negatively with foreign language learning in that lower levels of anxiety lead to better learning and high levels inhibit learning (*ibid.*). The affective variable motivation has a different effect in that it correlates positively with foreign language learning; higher levels of motivation lead to better learning and vice versa (*ibid.*). In addition to the integrative and instrumental orientations explained above, Krashen integrates a third type of affect variable which is self-confidence. This affective variable, like motivation, correlates positively with foreign language learning. Krashen (*ibid.*) explains that these variables operate subconsciously and that the area of foreign language learning they impact the most is the communicative skills. He adds that learners in the least optimal affective state, that is when they are anxious or lacking motivation, have a mental filter, which prevents them from accessing the input to the fullest extent, and subsequently blocks further language acquisition. In such a state, they comprehend the input but the input is not processed appropriately in the language acquisition device (Stevick, 1976). Similarly in production, Brown (2001b) explains that,

One of the major obstacles learners have to overcome in learning to speak is the anxiety generated over the risks of blurting things out that are wrong, stupid or incomprehensible... Our job as teachers is to provide the kind of warm, embracing climate that encourages students to speak, however halting or broken their attempts may be. (Brown, 2001a, p. 269)

A study by Ziash (2013) in the Kazakhstani context revealed that Kazakhstani learners of L2 English have negative experiences with speaking activities in EFL classrooms, which can be attributed to the Kazakhstani educational system. The Kazakhstani EFL teachers argued that the educational system in Kazakhstan is not designed to increase the communicative competence of students which, in their opinion, led Kazakhstani EFL learners to have high levels of anxiety and embarrassment during speaking activities. The findings of the study showed that the activities which induced anxiety the most were being called out to the board, performing in front of others, anxiously waiting for their turn to speak, fear of speaking altogether, performing worse because of anxiety, loss of confidence during a speaking activity, getting tense and nervous, a continuous fear of forgetting what they had prepared to say, unfocused thoughts, volunteering answers, and teacher corrective feedback. von Wörde (2003) investigated the perspectives of foreign language learners from a variety of L2 backgrounds including French, German, and Spanish on foreign language anxiety. She found that among the main sources of anxiety in the foreign language classroom were their inability to comprehend what was said because the teacher either spoke too fast or would not use their L1 (English) at all, speaking activities, instructional practices, error correction especially when the teacher used a reprimanding tone or corrected before the students formed their response causing a disruption in focus, and finally the being negatively compared to the native speaker. In her learner participants' view some ways of reducing anxiety were having a sense of connectedness with the other learners in the class, having a relaxed classroom.

2.2.3 Authenticity

Another factor which presents itself in the EFL classroom is authenticity. If learners need to be prepared for successful real world communication, authenticity should have a key part in the EFL teaching system. The use of authentic materials and engaging in authentic activities can have substantial benefits for the EFL learners: first, it connects the classroom to the real world (Kelly et al., 2002), second, according to Nuttall (1996) using authentic materials can increase the level of motivation and engagement (Little, Devitt, and Singleton, 1988; Lee, 1995; Peacock, 1997) by showing the learners the language they are learning can be used in real life by real people, third, exposure to authentic listening and reading materials provides learners with native input required for real life communication (Nunan, 1997), fourth, research has shown that authentic materials allow the learners to bootstrap the target language more efficiently (Weyers, 1999) and that they have a positive impact on language attainment. Research findings show that using authentic listening materials significantly improves FL learners' performance and increased their level of motivation (Otte, 2006) and self-satisfaction (Bacon and Finneman, 1990; Otte, 2006). Improved listening skills as a result of exposure to authentic materials consequently leads to improved development of oral language (Bacon and Finneman, 1990; Otte, 2006), a faster rate of learning, improved level of self-confidence amongst learners (Harmer, 1994). There are several types of authenticity essential for language learning and teaching: authenticity of goal, environment, text, task (Candlin and Edelhoff, 1982), and authenticity of learner, which entails the learner acknowledging and accepting the former four types of authenticity (Nunan, 1997). Akbari and Razavi (2016) investigated EFL teachers' perspectives towards using materials in EFL classrooms in Iran against these benefits cited in the literature on authentic materials and they found that Iranian EFL teachers have positive attitudes towards them. Opponents of authenticity argue that the use of authentic materials in the EFL classrooms

pose difficulty for the EFL learners and that course designers ought to simplify materials to facilitate learning. Ellis (1999, p. 249) argues that, “learners receiving premodified input were able to learn and subsequently remember more new words than learners exposed to unmodified, ‘authentic’ input.” He supports his argument with Krashen’s Input Hypothesis (1985; 1994), which posits that only comprehensible input becomes part of a learner’s *intake*. Another criticism of authenticity is the idea that language and culture are inseparable and that one language does not necessarily reflect a single culture (Mishan, 2005). EFL textbooks published in English-speaking countries typically have culturally-biased materials reflecting a Western lifestyle, which may be criticised as being culturally unacceptable/ inappropriate in non-native contexts. Pinner (2016) argues that some notions of a foreign language may be un-learnable without a background of the culture which produced such notions. Mishan (2005) calls for the adaptation of culturally appropriate materials and by embedding an aspect of locality, of where the language is learned, that connects the concept of culture to where the target language is spoken. In terms of the environment, Breen (1985) adds the authenticity of the social situation inside the classroom as a further dimension in the authenticity discussion.

2.3 Assessment: definitions and views

Assessment, as a process, has been widely investigated within different educational (learning and teaching) theories (Black and Wiliam, 1998; Ketabi and Ketabi, 2014; Kissling and O’Donnell, 2015; Lealy et al., 2005; Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick, 2006; Taras, 2003; Wiliam, Lee, et al., 2004; Willis, 2011). This results in multiplicity of definitions that have different import and substance. What is important here to focus is the assessment related to ESOL. This type of assessment can be in broad terms defined as the process by which the performance/ achievement of a learner in a specific subject area is evaluated by means of formal or informal diagnostic tools to measure students’ progress,

within different language skills, including listening and speaking (Brindley, 2001, p. 138). In this regard, Brindley (*ibid.*) indicates that assessment refers to a wide variety of ways of collecting information on a learner's language ability or achievement, and hence the ability to decide whether the student is progressing or not. This so being, assessment, as a process, targets students in terms of their overall progress of a given skill (or all skills). Assessment is also seen as a tool to gauge students' progress gradually. It was not a product of this century but dates back to the previous centuries in general and the time of universities establishment in particular (O'Sullivan, 2012).

In Libya, students and graduates struggle mostly with oral and aural skills (Ahmad, 2001). Several studies investigated potential reasons for this phenomenon of learning difficulty especially with oral/aural skills in English. Some studies argue that the lack of communicative skills by the teachers and their social beliefs about their roles in the classroom are the primary factors contributing to the problem (Orafi and Borg, 2009). Meanwhile a study by Saleh and Zakaria (2013) suggests that the issue is related to assessment methods and students' exam preparation techniques, supporting Duff's (2001) argument that the problem is rooted in a lack of consistency in assessment methods.

2.3.1 English Language Assessment

Brindley (2001) provides a background account on the development of language assessment. He states that in the 1960s and 1970s language tests were designed to assess the proficiency in various linguistic domains/skills that range from phonology to grammar and vocabulary.

Approaches to designing appropriate assessment for language learning has been widely debated in the literature for some years (Brown, 1993; Brown, 2005; Brown, 2012; Cohen, 1994; Hughes, 2003; Madsen, 1983; McNamara, 1996; McNamara, 2001; Spolsky, 1985; Weir, 1993; Weir, 1993; Weir, 2005). While some differences in approach are evident, for example the Communicative

Language testing approach focuses on what a learner can do with language (for an overt purpose) rather than what/how much s/he knows about it (Morrow, 2018), alternative assessment is rather longitudinal in nature, involving learner and teacher (Hancock, 1994) and is used within the course of instruction monitoring the learner's progression (O'Malley and Pierce, 1996) and the task-based assessment approach that considers the task, rather than form, as its fundamental unit (Long and Norris, 2000) and assesses communicative acts in the context of meaningful and goal-directed language use (Ellis, 2003), there is general agreement that language assessment must be contextualized and relate to real life (Ellis, 2003; Morrow, 2018; Stiggins, 1987; Wiggins, 2011).

Some of these approaches (for example, task-based and alternative assessment, to name but a few) ascertain the importance of integrating ongoing assessment throughout the learning process a) to evaluate and monitor the learning progress of each learner, b) to reflect on and modify instruction according to the learner's needs and c) include the learner in his/her learning process. Most importantly, linking assessment to learning can determine course accountability (Katz, 2012). The seminal work by Black and Wiliam (1998) on Assessment for Learning lends support to formative assessment. This mode of assessment is based on supporting learning through effective feedback (*ibid.*). Several studies (Crooks, 1988; Kluger and DeNisi, 1996; Natriello, 1987; Nyquist, 2003) advocate and support Black and Wiliam's arguments for formative assessment. Marzano (2007, p. 13) further corroborates their work based on international evidence indicating that "the gains in achievement are amongst the largest ever reported for educational interventions". Gipps' (1999) inferences propose involving the learners in assessment of their own work and thus becoming autonomous learners. However, Foucault (1998) argues that mass education, instead of supporting learner autonomy, it considers

the body as a machine: its disciplining, the optimization of its capabilities, the extortion of its forces, the parallel increase of its usefulness and its docility, its integration in to systems of efficient and

economic controls (Foucault, 1998, p. 139).

Contrary to AfL's arguments on the focus on the learner/ learning, Biesta debates the difference between learning and education that are commonly viewed as synonymous. Biesta also contends for the role of the teacher.

In Libya, there seems to be an absence in the link between goals of a curriculum and learning outcomes. This is evident in that learners of English language in schools and universities struggle to communicate in real-life situations (Abu Srewel, 2002; Shihiba, 2011). Libyan learners of English sit tests/examinations at regular intervals throughout and at the end of the course of a programme in schools and/or universities. These are characterised as high stakes tests/exams, they neither inform instruction nor involve the learner.

In the next subsection, I will highlight factors affecting assessment in the Libyan context.

2.3.2 Factors affecting (and affected by) assessment in Libya

Assessment policy in Libya does not reflect the curriculum intentions (Orafi, 2008; Orafi and Borg, 2009). The curriculum reform in English is based on the Communicative Approach, however, exam materials do not test oral/aural skills (Orafi and Borg, 2009). One reason for this is the interplay of power relations in the educational context in Libya. To clarify what is meant by power, I adopt a Foucauldian account. Foucault (1980, p. 198) explains that, "power means relations... organized, hierarchical, co-ordinated cluster of relations". His perception of power (Foucault, 1977) in relation to the current study is threefold involving the concept of the PANOPTICON - the power of the gaze or hierarchical surveillance as he calls it – rhetoric, and the birth of discipline - in the form of normalised and standardised judgement.

Foucault's PANOPTICON was a new form of prison designed with a purpose in mind. It was designed as a big circle (see Appendix D, figure D.1), with cells

on the outside, and the guard in the middle. The guard has total view of the cells and the prisoners inside. He focuses on the prison for several reasons. Not only does its architectural design help develop the power of the state, but also the method, in which it exercises such power. The state founded the prison such that it had total domination over the prisoners, both physically, in the form of metal bars, and psychologically, in terms of the guard's ability to see prisoners, without their ability to see the guard. This is part of Foucault's discussion on the power of the gaze. The guards had the power of the gaze, and the prisoners did not. An analogy is made for educational institutions, where the learner is constantly gazed upon by the teacher especially during examinations.

Moreover, MacLure (2006, p. 9) asserts that higher authorities and agencies, which have the upper hand tend to dictate rigid criteria and protocols, by which education workers, of the whole spectrum, report their activities and assess their work and that of others. The teacher is monitored by higher authorities such as the school principle be it physically through small windows within doors (Foucault, 1977, p. 173) or in the form of pedagogical inspectors. As indicated on the Libyan Ministry of Education's website:

- The educational inspector does not spare any effort to *elevate* the teacher, and continuously cooperate with him/her.
- The educational inspector knows the competencies required by the teacher.
- It is not the educational inspector's job to search for mistakes or to *exercise authority* over teachers, to criticise, or to *write reports* that are not based on sound scientific and professional *criteria*.
- The educational inspector is a guide, who assists the teacher with professional growth, and *improve the level of his/her performance* in partnership and cooperation, and help to understand his/her job and achieve the educational goals in order to follow the educational process according to a *distinct methodology*.

- The educational inspector performs his/her duties on the basis of an educational professionalism above personal matters and *measures* the work of the teachers and their actions on an objective *scale*.
- The educational inspector *raises the morale of teachers*, and it is also his/her duty to provide a sense of security and reassurance among them and not to undermine confidence in them and/or in their professional abilities.
- Educational inspector focuses on positive aspects in the work of teachers and developing them and not only focuses on weaknesses, but works to motivate them to *correct their performance* instead of criticism and *punishment*.

To reflect on the above bullet-points which the ministry lists as the roles of the educational inspector, a reference to Foucault’s analysis of the power embedded in rhetoric/discourse – the two terms are used interchangeably in this study - is due. Discourse, according to Foucault is, “...ways of constituting knowledge, together with the social practices, forms of subjectivity and power relations which inhere in such knowledges and relations between them...” (cited in Weedon (1987, p. 102). Foucault also analyses discourse as, “a form of power that circulates in the social field and can attach to strategies of domination as well as those of resistance” (cited in Diamond and Quinby (1988, p. 185).

By a close examination of the discourse used by the ministry to specify the educational inspector’s role (italicised above). Words such as ‘elevate’ and ‘improve the level of his/her performance’ indicate a teacher’s qualification is not up to par with that of the inspector and that it requires elevating, upgrading and improving. The phrase ‘raises the morale of teachers’ indicates a pre-existing state of low morale. ‘Correct their performance’ is also indicative of a requirement for correcting something that is presumably wrong. These terms diminish the teacher by those one level above in the hierarchy. Terms such as, ‘criteria’, ‘measures’, and ‘scale’ elucidate Foucault’s notions of ‘normalised’, ‘standardised’ judgements, a facet of modern indoctrinated institutions where a

teacher undergoes assessment processes that reflect value judgements (*professional criteria*) that rely on a specific culture or historical point in time instead of being “‘objective’ neutral processes that allow a ‘true’ reflection of individual ability” (Crossouard, 2012, p. 189).

The inspector examines and monitors the teacher’s performance and competency in periodic visits throughout the year. One of the inspectors’ roles is to report to the Ministry of Education through a standardised teacher’s evaluation form of relevant criteria. MacLure (2006) further discusses the power relations embedded in discourse. She puts forward,

Education workers... in the inspection service... are obliged to report their activities and to assess themselves and others according to structures, categories and bullet-pointed lists of objectives that are substantially pre-written by the authority or agency that regulates their work (*ibid.*, p. 4).

Despite the explicit reference to the point that it is not the inspector’s role to punish (see the last point above), the evaluation form is marked on a scale ranging from ‘weak’ to ‘excellent’ and that the inspector’s final evaluation has serious consequences, that is reward or punishment, for the teacher, carried out by the Ministry of Education (Abdulali, 1987). Foucault (1977, p. 177) discusses how punishment has become habitual in disciplinary institutions, stating that “at the heart of all disciplinary systems functions a small penal mechanism”. Institutions such as educational ones, he further posits, are “subject to a whole micro-penalty of time, of activity, of behaviour, of speech, [and] of the body” (*ibid.*, p. 178). Punishment, thus, has become a power structure. Such conception of power leaves little room for agency or resistance from those under it.

In reference to the phrase above ‘achieve the educational goals in order to follow the educational process according to *a distinct methodology*’, MacLure (2006, p. 9) asserts that teaching operates in scripted regimes and that classroom discourse is static across different times and various cultures. In addition, the teacher-driven routines and recurrent themes reflect the asymmetries of power

and status. MacLure (2006, p. 4) referred to education workers, including students and teachers, as:

Work[ing] from packages that specify objectives for every activity; how long each activity should take (to the nearest minute); its position and reference number within a nested structure of sessions, units and modules; and which actions to perform... In many cases, the trainer or practitioner will even be told what to say.

Having taught in the system myself, syllabi for all subjects in schools, including English language, come in packages that contain teachers book, student book and workbook. However, teachers and students do not necessarily abide by the textbook's recommendations or prescriptions as MacLure indicates. There seems to be another power structure that comes into play. In Libya top to bottom instructions involve curriculum management and design, teacher training programmes, student numbers as per classroom, and even teaching methods (Gadour, 2006, pp. 173–5). MacLure (2006) observes that such contemporary educational policies are those of 'closure', which tend to 'repress' and 'control gaps', and envisage teachers as means of transferring packages of knowledge into the student's mind and assume uniform assimilation amongst learners. They view the curriculum as static knowledge which teachers and learners must adhere to without entitlement (*ibid.*, pp. 2–3). These curriculum packages, she proposes, are pinned by discourse of practice which "strips it of flexibility and sensitivity to context and local needs", a discourse that impedes reflection, weakens teacher agency and inhibits learner autonomy (*ibid.*, p. 7).

The National Office of Measurement and Assessment exerts rigid rules for teaching and assessment upon teachers and students (Asker, 2012). Teachers are obliged to conform to criteria and a time plan for test marks and carefully prescribed calculations for examinations (*ibid.*). Such technical and managerial, bureaucracies interfere with good educational intentions and judgements of teachers based on a focus on measurements rather than quality education (Biesta, 2009, p. 36). Students are also obliged to adhere to such power by means

of rewards that are based on these marks and results. The government's success reward policy grants overseas scholarships (undergraduate and postgraduate degrees) to students who finish top in secondary schools. This has shifted the learners' motivation from true learning into a motivation for gaining top grades (see Appendix D, figure D.2 for a recent (2017) copy of mandate 1532 issued by the Minister of Education). Foucault (1977) posits that a system which uses rewards and punishments creates gaps amongst individuals. The "[r]ank in itself serves as a reward or punishment" (*ibid.*, p. 181).

Foucault (*ibid.*) explains a shift in power as a result of what he describes as the birth of discipline. Disciplinary institutions use carefully collated data in a systematic way through learning about individuals and consequently establishing norms from each individual case. This knowledge is used by the state or whomever has control, in this case the Ministry of Education, to obtain power over individuals that is teachers and/or students, hence sovereignty. An example of such dynamic in an educational institution is that of the examination whereby a candidate is a 'case', who is 'compared with others, in his very individuality' (*ibid.*, p. 191). To put it differently, an individual, alongside his/her unique characteristics, is lost in these rather standardised testing formats, which are imposed by higher authorities. Foucault's notion of the disciplinary nature of testing refers to "the examination... a normalizing gaze, a surveillance that makes it possible to qualify, to classify, and to punish" (Foucault, 1984, p. 197). This leaves little room for reflection and creativity and instead produces disciplined, docile subjects.

In the case of Libya, these authorities, Ministry of Education, and the Department of Examination which works under it, aspire to different objectives from the ones intended by English language teaching curriculum designers. The mismatch is evident in, for example, examination content, on one hand, which relies heavily on testing students' ability to memorise language forms (Asker, 2012; Shihiba, 2011) rather than language use, specifically communicative and functional abilities and, on the other hand, the goal of curriculum reform, which

is meant to be based on Communicative Language Teaching principles.

Moreover, the teacher book designed by ELT curriculum designers recommends using alternative assessment, such as portfolios and journals, for example. However, pressure from the National Office of Measurement and Assessment by issuing rules of teaching/assessment has caused teachers to focus on a more systematic programme of formal/traditional assessment, which relies mostly on test marks (Asker, 2012).

Prescribed textbooks do not allow flexibility for teachers to prepare relevant materials based on learners' needs/interests. In Libya, the majority of teachers and students are dissatisfied with content of assigned textbooks (Shihiba, 2011, p. 288) despite the curriculum designers' claim that they are tailored to the Libyan teacher and student needs and interests (*ibid.*). Teachers are also required to finish predetermined set of contexts in due time based on laws and regulations issued by the relevant departments within the Ministry (Ministry of Education, 2018).

2.3.3 Learners' perspectives towards assessment and the impact of assessment context on learning

Learner's involvement in educational settings and enquiries is important in investigating assessment in relation to learning. One of the main purposes of educational research and practices lies in understanding student's learning and how it is shaped.

Recent findings challenged the long-held view that the educational context is what defines learner's approaches to learning (Entwistle, 1991; Joughin, 2003; Ramsden, 2003). Rather, they have argued that it is the learner's perspective towards the context in which educational practices occur is what shapes his/her learning. The learner's construction of reality is a major variable required to improve and understand learning especially at the level of post-compulsory education, i.e. secondary and higher education (Entwistle and Ramsden, 2015) (Struyven, Dochy, and Janssens, 2003). Relevant here is that students are

assumed to be aware of the specific characteristics of the context and, hence, they adopt their learning approaches accordingly (Biggs, 1989).

In order to understand the learner's perspective towards assessment, it is important to recognise where assessment stands in terms of the learning context in addition to the elements, which constitute learning. On the other hand, the latter includes the curriculum, which, in turn, involves content, objectives, teaching methods, climate for learning, and institutional requirements such as assessment. The Libyan learner of English as a foreign language is situated in a different context from those in other parts of the world. The Libyan learner is driven by exam practices, political factors that shape his/her attitude towards learning a foreign language. The Libyan learner lives in a special socio-cultural setting and has had a historical background that distinguishes it from other cultures and societies. In considering the learner and teaching attributes, it is important to discuss relevant Libyan attitudes towards learning English as a foreign language. According to (Brown, 2007) identity and motivation are critical features in learning a given language. Attitudes towards the target language community and towards the learning situation can be a predictor of motivation to learn the L2 (Gardner and Lambert, 1972). Libyans are known for their long resistance for colonisation throughout their history compared to other nationalities within the region (Hajjaji, 1967). For example, in Egypt, there has been a change in trends from negative to positive attitudes towards learning English as it is seen as tool for economic, social and educational growth (Imhoof, 1977). In Morocco, although English does not have an official status, it is a neutral language that carries no imperialistic undertones like French does (Errihani, 2017). In fact, in Arabic countries in North Africa, such as Morocco, Tunisia and Algeria, French is the dominant language albeit not official (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017).

The enforced language policies by colonisers in the past and punishment that ensued for using the Libyan's native language in an attempt to limit the Arabic

identity and language (Hajjaji, 1967; Youssef, 2012) has arguably caused a negative attitude towards foreign language (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017). Moreover, the American military engagements against Muslim countries has been argued to have contributed towards this negative attitude towards foreign languages (Youssef, 2012) as well as maintaining outdated teaching methods in teaching it (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017). Another factor contributing to this attitude amongst teachers is claimed to be the low income that teachers in general receive (Ibrahim, 2015; Mahjobi, 2007) and the absence of financial motivations for teaching, such as career promotions (Allag, 2004). Zainol Abidin, Pour-Mohammadi, and Alzwari (2012) study on EFL students' attitudes towards learning English language in Libyan secondary schools also revealed negative attitudes towards learning English. They attribute this to the traditional method of instruction. This is also attested in university education in Libya where teachers adopt the Libyan version of Grammar-Translation method since there is a lack of guidelines with regards to materials and/or teaching method (Elabbar, 2011). Reasons for this choice of teaching method is attributed (*ibid.*) to a very low demand on specified teaching skills and that it is easier to test and score objectively since it relies on memorisation of grammar rules and translation (Brown, 2007). These findings are validated by Ibrahim's (2015) action research. He incorporated the Communicative Approach to his experimental group and as a result, students in this group developed more positive attitudes towards learning English.

With the socio-political reform, introduced in the 1990s in Libya, which involves accessibility to the international community, some researchers anticipated change in the attitude towards learning foreign languages. Alhmali's (2007) study concluded that there is an increase in Libyan EFL learners' interest in learning English compared with other curricular subjects in school as a result of the learners' perception that English allows them accessibility to the outside world through the Internet, which allows them to have friendships from other

countries. Turki (1994) observes that although school students held positive attitudes towards English as a global language, the effort they invested in learning was low. Omar (2013), in this regard, points out that a reiterated statement, which reflects Libyan learners' attitude towards learning English is, "learning English is not easy at all" (*ibid.*, p. 27). Another study by Mahjobi (2007) reported similar results, although he attributes this to the fact that his participants did not reside in the capital city, Tripoli, where socio-cultural change is allegedly most effective. Speaking English outside the classroom is discouraged by families in that the speaker can be subject to derision and/or accused of "showing off" (Omar, 2014, p. 122).

However, Asker (2012) reports a different trend in attitudes, positive, amongst freshman English majors who had just finished a three-year programme of English-speciality secondary school. He describes them as,

remarkably different from what I have experienced before ... more enthusiastic to learn, they asked more, and generally had a more positive attitude to English learning than the students who came from the old general secondary schools and who had only studied English as a compulsory subject (*ibid.*, p. 1).

Similar positive attitudes held by EFL school teachers about integrating English culture in their classrooms are also reported (Ahmed, 2015). However, whether they actually incorporate it is a different issue (*ibid.*).

In other Arabic countries such as those in the Arabian Gulf, people in general have positive attitudes towards English language seeing it a vehicle for economic growth and prosperity (Kirkpatrick and Barnawi, 2017). Parents have called for introducing English language education to their preschool children as well as admitting them to immersion schools (*ibid.*).

2.3.4 Learner and teacher perspectives towards oral practice and assessment

Omar (2014) carried out an extensive study on teacher perspectives on teaching English in Government-led schools in Libya (in public schools not private centres). He asked teachers about challenges relating to teaching and asked students about challenges faced in learning. His data reveal several insights, of which I select those relevant to oral practice and assessment. His teachers revealed challenges pertaining to the dominant use of Arabic as the language of instruction (*ibid.*, p. 144) due to teachers lacking a good level of fluency/proficiency, which in turn is attributed to the limited opportunities/encouragement to practice the language outside the classroom. In cases where the teacher is proficient, students cannot cope (*ibid.*), due to the learners' lack of an appropriate level of proficiency (Orafi, 2008; Orafi and Borg, 2009; Abuklaish, 2014). This raises the issue of whether the teacher is capable of assessing oral skills objectively given that s/he is not proficient enough to speak the language let alone assess it. There seems to be a relationship between the teaching context, that is in a public sector vs a private one, and an EFL teacher's language proficiency. A study which compared the amount of L1 use between public school teachers, private language institute teachers, and teachers working in both private language institutes and public schools in an Iranian context (Gholami, Sarkhosh, and Abdi, 2016) found that teachers with experience in public schools only used their L1 in English language classrooms significantly more often than those who work in both public schools and private language institutes, who in turn, use their L1 significantly more often than those who work solely in private language institutes.

Another reason for avoiding practising oral skills, Omar (2014) reports, is the lack of a language lab/equipment such as CD players, Internet access, computer machines, or headsets (*ibid.*). His data reveal that although curriculum packages refer teachers to using sections from CDs, the school does not provide them

(*ibid.*). Similar findings are reported by Abuklaish (2014). Additionally, the lack of appropriate education environment has also been reported (Abuklaish, 2014; Omar, 2014). Overcrowded classrooms prevent teachers from mobilising freely or rearranging students in groups where they can have group discussions (Omar, 2014). As indicated by Wood, Linsky, and Straus (1974, p. 533), “foreign languages cannot be taught in large classes”.

Practising speaking poses a challenge in such environment as teachers are not able to supervise the speaking practice for every individual student (*ibid.*). It can be argued that a solution to this could be peer-assessment or pair/group-work activities. Gholami, Sarkhosh, and Abdi (2016) explored differences in the duration of pair-work and group-work activities between private language school teachers, public school teachers, and teachers with experience in both sectors. They found that private school teachers spent more class time running pair work and group work activities compared to either public school teachers or teachers with experience in both sectors. However, in Libya, classrooms are teacher-centred (Elabbar, 2011) and it is believed to be the teacher’s role to perform such duties (Orafi and Borg, 2009).

If learners/teachers do not have access/exposure to native input inside the classroom, it is not surprising that learners do not do well in international tests. The Libyan education policy’s negligence towards such aspects has detrimental consequences on Libyan learners in that it creates unequal opportunities for them to engage in international affairs. For Libyans who can afford to travel abroad to improve their language or to study in private language centres, it can have the potential to further divide Libyans within the same community, the haves and have-nots.

Because teachers lack training programmes especially with the curriculum reform, it is highly unlikely that they are familiar with oral assessment practices. Oral assessment is one of the most difficult skills to assess according to Madsen (1983). Another challenge is the aspect of whose English is to be tested. Krashen

defines three circles of English and Libya falls within the Expanding Circle. This makes it problematic for the teaching, learning, and subsequently testing: the pluralistic and diverse nature of English poses the challenge of deciding whose norms should be taught. Moreover, in relation to assessing English as an international language, the debate about whose norm to use revolves around a choice between Standard English (Davies, Hamp-Lyons, and Kemp, 2003) and World Englishes (Lowenberg, 2002). Canagarajah (2006, p. 230),

calls for a complex orientation that moves the discourse on assessing English to a different level [that is] the new orientation to norms and proficiency that inform assessment. It becomes clear that we have to reconsider the dominant paradigms of testing based on single varieties of English, grammaticality judgments, and a display of formal competence. This is a call to creatively devise new instruments that address our emerging communicative needs.

Libyans do not have access to English the same way other learners from different parts of the world do. This creates unfair opportunities as it discriminates learners from different linguistic and political backgrounds on the basis of their countries' politics. Similar concerns have raised with regards to Palestinian and Israeli students (see Or and Shohamy, 2017). In addition, Kachru and Nelson (2006, p. 28) argue that,

[i]n the nations of the Expanding Circle, English has limited roles in the public life, basically in higher education in science and technology, and very restricted functions in the personal domain.

Razmjoo and Riazi (2006) question the practicality of implementing the CLT approach in the Expanding Circle. They argue that EFL teachers' attitudes on CLT practice rely on how they perceive and conceptualise the approach. They compared the private sector and the public sector and found that although teachers from both sectors had positive attitudes towards the CLT approach, only the teachers in the private sector implemented it. This demonstrates that language use in these two sectors which are both from the same context of the Expanding Circle is a strong predictor of the implementation of the CLT approach. The public

sector does not require students to develop communicative oral competence since it probably does not test it.

However, when it comes to private language centres, in the absence of the majority of these constraints – since the learner’s motivation to learn English comes within and the teachers are not as constrained by external influences – such as the Ministry of Education – that impact their choice of practices nor assessment methods — it is not clear the extent to which these factors influence English language learning. Despite its significance in English language teaching and learning this issue had not received its due attention. The literature exploring these factors in the private sector is still in its infancy. The majority of studies started in the late 2000s and are heavily focused on, but not restricted to, the Iranian context which like Libya is a part of the Expanding Circle (Kachru, 1985) where English is practised as a Lingua Franca (Graddol, 2006). A study by Razmjoo and Riazi (2006) investigated the attitude of Iranian teachers from both the public and private sectors towards the Communicative Language Teaching approach and also teachers of which sector implemented it. The first private language school was established in the early 20th century in Iran (Farzin-nia, 1964), but owing to the Islamic Revolution in 1977, this language institute underwent some changes: the management, objectives, syllabi, and it was renamed from Iran-America society to Iran Language Institute (*ibid.*) suggesting an anti-American/Western attitude. Their findings indicate that teachers from both sectors had positive attitudes towards CLT: they viewed group-work being an essential component of the ELT classroom, for example. They viewed grammar tasks as a means not a goal, they encouraged self-directed learning, feedback should focus on appropriateness not accuracy, errors are tolerated as they are an integral part of the process, and that the teacher’s role is a facilitator. However, when it comes to assimilating beliefs into practice, Razmjoo and Riazi (2006) found that only teachers from the private sector implemented a quasi-CLT version of the approach. Public schools teachers argued that large

classrooms were a major obstacle in practising the CLT principles. In real practice the public school teachers placed the least emphasis on the importance of oral skills and authentic materials in CLT practice. The researchers attribute these discrepancies between attitude and practice to either that the teachers are claiming one thing and doing another or the limitations they face to implement their views in real practice. Gholami, Sarkhosh, and Abdi (2016) further probed the teaching practices of public and private EFL teachers in Iran, but in their study they included teachers with experience in both sectors and they looked into further EFL practices. They sought to explore the role of the context in influencing teaching practices, how the teachers vary in their coping strategies, and how well these groups of teachers maintain their practices in the light of the varying contextual (private vs public) challenges. They compared their three groups of participants, that is teachers with public school experience only, those with private institutes experience only, and those with both public and private sector experience. They compared the classroom practices of those groups in terms of group and pair work, teacher talking time, use of L1, questioning, corrective feedback, and how well the teachers covered the range of language skills. Their findings show that the three teacher groups varied significantly in terms of the points of practice mentioned above: first, within the public sector teachers with public/private experience varied significantly from those with public experience only apart from the time spent on pair and group work activities, explicit correction, and amount of repetition. The teachers who had experience in both private and public sectors spent less time using their L1 and talking time compared to the ones working in the public sector only, but both spent significantly more time using their L1 and talking time compared to the teachers working solely in private language schools. Teachers with public school and public-private school experience used their first language to provide corrective feedback and to explain grammar rules. They also found that listening activities were not part of EFL classroom practice in the public sector

irrespective of whether the teacher had experience in the public sector only or the public and private sector. The private sector only teachers spent significantly the longest time on pair and group work activities suggesting that the students had more talking time compared to those in the public sector. It is argued that maximising student talking time promotes learner autonomy (Harmer, 2006). The higher use of L1 in the public sector is arguably caused by a plethora of reasons: the lack of placement tests, class size, Government-imposed textbooks, which do not consider the difficulty of text or its readability on students varying abilities, and also the lack of policy on L1 use in EFL classrooms (de la Campa and Nassaji, 2009). Gholami, Sarkhosh, and Abdi (2016)'s findings also indicate that in private language schools, questioning techniques were used considerably more often than in public schools suggesting that students in private schools had more interactive classes, more opportunities to produce language, and thus more learning as a result of more practice and feedback. Teachers with private sector experience only outperformed those working in public schools (be it with public sector only or public and private sector experience) in terms of corrective feedback suggesting their classes are more communicative. Sadeghi and Richards (2015) argue that in Iran, Spoken English practice is identified as discussion skills only, the nature of which is not clearly defined or understood. Fluency in spoken English is a requirement for social interaction, travel, work, business and education purposes, all of which are varied and require different skills set and strategies. The skills required for one situation may not be directly transferable to another. They critique the approach used to teach spoken English in Iranian EFL classes arguing that, "in language classrooms, the teaching of speaking skills has often misrepresented the nature of spoken English and spoken interaction, and, as a result, speaking classes are most often little more than unfocused discussion sessions, with little real teaching of what oral proficiency in spoken English entails". On a different note, Farooqui (2007) argues that in Bangladesh, students enrolling in private and public universities have the same level of

proficiency upon entry, but towards the end of the undergraduate years, students studying in private universities outperform their peers from public universities in their English language proficiency. She investigated the EFL teaching practices in private universities, as to how they help their students to develop English language skills, what obstacles students encounter in speaking practice and how they overcome these obstacles, all from the teachers' perspectives. Her findings show that in private universities in Bangladesh, teachers are not obliged to follow a particular textbook for teaching English. The course outline is fixed but teachers can choose any materials they see fit. She also found that the language of instruction is English, students are only allowed to speak in English inside and outside the classroom, oral summative assessment takes place during and at the end of the module, students have access to facilities such as a language laboratory, where they can practise listening and speaking, including self-access centres and language clubs, and also students can partake in various competitions arranged by the university. The problems that arose in her findings from the teachers' perspectives were that students typically have a small vocabulary repertoire, they do better in reading and writing than they do in speaking², inertia owing to shyness from peers, and that students do not see themselves speaking English outside the university as the majority of the Bangladeshi population is monolingual. Furthermore, her teacher participants blamed the public sector for ignoring oral skills and that in the EFL classes in the public sector, teachers only used their L1 for EFL instruction and students rely completely on rote memorisation. They are not taught or given the opportunity to think or be creative before they write or speak. The lack of basic speaking proficiency makes it challenging for teachers to practise oral activities with their students. Another study by Diaz Larenas, Rodriguez Moran, and Poblete Rivera (2011) compared teaching styles and personality types of English language teachers in the public and private sectors in Chile. Their findings

²This is because their Senior Secondary School Certificate tested their reading and writing skills only even though the books are based on the CLT approach.

revealed that instructors from the public sector had a facilitator teaching style, congruent with the principles of the CLT approach, and that they had an extrovert type of personality. Teachers from the private sector showed the opposite personality type being more introverted and authoritative.

As such, a theoretical framework is needed, which would address the process of learning and teaching, as it would emphasise the importance of assessment practices in these, as well as provide a critical lens, through which the issues identified earlier can be explored and critically examined.

To this end, my analysis of the literature and my understanding of the situation in Libya leads me to the conclusion that these are central questions that need to be asked. The main area I want to research is identifying the strategies used for oral practice and assessment in Libyan private language centres from the perspectives of teachers and students working/enrolled in these centres. The question I ask is how 'best practice' in English language learning and assessment is understood in the Libyan context and the research questions of the present thesis are thus:

1. What is the role and effectiveness of the practice of oral assessment in developing authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya?
2. What are the similarities and differences between lecturers' and students' perspectives towards the strategies used in the development of authentic spoken language assessment in private language centres in Libya?
3. What are the implications of the findings?

Chapter 3: Methods

3.1 Introduction

According to many pertinent studies (for example Podolefsky, Moore, and Perkins, 2013), the design of a study is the most important component of research. This comes with no surprise given that the design of the study is robustly tied to the objectives the study ought to achieve. In order to insure that a given study has a well-made design, the study methodology is required to meet the research demands its design imposes (Yin, 2018). Having said that, a study with assessment-based purposes is different from, say, one with linguistics-based purposes. In this section, the methods followed in conducting this work will be discussed, most specifically the methods through which the lecturers' and students' perspectives towards the strategies used in oral practice and assessment in Libya.

With the intention to obtain a high level of presentation of the work methods, the main research paradigms examined will be delved into, including the positivistic paradigm, the phenomenological paradigm, subjective vs. objective research approaches, and deductive and inductive theory. The treatment of these approaches is restricted here, on account of space, to giving definitions and some descriptions of these related concepts. Afterwards, the data collection methods used in the current research will be elaborated on, which are mainly in conducting semi-structured interviews with both students and lecturers/instructors. Next, the sample will be described, the procedure will be explained in detail, and the ethical consideration pertinent to the current study will be covered.

3.2 Research Design and Research Methodology

It is important to explain in simple terms the definitions of the research design, research method, and the research methodology for their underlying relationships to the work. That is also motivated by the fact that these concepts, once demarcated, can help reach a deeper understanding of their interactions

with one another on the one hand, and how this interaction impacts on the general framework of this study on the other (Marczyk, De Matteo, and Festinger, 2005).

To begin with, research design is defined as the science of establishing and planning specific steps (better known as schemata or ‘procedures’) so as to conduct the research at issue (Yin, 2018). This being the case, the research design is not an unorganised step, rather a systematic procedure with clear stages. In this regard, Collis and Hussey (2013), among others, regard research design as an overarching stage of research, most notably in education. By an appropriate research design, the researcher makes use of a principled guide by which he/she can yield reliable results. In a related vein, Yin (2018) argues that the research design must be conceived as ‘a blueprint’ with the goal to assist the researchers in working out any problem they might face during the implementation of their work. Accordingly, the research design is considered an essential step that guided the researcher while collecting, interpreting, and analysing the data (Frankfort-Nachmias and Nachmias, 1992).

Another significant concept, to be distinguished from research design, is the research methodology. Research methodology is best seen as an overall approach adopted to facilitate the research process (Hussy and Hussy, 1997). It extends from the first stages of the research such as data collection to the final stages including the analysis of the data. Hussy and Hussy (*ibid.*), among others, stress that methodology must be determined with reference to time, place, objective, data collection and the strategies by which the data collected are analysed. Crucial here is the fact that confusion sometimes occurs when differentiating between methodology (as a concept) and the methods (as a concept).

Many studies have indicated that this confusion is caused because of different definitions, which were associated with these terms in educational disciplines and even in any other humanities and social sciences (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). Wolcott (2002) argues that the main difference between these two concepts lies

in the notion of dependence. That is, the methods, as concepts, rely on the methodology in that the latter provides the philosophical groundwork for methods, not vice versa. Wolcott (2002) means that both methodology and methods are two distinct concepts. However, methods of one research depend on the methodology of that research in justifying why such methods are appropriate. The methodology is concerned with the theory of how research must be conducted, hence methodology is the philosophical basis for the methods adopted in the research, whilst methods are the techniques and the rules used to collect data and carry out the analysis within the general framework of the methodology (*ibid.*).

Given that the current chapter deals with the methodology and the methods of the current research and how they should be set up, it is beneficial to brief on research philosophy and the related paradigms from which the methodology in general is derived.

3.3 Research Philosophy

There are two philosophical perspectives, which oppose one another in deciding on a suitable research design the work under discussion must follow. These two approaches are positivism and phenomenology (Collis and Hussey, 2013). Other works identify these two terms alternatively as quantitative and qualitative approaches, respectively. To start with the former, several definitions have been given to the positivist paradigm. One commonly quoted definition is that of Denscombe (2014, p. 299) who defined the positivist paradigm as an approach, which attempts to apply the natural science model of research to investigation of the social world. Positivism is seen as a connection between the social world and phenomena, on the one hand, and the natural scientific model of investigation, on the other. The quantitative methods of the positivist approach may be applicable to the social world by using, for example, large-scale social surveys (Benton and Craib, 2010). In this paradigm, there is no difference between social sciences and natural sciences either in terms of the main aim as

well as the method used to analyse and interpret the data. Positivism, being objective, aims at bridging the gap between social sciences and natural sciences by applying quantitative methods on social data.

On the other hand, the phenomenological paradigm or the qualitative paradigm is distinguished by the assumption that objectivity is not a property of social science investigation. The researchers in this paradigm believe that the social sciences are characterised by subjectivity in nature. The phenomenological paradigm is subjective, whereas positivism is objective (Collis and Hussey, 2013). This is because phenomenology resides on the idea that social reality is an artefact of the mind, it is multiple, and it can be influenced by the investigation process and the *perception* of reality (*ibid.*). Positivism on the other hand, relies on quantitative methods which measure frequencies and consider social realities to be independent of and unaffected by the investigation process (*ibid.*). In this regard, Remenyi et al. (1998) postulate that the phenomenological paradigm pays much attention to meaning rather than facts and is characterised by its way of considering the totality of the situation under investigation. Here induction is the way of analysis and in bringing about the needed evidence either to attest the hypothesis or even to reject it. For this reason, some authors have argued that the phenomenological paradigm is more appropriate to the social sciences whose nature necessitates the researcher to be somehow involved in the investigation not to be totally separated from the process of investigation as is the case in positivism (Wolcott, 2002).

The discussion thus far might imply the difference between deduction and induction as tools for reasoning. Deduction is concerned with the potential relationship between theory on one hand and the social sciences on the other hand. In this kind of reasoning, the researcher observes a particular phenomenon, he or she sets out a theory and advances a hypothesis in an attempt to account for his or her observation in the first place. Afterwards, the researcher becomes involved in the process of data collection and analysing and

interpreting the data he/she collected. Once the findings arise, the researcher is able to either attest his or her advanced hypotheses or reject them. In light of this confirmation or rejection of the advanced hypotheses, the research can revise the theory he/she postulates to account for his or her initial observation (Goel, 2007). Deductive reasoning is strongly associated with qualitative research whose nature can be investigated using the steps adopted in this kind of reasoning.

On the other hand, induction (or inductive reasoning) is different from deduction in the way in which the research is carried out (Arthur, 1994). As clearly evident in the discussion above in deductive reasoning, the theory comes prior to the data collection or findings. However, the picture is mirrored when it comes to the inductive reasoning where data collection and the findings come prior to the theory (Heit, 2000). The researcher in the inductive approach collects the required data, analyses and interprets them according to the methodology that he/she uses, and afterwards he/she draws the findings based on the his/her analysis of the data. In a further step, the researcher sets forth his/her theory depending on the findings of his/her research. This type of reasoning (i.e., induction) is strongly related to quantitative research whose first step, generally speaking, is data collection and observation. Against this background, the following study questions and how I approached them will be explored.

3.4 Research Questions

It was shown in Chapter 2 that the conception of oral English assessment practice in the context of privately-run language schools is overlooked especially in the absence of major power relations which exist in government-led institutions. There is a lack of understanding of what factors influencing English language learning in such contexts in spite of its importance for English language teaching and learning. Hence, a theoretical framework that enables us to address the process of learning and teaching is required not only to draw attention to

these conceptions and relative practices but also as a critical lens that helps identify and examine issues presented in Chapter 2. To examine the perspectives of teachers and students on the development of authentic spoken language through oral assessment practice in private language centres in Libya, we ask the following questions:

1. What is the role and effectiveness of the practice of oral assessment in developing authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya?
2. What are the similarities and differences between lecturers' and students' perspectives towards the strategies used in the development of authentic spoken language assessment in private language centres in Libya?
3. What are the implications of the findings?

In order to answer these three primary questions, qualitative methods of research were adopted in the current study. It should be made clear that I selected such methods for a host of reasons. First and foremost, on surveying the related literature, one observes that there are few studies addressing this specific topic at the level of Libya. A matter though unwelcome it gives this study significance and prominence. Several studies highlight the use of qualitative methods of research when the topic is new, given that a holistic view on the relevant data is needed (Neuman, 2011; Patton, 1990; Patton, 2005). Additionally, considering that the topic under discussion might be affected by different factors, qualitative research seems to be the right option since it is interested in exploring the complex interrelationships between several variables including power relations and discovering meanings and interpretations (Rowley, 2012).

In a related vein, Creswell (2014) argues that qualitative research approach is interested in exploring the events and data through observation and analysis of events, attitudes, photographs, and verbal and non-verbal communication. Because the main interest here is to explore the understanding of the dynamics

surrounding oral practice and assessment used in language centres in Libya to assess students' oral proficiency in English, I think that the best way to investigate this is through conducting interviews with the language instructors and students who are part of these centres. The qualitative research approach reflects the subjective aspects of people's doings through focusing on the meaning rather than the measurement of the social phenomena (Higson and Blake, 1993).

In qualitative research, there are two major ways of collecting the data, namely interviews and observation. The former was selected for collecting data, following Runch (2005), since the interview is one of the most powerful data collection methods in the qualitative research approach due to the fact that during interviews large amounts of data can be collected quickly. Although many definitions were given to the term 'interview' as a tool in the qualitative research approach, Frey and Oishi's (1995) definition of interview is common. They define the interview as a purposeful conversation in which one person asks questions (the interviewer) and another answers them (respondent or the interviewee). What is important here is to capitalise on several papers (Creswell, 2014; Polit and Beck, 2006; Whiting, 2008) that differentiate between structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews (Whiting, 2008).

The main difference between these three types of interviews lies in whether the questions to be asked to the respondent are pre-determined or not and the ways in which the interaction is managed (Moore, 2000). In structured interviews, there is a list of predetermined questions to be asked to each respondent in the same manner. Semi-structured interviews have prepared questions in advance but with open nature, so the interviewer can ask other (new) questions according to the respondent's reply (*ibid.*). According to Easterby-Smith, Thorpe, and Lowe (2002), one of the main purposes of such interviews is to develop an understanding of the respondents' world so that the researcher might influence it independently or collaboratively. Such a type of interviews is used when the interviewee might be reluctant to be truthful and the

subject matter is highly confidential (*ibid.*) or when the type of the data to be collected needs a sort of flexibility (step-by-step logic of a situation). The third type of interview is unstructured which is characterised by being informal with open question with no pre-determined questions (See, Oppenheim (1992) for further information about this type of interviews and the aims of their use).

In this study, semi-structured interviews were used. In this regard, several authors have argued that semi-structured interviews are a very useful method used to collect data. Following Sorrell and Redmond (1995), Whiting (2008) states that semi-structured interviews give the interviewer the opportunity to elicit some extra information, depending on the interviewee's replies, which are important for the purposes of the given research. As such, the interviewer might allocate some space to the interviewee or even give him or her some control on the stream of information. Whiting (*ibid.*) argues that it has been advanced that the interviewer usually maintains control over the interviewee in structured interviews, asking questions, but contributing little else. Several other researchers have stated that trying to control the interview process does not give the needed credit and respect to the role of participants, since they are treated as if they are there just waiting to produce data. Semi-structured interviews are useful tools to overcome these obstacles and barriers placed on the participants. However, sometimes some control over the participants is needed; thus, semi-structured interviews as a tool are considered to be better than structured and unstructured ones.

3.5 Theoretical Framework

Graduates from Libyan public schools and universities, despite studying English over an extended period of time, do not seem to be successful in acquiring satisfactory communicative English language skills (Ahmad, 2001). They find it difficult to implement their English language knowledge in real life situations in spite of their university education, in which they study English

language as a compulsory subject (Abu Srewel, 2002). The same is true for English language majors in Libya (Shihiba, 2011). Orafi and Borg (2009) argues that the curriculum reform introduced in Libya in 2000 is pedagogically challenging for teachers to deliver in EFL classrooms and is further challenged by their lack of English communicative skills required to deliver its content in English. This has led to the poor English speaking and communication skills amongst graduates (*ibid.*).

If students were to use English proficiently in the real life situations, they are required to use English communicatively and have good language skills, especially oral/aural skills (Omar, 2014). The importance of acquiring good comprehension and speaking skills of authentic English has heightened the value of private centres to train Libyan students to effectively and successfully communicate in English (Najeeb, 2013). Oral skills, both listening and speaking, are the skills whereby Libyan students experience the most issues (Ahmad, 2001). Therefore, we must invest further in scrutinising this context and the reasons Libyan EFL students find oral skills difficult to learn (Ibrahim, 2015). Some studies attribute this weakness to various reasons, including the strategies used for English language instruction and teaching, whilst others focus the attention on factors relating to assessment methods and how students prepare for the exams (Saleh and Zakaria, 2013). Yet, other studies argue that the issue stems from the lack of consistency in oral assessment of English language learning (Duff, 2001). Orafi and Borg (2009), on the other hand argue that it is the result of poor English communicative proficiency amongst Libyan EFL teachers.

It has been noticed from the studies above that the outcome of teaching oral/aural skills is generally poor in Libyan public schools and universities due to the fact that students have difficulties in communicating authentic English in an authentic context. The current study attempts to investigate this issue in private English language centres. Therefore, all of those involved in this process (i.e. students and teachers) were interviewed regarding their perspectives of the

strategies used in the development of English language assessment in the Libyan context and what the role and effectiveness of oral assessment is in developing authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya. The theoretical underpinnings of the approach adopted in this study was linked to two theories; Assessment for Learning (AfL) and Bandura's Social Cognitive Learning Theory (SCLT). Both theories and their pillars and how they are related to the current study will be explored next.

3.5.1 Assessment for Learning (AfL)

Assessment for Learning also referred to as formative assessment, has been widely adopted by educational institutions all over the world ((Klenowski, 2009; Stobart, 2008). Researchers argue that AfL is supported by empirical evidence in Black and Wiliam's 1998 seminal work and in subsequent research studies (for example Harlen and Deakin Crick, 2003; Stobart, 2008). Formative assessment has been repeatedly shown to yield a positive impact on the students' motivation, active engagement, and self-efficacy (Hayward and Spencer, 2010; Black, Harrison, and Lee, 2003).

Black and Wiliam (2009, p. 7) demonstrate five essential practices for the successful implementation of formative assessment. These are namely sharing success criteria with learners, questioning, feedback in the form of comment-only marking, peer- and self-assessment, and formative use of summative tests. Additionally, there are three essential stages which represent the cyclical process of formative assessment in classrooms. These stages represent a unifying basis of the practices discussed above (Wiliam and Thompson, 2007) and expressed rather efficiently in Ramprasad's (1983) model of learning and teaching as shown in figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Ramprasad's model of learning and teaching

These stages in the process are socially constructed given that they involve three types of agents, namely the teacher, the learner and his/her peers (Järvelä and Järvenoja, 2011). Thus, it seems promising to evaluate the quality of practising and assessing authentic spoken English in private centres in Libya in light of the above mentioned five key practices of formative assessment, despite the challenges formative assessment faces in the literature. Perhaps the biggest challenge to formative assessment relevant to the current study is that presented by Crossouard (2012) in her commentary on formative assessment. She opens her analysis with the following statement,

...what might become of formative assessment if it was to attempt to attend more explicitly to the wider social contexts, which frame institutionalised learning, and thus take on a more political guise (*ibid.*, p. 188).

Crossouard's commentary reflects the views of Foucault (1977) who asserts that the key motivation for assessment is to control mass education, its goals and rewards, and therefore to gain power. Assessments that are designed by individuals who come from a specific socio-economic background, ethnic group, gender, and language background tend to reflect the values, cultures, and experiences of the designers (Gipps, 1999). It is because knowledge is defined by their beliefs and views and not because they know better. Therefore, these tests disguise such inequalities by legitimising them (*ibid.*).

The Libyan EFL learner as well as teacher equally work from course packages designed by authors from a different cultural and linguistic background against which English language learning, teaching and assessment are formed (MacLure, 2006). It is not because English language and culture is better than their native language and/or culture. It is simply because it is the language of the globe (Graddol, 2006). Libyan learners do not perform well in international language proficiency tests such as IELTS or TOEFL, for example (Abuklaish, 2014; Omar, 2014). These standardised tests make use of standardised English such as Standard British English or Standard American English, which thus create inequities between native and non-native speakers and further amongst natives whose dialect is not the standard. Performance in international tests is thus influenced by a) socio-cultural factors such as poverty – allowing those who are financially-capable to attend training courses and excluding those who are less financially capable from attending the same courses – and the mismatch between language and culture (Gipps, 1999), that is, a mismatch between Arabic native speakers’ social and cultural background and that of the English language they are learning.

Wiliam (2011) has a rather defensive stance against these views. He ascertains that the end goals of formative assessment and summative assessment should not be confused. He argues that unplanned results of “policy diffractions” are an attempt from education policy makers to obtain “quick wins”. He states that teachers have been applying the ‘letter’ of formative assessment and have lost the essence of it and that formative assessment has been abused for the purpose of sustaining power over assessment though he acknowledges that it is all with good intention from the the school leaders’ part in trying their best in a culture of accountability. Gipps (1999), nonetheless, illustrates the clear and inevitable relation between the formative and summative assessment arguing that assessment has been used to control and regulate the curriculum at the hand of recent globalisation trends of curriculum reforms and standardised tests

all over the world. She further argues that classroom assessment can also be used to sustain power over classroom management (Gipps, 1999). Perrenoud (1998) challenges this socio-cultural view of collective development by extricating two discrete processes. He points out that there is a process of regulating activities which aim to promote productive learning distinct from the process of regulating learning itself, in which teachers develop an understanding of the learners' cognitive and learning processes and the role of feedback in supporting learners to become self-regulating (*ibid.*). From this point of view, formative assessment is also argued to demonstrate a shift power and control from a tradition whereby power is exclusively held by the teacher to a situation whereby power and responsibility over the learning process are shared between the teacher and the learner (Willis, 2007). This notion can be either accepted and adopted by some teachers or placing a sense of threat to others (Black and Wiliam, 2006). This is typical for the case of teachers who struggle to find the perfect balance between accountability requirements on the one hand and the attempt for improvement on the other (Brown, 2004).

Crossouard (2012) further challenges learners' self-regulation by situating the misconception of linking emancipation in association with autonomy and creativity of thought and education, which consequently may have led to mass schooling, indoctrinated education and the emergence of what Foucault (1977) refers to as the 'nation-state'. From this perspective, she argues that indoctrinated institutions produce disciplined and docile subjects instead of creative and independent thinkers who are able to reason and construct knowledge within and beyond the walls of such indoctrinated educational institutions. Foucault's analysis with regards to disciplinary institutions is that they consider pupils/students as a machine: its disciplining, the optimization of its capabilities, the extortion of its forces, the parallel increase of its usefulness and its docility, its integration into systems of efficient and economic controls, and that they are based on hierarchical observation, surveillance, and

normalising judgement ([ibid.](#)), which do not take into account individual differences in preparedness to learn as Crossouard ([2012](#)) observes.

Crossouard ([ibid.](#)) further argues that AfL does not seem to take into account the potential undesirability of learning or recognise the power dynamics that are inherently found in formative assessment. The general consensus among Libyan EFL students about the undesirability to learn English is becoming a recurring theme as Omar ([2013](#), p. 27) reports. Omar ([ibid.](#)) states that Libyan students reiterate that, “learning English is not easy at all”. The power dynamics shown in peer and group assessment in Crossouard’s ([2012](#), p. 194) findings pinpoint two distinctive aspects. The first aspect is a pattern of peer and group disparagement, where she describes, “assessment hierarchies left lower-attaining pupils vulnerable to the criticisms of higher-attaining pupils and where learners had concerns about critique from their peers”. A similar pattern of peer and group disparagement during communicative skills practice was demonstrated in Libyan EFL language classrooms (Aloreibi and Carey, [2017](#); Omar, [2014](#)), albeit for different reasons. It is rather the result of the socio-historical perception of foreign languages in the Libyan context. Aloreibi and Carey ([2017](#), pp. 98–9) add that when students speak English inside the EFL classroom, “their peers do not take them seriously. It is most often perceived as showing off, so it is therefore socially taboo to use English in public”. This arguably stems from a history of colonisation (Youssef, [2012](#)) and an impact of the former regime’s ideologies against the West in the form of political discourse, a power structure recognised in Foucault’s ([1970](#)) analysis of power. The second is that power hierarchies are also discernible when teachers appoint a group leader, who can become dismissive of ideas from other group members (Crossouard, [2012](#)). In addition in peer discourse, Gee ([2004](#), p. 55), notes that learners,

[A]re less likely to simply defer to the authority of the other’s viewpoint, more likely to seek some rational way to deal with differing viewpoints and perspectives, and more likely to actually change their own viewpoint for reasons they understand.

Whilst observations by Crossouard (2012) and Gee (2004) concern children, similar social-power dynamics involved in peer-assessment can be observed in higher education. A fear of over- or under-penalising in peer-assessment as a result of personal relationships has also been reported (Topping, 2009). In addition, peer assessment was also perceived as impeding relationships among peers and criticised for lacking objectivity (Lindblom-ylänne, Pihlajamäki, and Kotkas, 2006; Hanrahan and Isaacs, 2001) as well as the students' inability to defend their work in front of the assessor. Moreover, students have expressed anxiety, stress and discomfort knowing that their work is being assessed by others (Lladó et al., 2014).

Black and Wiliam (1998) report on the positive effects from project implementations of the Formative Assessment Research Group that was applied by teachers of mathematics, science and English in both Oxfordshire and Medway (Black, Harrison, and Lee, 2003) and considerable attainment in test results within the classes involved in the study (Wiliam, Lee, et al., 2004). This raises the notion of how attainment is measured and whether it is measured in a way that reflects true learning. One of the factors that play a role in such results can arguably be the facet of sharing success criteria with the learner. Nonetheless, the question that arises is what educational success is and how it is measured. Biesta (2009, p. 35) challenges such practice and educational discourse based on statistics that do not 'measure what we value' but instead 'value what we (can) measure'. In a culture that values scores, success is contingent on how students perform in tests and how they compare to other national or potentially international institutions rather than true, reflective, and democratic learning. In Libya, EFL learners do not seem to struggle with end of local schools' test scores. Not only are Libyan students' incapable of communicating in English successfully in real-life situations, their performance on English language international tests are reportedly low (Abuklaish, 2014; Omar, 2014). Policy decision makers and teachers focus on form because it can easily be measured compared to oral

communication (Madsen, 1983).

Biesta (2009, p. 38) further expresses concerns over the rise in discourse about learning. His arguments are that learning is individualistic compared to education that involves a relationship. Learning he argues is a process that is devoid of content or direction. He argues that the problem with learning theories is that they prioritise the learner over other factors and this consequently shifts the responsibility from teacher to learner and shifts education from a right to a duty.

As a result, it seems that AfL's approach to learning prioritises the individual's responsibility as well as his/her success above other external factors. The theory does not account for other factors beyond the individual, such as social, cultural, or generally environmental influences on the learning process. It seems to be lacking an element that,

...conceives of learning not as something that happens in the heads, minds or brains of the students, but sees it as something that happens in and 'through' social practices (Hodkinson, Biesta, and James, 2007, p. 22).

A theory that accounts for a socially-constructed learning accounts for such shortcomings. The next section explores the role of the bidirectional relation between the individual, the environment and the individual's behaviour.

3.5.2 Bandura's Social Cognitive/Learning Theory

Social Learning Theory revolves around the concept that through actions, humans 'produce the environmental conditions that affect their behaviour in a reciprocal fashion' (Bandura 2006; 1977). Bandura's theory can be applied to pedagogical practices as it relates to both the learner and the teacher. The theory in its relation to education focusses on the idea that cognitive processes that take place during social activities in the classroom affect learners' and teacher's behaviour and development (Bandura, 1986). Relevant aspects in this

context include observational learning, reciprocal determinism, self-efficacy and self-regulation.

3.5.2.1 Observational learning

Humans learn by observing models/modelled activities (Bandura, 1977). Models in the EFL classroom may include the teacher and/or peers who enact language behaviours and activities that demonstrate superb oral practice. Oral activities include listening to/speaking the language, and/or dialogues, recordings, and/or videos, from native speakers, illustrating a language behaviour/element, for example learners taking roles in pair work activities to ask for directions or check in at the airport. In Libyan schools, EFL teachers tend to ignore listening and speaking practice Orafi and Borg, 2009; Shihiba, 2011. This has been attributed to several reasons. One reason is the misalignment between curriculum goals and assessment, evident in teachers' perception that practising oral skills is a waste of time since exams do not test it (Orafi and Borg, 2009, p. 250). Another reason is that teachers lack the proficiency/fluency to speak English and rely on Arabic in their instruction (Omar, 2014; Orafi and Borg, 2009) thus cannot act as models themselves.

Another reason is the lack of teacher training initiatives with the introduction of the communicative curriculum reform (Asker, 2012, p. 17) and especially after English was banned for over a decade (Zainol Abidin, Pour-Mohammadi, and Alzwari, 2012; Aloreibi and Carey, 2017; Bagigni, 2016; Elabbar, 2011; Mohamed, 2014; Mohsen, 2014; Najeeb and ELdokali, 2012; Omar, 2014; Orafi and Borg, 2009; Sawani, 2009; Shihiba, 2011). Orafi and Borg (2009, p. 245) indicate that,

The new English curriculum in Libya can be described as power-coercive; that is, teachers were not involved in the design of the innovation and their role was to implement the decisions about the curriculum made by the educational policy makers.

Additionally, it has been argued that English course books in Libyan schools are provided in incomplete packages. They lack listening materials such as CDs

(Omar, 2014, p. 124). In a study of English practice in Libyan universities, listening was only practised by listening to the teacher reading aloud short texts and dialogues slowly and clearly and speaking practice was restricted to students reading ‘scattered’ dialogues and texts (Bagigni, 2016, pp. 185–6). Such practice does not reflect authentic language use (Ur, 1999). Lack of appropriate teaching facilities is another issue highlighted by Omar (2014). This includes technology, language labs and visual and audio teaching aids.

3.5.2.2 Reciprocal Determinism

Reciprocal determinism refers to the concept that personal, behavioural and environmental factors are interdependent (Bandura, 1977, pp. 194–5). The relative impact of each factor varies depending on settings and for different behaviours (*ibid.*). How learners/teachers construe the outcomes of their behaviour informs and changes their environment and their personal characteristics, which subsequently changes behaviour (Bandura, 1986). Other schools of thought argue that human beliefs, thoughts and behaviour are shaped by cultural, historical and social environments (Wertsch, Tulviste, and Hagstrom, 1993). Hodkinson, Biesta, and James (2007, p. 22) propose a similar, but more educationally-situated, dynamic to Bandura’s reciprocal determinism proposing a reciprocal relationship between individuals and learning cultures, which “refer to the particular ways in which the interactions between many different factors shape students’ learning opportunities and practices”. Dispositions, actions and individual histories of students are part of the learning culture (*ibid.*, p. 23) which is in line with Bandura’s explanation of how personal characteristics and attitudes contribute to the learning experience.

Libyan students and teachers come with a historical ‘baggage’ of foreign invasion that has had an impact on their attitude towards foreigners and foreign language (Brown, 2000). According to Modiano (2001) EFL learners in culture-specific settings, where cultural inheritance is highly valued, are coerced

to adapt to power-based nation regulations. Moreover, Canagarajah (1999) argues that the English language has been imposed on smaller communities for political and material reasons, and it has been implicated in conflicts for dominance against other languages over the construction of the identity and culture of native people. Motivation to learn English has not only been affected by these events but also by the banning of English during the 1990s. In Libyan schools students for the most part experience difficulties with English (Omar, 2013), whether it is related to the English culture (Ahmed, 2015) learning the language (Najeeb, 2013; Omar, 2013; Youssef, 2012), speaking it (Khalid, 2017; Diaab, 2016) and/or understanding it (Khalid, 2017). Teachers also experience difficulties implementing communicative activities in the EFL classroom (Shihiba, 2011) as part of the communicative curriculum reform. These difficulties result in low self-efficacy (will be discussed next in 3.5.2.3), which discourages them from actively participating in activities that can potentially improve their learning. Teachers' beliefs in the inabilities of students to carry out oral tasks (Orafi and Borg, 2009) deprive students of having the opportunity to learn and improve. Furthermore, learners and teachers' attitudes towards the language and its culture have an impact on their behaviour (Brown, 2000). Similarly, the environment has a negative impact on the student's ability to speak as s/he is surrounded by people who only speak Arabic (Khalid, 2017). Although practising English is limited to the classroom, this opportunity is also hindered by the Libyan learner's characteristics, for example shyness to perform in group discussions or pair work as a result of a cultural tradition "where young people, in general, and students, in particular, are less open to group discussions which are usually the domain of older people" (*ibid.*, p. 56).

3.5.2.3 Self-Efficacy

Perceived self-efficacy from the student and teacher automatically leads to them raising the bar for future goals as well as raising the probability to realise such goals

(Bandura, 1994). Confidence to participate in classroom activities considered as a means to attain pre-determined goals is one form of self-efficacy (Bandura, 1986). This aspect is lacking in Libyan English language classrooms especially in carrying out oral language tasks (Orafi and Borg, 2009, p. 249). The reluctance of student participation in Libyan classrooms can be attributed to lack of speaking proficiency (Diaab, 2016), which may be rooted in pronunciation and comprehension issues (Khalid, 2017) in addition to socio-cultural reasons (Ahmed, 2015). Furthermore, pressure from parents and other individuals from the EFL student's surroundings to study as well as English not being the learners' subject of choice (Zainol Abidin, Pour-Mohammadi, and Alzwari, 2012) can also be a factor influencing students' self-confidence to practice oral skills in EFL classrooms. Findings by Shihiba (2011) show that English is viewed by Libyan students as a subject imposed by the Ministry of Education and that it is a subject they are not interested in learning, but they do so only to pass exams (*ibid.*). Students not practising oral language activities in Libyan EFL classrooms has also been attributed to the teachers' lack of adequate proficiency (Maley and Duff, 1987). Various Libyan researchers (Elabbar, 2011; Omar, 2014) argue that not only are Libyan EFL teachers, in general, not proficient speakers but also lack good English language teaching skills.

3.5.2.4 Self-Regulation

Self-regulation is the process whereby students and/or teachers sets goals and modify their current behaviour, namely strategies, plans, or instruction to realise these goals (Erlach and Russ-Eft, 2011). This can be seen in classroom learning processes such as determining goals and self-monitoring (Caprara et al., 2008), which is also also a central principle in formative assessment. Powers (1991, p. 152) challenges this concept. He argues that,

Purposive behaviour as control behavior entails neither prediction nor an impossible influence of future outcomes on present actions. Instead, it works through ... continually comparing a perceptual version of the current external situation with an inner specification for that perception. Action is driven by the difference, or error.

Learners acquire functions of self-regulation through model observation. Research (Bandura, 1989; Caprara et al., 2008) supports the argument that model observation lends support to incorporating novel techniques in teacher training. In Libyan public schools, classrooms are teacher-centred (Elabbar, 2011; Shihiba, 2011), where learners have a passive role and do not actively engage in oral English language classroom activities, such as listening and speaking practice. Such lack of engagement in classroom oral activities inhibits self-regulated learning. This is because they do not practice activities which are meant to enable them to identify their current language level of oral competence. Identifying their current level of competence is arguably the precursor for setting future goals, which in turn leads learners to reflect and modify their learning strategies to achieve these goals. Findings by Khalid (2017) show that Libyan undergraduate students lack an understanding of their oral English language competence, as well as lack clarity of future educational objectives .

In the light of the ideas discussed above and how power structures come into play, the data were examined on two levels. The first level is an exploration of the role and effectiveness of the practice of oral assessment in developing authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya. This is to examine how and if these practices aligns with AfL principles and Bandura's Social/Cognitive Learning theoretical tenets and how exactly they are perceived by the learners and teachers. The second level is to explore social, power dynamics, discussed above, involved in such practices, and how each perceives them.

It is essential to present the methods that were adopted to achieve this, now that a solid idea about substandard oral English assessment practices in government-sponsored schools and universities in Libya are established, and having showed the motivation behind investigating oral assessment practices in private centres in Libya.

3.6 Methods

This section will explore the methods used in the current study by discussing the questions asked during interviews, giving detailed description of the selected sample, explaining the procedure that was followed for collecting data and presenting the ethical consideration pertaining to this study.

3.6.1 Interviews

The reasons and motives behind conducting semi-structured interviews were extensively discussed in section 3.4. Therefore, it is worth noting that the focus in this subsection is on the nature of interview questions, why they were selected and how they helped in answering the research questions pertinent to this study. Additionally, the reasons why other data collection methods (for example, questionnaires, classroom observations) were declined will be discussed in section 3.6.1.1.

As far as the current study is concerned, 20 semi-structured interviews were conducted; nine with instructors and eleven with students. The main aim of the interviews was to explore the views of the selected English language instructors and students, if any, towards the type of authentic oral practice and assessment used in English language centres in Libya to assess students' oral proficiency in English. Given that the interviews were semi-structured, there were a set of predetermined questions. These questions can be divided into three categories (see Appendix A): the first was an ice-breaker. Specifically, the interviewer asked the participants about their jobs, how long and why they have been learning/teaching English in order to ensure that a rapport was established (Lune and Berg, 2017). Also, participants were asked whether they enjoy learning/teaching English and were prompted to give reasons for their answers.

Assuming that teachers used various forms of assessment as well as oral practices in classrooms, the second category of questions targeted students'

awareness of these concepts. This category included questions about the type of oral skills students and teachers practised in classrooms, what type of oral assessment practice they used/received, how often they practised authentic English, and whether they thought it was important to practise authentic English and assess/be assessed or not. Additionally, they were encouraged to discuss how much they enjoyed doing oral assessment practice. Edwards and Holland (2013) argue that listening intuitively is an essential interviewing skill that is as important as the art of asking questions. Interviewers have to be good listeners in order to control the flow of the conversation and to know what follow-up questions to ask (*ibid.*). Answers to questions within this category confirmed that both the interviewer and the interviewee were in agreement and it was safe to continue with more open-ended key questions unless the respondent seemed to be reticent and reluctant to share their thoughts (Qu and Dumay, 2011). Also, participants' answers to these questions indicated whether they were a helpful source of data as well as gave an initial insight of the participant's attitude towards oral skills practice and assessment.

The third category of questions was the most informative one in terms of participants' viewpoints of oral skills practice and assessments. There were more open-ended questions in this category asking participants about how satisfied they were with the level of oral skills practice and assessment they were giving/receiving. Moreover, participants' thoughts and ideas were sought regarding any desired changes to the current techniques used for oral skills practice and assessment. Bernard (2013) assert that probing is a useful technique to encourage interviewees to keep talking, and they suggest a few ways of probing to use during interviews. These include, but are not limited to, silent probe (i.e. to remain silent and wait for the interviewee to continue), echo probe (i.e. to repeat the last thing the interviewee has said), Uh-Huh probe which is an affirmative utterance that shows you are following with your conversational partner, or the 'tell me more' probe. Other types of questions that lie within this

category were those asking about what oral assessment adds to students' learning experience, if they gave/received any assessment criteria, and whether students were informed about oral assessment beforehand (for example Black, Harrison, Lee, et al., 2004). The participants' answers to such questions helped the researcher construct a full insight of participants' opinions towards oral skills practice and assessment. It was also expected to reveal any power dynamics that might come into play during the process of oral practice.

Furthermore, the interviewer asked extra prompt questions to participants if there was any need to elicit further information from a particular participant in response to a certain question. Rubin and Rubin (2012) suggest that a follow-up question is needed when an interviewee raises an issue that is central to the research and he/she seems willing to talk more about it. For example, when a student participant mentioned that they felt stressed when informed about oral assessment, it was sensible to try to elicit extra information about it by asking further questions. Also, such questions were beneficial when a participant digressed and did not answer a question precisely. In such case, they were redirected back on track by interpreting them nicely, or by asking them another unplanned/paraphrased question (Bernard, 2011) as it was essential to keep the conversation going (Rowley, 2012).

Finally, each interview lasted approximately between 20 and 30 minutes. The intention was to conduct the interviews in L2 English to avoid having issues that are typically associated with translated texts. However, when the participants responded in L1, their responses in Arabic were welcomed. In the latter case, the interview was translated into English where necessary, transcribed and coded. The participants were not pressured to answer in English. The majority chose to respond in Arabic either because it can also be comfortable for them to answer in depth using their native language, one in which they feel more confident and able to express complex issues, or because of the sociolinguistic setting, being in an Arabic-speaking country and having an Arabic interlocutor, that is the

interviewer. Allowing participants to respond in their L1 can have an advantage. According to Mackey and Guss (2005), this can maximise the amount and quality of data the participants produce by eliminating any potential influence from low L2 proficiency. However, this can be considered a potential limitation on the study findings in that data require translation, which can be problematic. Temple and Young (2004) explain that individuals who speak different languages may perceive social life differently. This creates methodological issues. They explain that the relationship between the translator and the language being translated, and languages and researchers, is detrimental for the selection of the most appropriate translation given the vast possibilities of potential ones. According to Simon (1996), the most crucial element in such translations is the preservation of the cultural connotations. She emphasises the importance of the cultural aspects, local realities, literary form, and fluid identities, all of which cannot be found in the descriptive meanings of words. One further element essential to the translation process is highlighted by Liu (2002) is 'psychological equivalence'. The risk lies in possible mismatches between the original text or speech and the translation referents in terms of psychological associations. One solution for such issues put forward by Banville, Desrosiers, and Genet-Volet (2000) to ensure the validity and reliability of translation is including other translators to eliminate subjectivity in translation. The idea is to compare translations by inter-translator reliability and resolving areas of potential disagreement in translation. Based on this, another Libyan-Arabic-English bilingual professional translator scrutinised the translated interviews. Disagreements in translation were discussed with the researcher and resolved. The choice of a Libyan Arabic-English translator was based on the language and culture shared by him, the interviewer, and the participants.

In the subsequent section, I outline other methodologies I could have used, namely questionnaires and classroom observation, considering their strengths and weaknesses, and why I rejected them.

3.6.1.1 Questionnaires and Classroom Observations

Despite the fact that questionnaires are a widely used tool for data collection in social sciences (Bernard, 2018), the researcher has not opted for using this instrument in the current study for a host of reasons. Brown (2001b) defines questionnaires as any written instruments that present a set of questions or statements to a group of participants who are expected to respond either by giving their own answers or selecting from readily available choices. It has been repeatedly noted that questionnaires are more commonly used in quantitative approaches to research (Codo, 2008; Walliman, 2017) and are mainly concerned with numerical analysis (Dörnyei and Taguchi, 2009). However, the current study employs a qualitative approach that is centred on investigating the participants' opinions, thoughts and attitudes towards the practice and assessment of authentic spoken English in classrooms. These target conceptual terms are difficult to transform into numbers, thus the option of using questionnaires to collect data in this research was eliminated. Although, questionnaires can be used to find out about people's attitudes (thoughts, opinions or beliefs) towards a certain phenomenon (*ibid.*), this data collection method is likely to yield unreliable results due to several shortcomings (Bernard, 2013).

One drawback of questionnaires is that questions and choices need to be as simple and direct as possible in order to be easily comprehensible for respondents, particularly when they respond to self-completed questionnaires (Dörnyei and Taguchi, 2009). This may yield superficial data making questionnaires unfit for probing deeper into the complex issues of the investigation. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) state that questionnaires can be completed either in the presence or the absence of the researcher. When the researcher is absent, questionnaires are self-completed by participants which paves the way for unreliable and unmotivated participants to leave out some questions unanswered, or give random answers because they do not fully understand the question, or simply do not like it (Dörnyei and Taguchi, 2009).

Ideally, collecting a full set of data in which participants respond to all questions has been a keystone in the current research, and the researcher could not tolerate to jeopardise the mainstay of this study. Additionally, this research attempts to gather data pertinent to participants' views, thoughts, beliefs and suggestions which require more than few words to express completely. Therefore, the researcher has opted for conducting interviews personally in order to ensure maximum response rate and genuine responses that are neither simple nor superficial.

Furthermore, the researcher cannot have control over how respondents interpret questions or statements in questionnaires (Bernard, 2013), or if their second language proficiency hinders their understanding of questionnaires' items (Dörnyei and Taguchi, 2009). There is little or no opportunity of correcting participants' mistakes when the researcher is not present at the time of data collection. In fact, this is a fundamental point to support the choice of the declining use of questionnaires and conducting interviews as a tool to collect data for current study whose cohort is non-native English speakers. Further evidence comes from Bernard (2006) who argues that the researcher, in face to face interviews, has the option to interfere by probing, paraphrasing or guiding if the interviewee shows that he/she does not understand the question, or provides insufficient answers.

Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018, pp. 474–5) assert that questionnaires fall into three categories: structured, semi-structured and unstructured, depending on the degree of freedom the participants are given to answer. In structured questionnaires, respondents only select one, or more in some cases, of the choices given after each question/statement. In semi-structured questionnaires, respondents enjoy the option of adding a comment after selecting one of the choices in response to the question/statement. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (*ibid.*) add that it can be misleading to describe a questionnaire as being 'unstructured' since the main purpose of questionnaires is to constrain

participants to a handful of responses, yet some researchers tend to include open questions in their questionnaires. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison's viewpoint about unstructured questionnaires indicates that questionnaires might not be the best choice if you tend to ask open questions to your respondents, or if you do not intend to restrict them with answers. Moreover, Dörnyei and Taguchi (2009) point out that cost-effectiveness and time/effort saving are the main advantages of questionnaires. For the purpose of this study, the researcher is willing to spend more time and pay more effort for the sake of accuracy, depth and validity of this study's results.

Observations, on the other hand, were also not considered as an appropriate tool for data gathering in the present study. Observation is defined as the process of looking at and noting humans, events, behaviours, routines, to name but a few (Marshall and Rossman, 2016). The main strength of participant observation – and unique to it (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018) – as a data collection tool is that it can provide more authentic and more valid data compared to other inferential data collection techniques (*ibid.*), such as reported data (Wellington, 2015). There are two types of observational research in social sciences: systematic observation, which is also called structured observation, and participant observation (Denscombe, 2014). Systematic observation is typically associated with social psychology to study for example the social interactions in a school classroom (*ibid.*). This type is typically quantitative in nature (*ibid.*). Participant observation, on the other hand, is typically associated with sociology and anthropology to study for example behaviours, cultures and the beliefs of a particular social community (*ibid.*). This type is mainly qualitative.

Systematic observation has its strengths and weaknesses. Amongst its strengths is that a) it allows for direct recording of data, that is what people actually do rather than what they say they do, b) it can yield large amounts of data in a relatively short time, c) it allows the researcher to achieve a high levels of reliability if established accurately, since observers working on the same

schedule should eventually produce similar data, and d) the quantitative data provided are pre-coded and analysis ready (Denscombe, 2014). However, in the current study, the aim is to investigate what the teachers and learners say and not what they actually do. It is their beliefs, thoughts and attitudes that we are interested in. According to Denscombe (*ibid.*), one of the major drawbacks of systematic observation is that it captures the behaviours not the intentions of the individuals under observation. It does not provide an understanding of why a behaviour happens or the reasons that motivated it (*ibid.*). Additionally, although inter-observer reliability is warranted in systematic observation, the numerical data does not provide the depth or richness required to answer the research questions, of the present study, effectively and appropriately.

Participant observation, on the other hand, has its own strengths and weaknesses. It focuses on covert intentions and motivations (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). In participant observation, the observer–researcher inherently takes the role of a participant within the context of observation, immersing him/herself in the lives of the observed-participants either overtly as a researcher or covertly using some disguise (Becker and Geer, 1957; Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018; Denscombe, 2014). A number of its strengths are that it gives the researcher the insider perspective, which consequently allows the researcher to obtain a good level of depth and detail (Denscombe, 2014) that systematic observation does not. It can yield rich, contextual, first hand information, which has the potential to uncover routines and the potential for documentation (Clark et al., 2009). Some participants prefer it to the time-consuming interview (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018) and it proves itself adequate especially in revealing behaviours that are otherwise deemed too sensitive to be talked about in interviews (Kawulich, 2005). Another important strength is that it preserves the naturalness of the settings (Denscombe, 2014). It can be highly non-intrusive (Simpson and Tuson, 2003), immersing the researcher in the group long enough to be unnoticed (Watts, 2011). However, depending on the type of participation,

this data collection tool has been criticised for violating the code of ethics, that is informed consent (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018; Marshall and Rossman, 2016), which is considered its greatest drawback. Gaining informed consent on the other hand, may potentially influence the naturalness of the settings.

3.6.2 Sample

Given that the current study focuses on private language teaching centres, 5 out of 25 private language teaching centres in the third biggest Libyan city, Misrata were selected. The selection of these 5 centres was based on the number of students attending English language classes; the 5 centres with most registered students were chosen. Arguably, the centres with the most enrolled students are more likely to be offering better teaching environment, using up to standard teaching techniques, and hiring proficient teachers. Such that they are popular among students who are willing to learn English in the city. Accordingly, the recruited sample for the current research represents 16% of the whole community. As for the number of participants, two students and two lecturers from each one of the 5 centres were selected arbitrarily. Participants are a mixture of male and female adults. The teachers were aged between 24 and 45 and the students were aged between 19 and 27. They are native speakers of Libyan Arabic and were born and raised in Libya. English is their second language, so the selected students and teachers are expected to be informative and provide the researcher with the required data needed to address the topic in question.

As such, 20 interviews are conducted; eleven with students and nine with lecturers. It should be made clear that all interviews were conducted with permission of each language centre's gatekeeper, lecturers, and students. In addition, participants were individually interviewed while interviews being recorded. Table E.1 in Appendix E summarises teacher demographics including years of experience teaching English and their motivation(s) for teaching it. Their teaching experience ranges between 24 years and 18 months. Their

motivation for teaching it varied albeit some reasons were expressed more frequently than others. The most common motivation for teaching English is because it is an international language and learning it allows them to connect with the rest of the world. Another recurrent motivation expressed during the interview is that they teach it for financial reasons. Others said they do it to gain experience and for career advancement. Some expressed that teaching English gives them a self of fulfilment and that it is fun to teach. Interestingly, many teachers stated that teaching English allows them to maintain their own L2 and protect it from language attrition. One teacher participant, Adam who has been teaching English since 1992, said that he feels happy teaching English because it is an international language which allows him to communicate with the ‘outside’ world as he refers to it. He added that because very few people in Libya spoke English back then, it made him feel special when teaching it, especially that as he became more proficient, he explains that it has had a financial upside to it. He also indicates that he particularly enjoys teaching English when he reaps the benefit of seeing his students as successful individuals beyond the classroom.

Table E.2 in Appendix E summarises student demographics, that is age, gender, number of years learning English, and motivation for learning it. Their learning period varied between as short as less than a year to as long as eight years. It is very likely for those indicating they have been learning for a relatively extended period that their experience includes school and university. Students echoed their teachers’ motivations: they recognised the importance of English as a global language and as a means to communicate with the outside world. They further indicate its ubiquity. Samah argues, “it’s the number one language in the world”, whilst Sammy indicates that, “it’s useful for reading labels/instruction manuals on products ... the Internet is mainly English; most of the web information is in English”. Inaas emphasises Sammy’s reasons arguing that, “everything is in English nowadays”. Reda, on the other hand, indicates that, “there has been an increase in English-speaking TV channels” and that without

subtitles or a good level of proficiency, it is hard to enjoy such movies. Another group of student participants – Abdallah, an engineer, Haifa, a dentistry major, Samah, and Inaas – revealed that they want to learn English for academic reasons and/or to be able to pursue higher studies. Career advancement was also one of the motivations expressed during the interviews. Reasons explained ranged from having better career possibilities to the competitiveness of the job market. One student, Ibrahim, indicated that he once learned English as a child who had resided in the UK with his family. Having experienced language attrition in English motivated him to re-embark on the language learning journey. Another student participant, Fady, indicates that he seized the opportunity offered by his father to enrol in language courses. Finally, Abdallah, indicated that he travels frequently and for this reason learning English is a must.

3.6.3 Procedure

It is worth mentioning that the participants were given brief information about the study in order to inform them about the aims of the current work and to familiarise them with the topic they are going to talk about. This process of introduction was repeated with every one of my participants who was interviewed individually. Such a process is vital as the participants need to understand the main objective of the interviews before they provide any information about their experiences to the researcher. Also, it gives the participants the opportunity to rapidly think about the information they are willing to share with the interviewer. Interviews took place in one of the classrooms in the language centre where the participant is either a student or a teacher. Additionally, in order to be approachable to the interviewees, every effort to establish a good rapport with them was exerted, specifically at the beginning of the interview (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006).

Probes were used to direct or explain the participants' responses, which are

expected to include many gestures, specifically students' responses when they try to express their views in English. Given the fact that English is the students' second language at which they have not reached high proficiency yet, they are likely to require some support to help them fully understand the questions. Moreover, a prompt was also used to remind the participants of essential issues they had not talked about (Gillham, 2000). For instance, if a student is asked about what oral assessment adds to his/her learning and he/she answers, say, about the importance of assessment in general, the student were prompted to talk about how oral assessment has positively influenced his/her learning.

Further to establishing a good relationship between the participants and myself, I used a series of questions that progressed from general to specific. For example, after greeting the interviewee, I started by asking about his/her job, work experience, and how long they have been studying/teaching English, then moved to the specific questions pertinent to the current study. The reason for using such a technique is to break the ice between us as well as motivate the participants to be more outspoken (Marshall and Rossman, 2016). The interviewer will always speak and ask using English, whereas participants will have the choice to respond in English, Arabic or even code switch, i.e. shift between both languages in response to any question. Hence, all interviews were recorded, translated – where necessary - and transcribed. The interviewer will take notes during the interviews as well as do a post interview check in order to ensure that the taken notes match the recording (Patton, 2015). Participants were informed that they have the choice to stop the interview at any time if they feel they need a break. This reduced the pressure on them and prevented them from feeling that they were confined for nearly 15 minutes, which was the approximate time of each interview.

Before the end of each interview, I asked the interviewees if they had any further questions, or if they would like to add any comments or statements that they thought should be relevant to the study. Also, they were requested to raise

any point they thought was related to the current study that may not have been mentioned during the interview. Finally, at the end of each interview, I expressed my great appreciation for their cooperation and agreeing to participate in my study and showed how thankful I was to their time and efforts (Lune and Berg, 2017).

3.6.4 Ethical Consideration

According to Lindorff (2010), researchers undertaking enquiries in any research discipline and working within any paradigm should consider participants' safety and ensure that they are treated with respect. This is true for all lecturers and students taking part as respondents in the current study. All students and staff who participated in this study were volunteers whose time and effort were highly appreciated. Also, the participants' permission to audio record the interviews was requested (Opie, 2004). They were supplied with a participant information sheet, which included full details about the research project (see Appendix B). They were also asked to sign a consent form before their participation (see Appendix C). Moreover, they were told that they can withdraw from the interview at any point without giving a reason or without fearing the consequences of this.

Furthermore, the anonymity and confidentiality of all lecturers and students was always protected. When their data were coded and analysed, participants' one-to-one interviews were labelled using pseudonyms, for lecturers and students, in order to protect their identity. I made use of pseudonyms instead of numbers. The rationale behind this was that a name humanises the statements and facilitates the reader in following the threads of the stories from the participants. Anonymity was not to be compromised as I made sure I chose a name that did not match the participant's real name (Lune and Berg, 2017).

Full ethical approval was obtained from The University of West of Scotland. The university policy on ethics were strictly followed. Hence, all aspects of data gathering were subject to respondents' permission and it was made clear from the outset that all respondents were anonymised. In addition, a commitment was

made that all data were securely kept and only be used for the purposes of the current study. Also, the interview recorder was kept in a locked place.

3.7 Data Coding

Saldaña (2013) defines a code in the qualitative paradigm as a word or a group of words that encapsulates the salient, core, comprehensive and distinctive qualities for a piece of data. There is a variety of data types including interviews, photographs and documents and data portions in each type vary in magnitude (*ibid.*). It was believed that the main aim of data coding, particularly interview transcripts, was capturing the essence of what had been said. This entails not only analysing these relatively substantial portions of data, but also reducing them into smaller chunks (Griffie, 2005). In the current study, the transcribed semi-structured interviews were coded and consequently reduced in an essence-capturing process.

Alhojailan (2012) argues that due to gathering huge amounts of evidence in the qualitative paradigm, data analysis usually relies on interpreting these data which indicates that data may require or yield several explanations. This idea is relatively echoed in Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault (2015) who think of coding scheme as a personal filing system in which data are stored in different categories based on conceptual similarities. The possibility of having different interpretations of any portion of data has led some researchers to suggest using more than one coder in order to ensure reliable categorisation of data and eliminate the intervention of coders' hopes and preferences (for example Lune and Berg, 2017). Nevertheless, in the current study coding was scrupulously undertaken by the researcher himself, and this process happened through few stages. In this regard, Saldaña (2013) asserts that it is seldom that a researcher can get coding right at the first attempt, thus meticulous attention is required for qualitative data which can be obtained by recoding and recoding again.

Patton (2015) argues that in the qualitative paradigm researchers have used

different terminology to refer to certain processes in data analysis. For example, Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas (2013) note that there is confusion regarding the term thematic analysis and how it is different from content analysis. However, Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) clearly state that content analysis involves coding, categorising and comparing. Similarly, Maguire and Delahunt (2017) indicate that the key objective of thematic analysis is to extract themes which are the significant and interesting patterns in the data set. Moreover, Saldaña (2013) highlights that it is of paramount importance not to initially code for themes, and he explains that themes cannot be coded, but they are the outcome of coding and categorising.

Contrary to this, it seems that there is a consensus among qualitative researchers on the importance of reviewing the data repeatedly before the actual process of coding begins in order to familiarise yourself very well with them (Bernard, 2011; Braun and Clarke, 2006; Charmaz, 2014; Patton, 2015; Saldaña, 2013, amongst others). More to the point, Lune and Berg (2017) suggest that a qualitative inquirer needs to search for similarities and dissimilarities (i.e. patterns) in the available data. This process helps in creating topics that can be indexed in the coding system. In addition, coding helps the researcher to develop insightful understanding of the data, not only to count the frequencies of particular words or phrases (Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault, 2015). Bernard (2011) goes further and proposes that coding and analysis are two interrelated processes. That is the researcher keeps discovering interesting remarks that may eventually develop into themes as he/she goes along the data. Likewise, Richards (2013) contend that coding is more than assigning labels to data portions; in fact, it is linking between data and ideas.

Content analysis or thematic analysis can be conducted in two distinct approaches: bottom-up and top-down (for example Braun and Clarke, 2006; Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018), or inductive and deductive (for example Bernard, 2011; Patton, 2015). Top-down or deductive analysis/coding of the

data is dependent on the study's research questions, or the researcher's focus and tendencies. This means that the analyst starts with a hypothesis prior to the actual coding where he/she tries to test whether the formulated hypothesis is correct (Bernard, 2011). However, 'bottom-up' or inductive coding is driven by the available qualitative data. The researcher's task when coding inductively is to find meanings that are either present in the text or supported by it (Lune and Berg, 2017). This being said, the analyst's key role is to find patterns, topics or categories in the data. According to Patton (2015), inductive analysis is typically conducted at the initial stages of processing qualitative data, particularly when the researcher tries to establish codes to analyse the data content or look for possible categories, patterns, and themes. This is normally referred to as open coding (Corbin and Strauss, 2015), which indicates being open to data (Patton, 2015) to find issues, topics and themes in a systematic manner (Lune and Berg, 2017). Additionally, open coding has been linked to Grounded Theory (Glaser and Strauss, 1967) which postulates being entirely indulged - grounded in - in analysing the data to develop comprehensive understanding of the target text (Bernard, 2011) and try to extract implied relationships and meanings (Patton, 2015).

In a similar vein, Saldaña (2013) refers to open coding as Initial Coding which entails breaking down qualitative data into smaller parts, meticulously examining them as well as finding similarities and differences between them (Corbin and Strauss, 2015). Maguire and Delahunt (2017) emphasise the same point by noting that using open coding means that researchers do not have previously created codes, rather codes are developed and modified as the coding process continues. Moreover, Saldaña (2013) proposes several methods for qualitative data coding, but it is beyond the scope of this study to go over them all. However, for data processing purposes in the current study, the researcher will employ open coding/or initial coding which, according to Saldaña (*ibid.*), can include other coding methods such as In Vivo Coding or Process Coding. In

Figure 3.2: Initial coding process based on Saldaña (2013)

Vivo coding (literal coding) is a process in which the researcher uses some exact words or phrases from the actual data portions. Process coding (action coding) refers to using the gerund form (verb-ing) to extract actions, particularly conceptual, from the data set.

Saldaña (*ibid.*) asserts that the coding process moves from particular to general or from real to abstract. Put differently, the researcher’s challenge is to try to reach to a theory from the data he/she has gathered which entails trying to put the initial codes they have created into categories or subcategories. Next, the categories are compared to find similarities and dissimilarities in order to form concepts or themes. These concepts and themes are eventually used to formulate assertions or develop into theories about whole set of data. This process, illustrated in figure 3.2 (*ibid.*), was employed in this study. Furthermore, Neuman (2011) recommends that some points need to be taken into consideration while coding which include frequency, direction, intensity and space. In regard of interviews, frequency refers to how often a statement (or message) is repeated and its directions shows whether the speaker is in support of or against it. Intensity is how powerful the speaker’s words are (i.e. the way it was expressed) and how long it was given from the speaker’s time is how much space it was given.

Some qualitative researchers suggest using software programmes to help in coding or analysing qualitative data. For example, computer-assisted, or aided, qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS) (Silverman, 2013) is one of the

commonly used software programmes and there is also NVivo and ATLAS.ti. However, using such software programmes has been criticised and claimed to have some shortcomings. Specifically, Taylor, Bogdan, and DeVault (2015) argue that it can be time consuming to train yourself to use these programmes, to enter your data in them, or even to programme them to categorise your data the way one prefers. Also, Saldaña (2013) doubts the accuracy of these software programmes in categorising data. Similarly, Patton (2015) finds hand coding more productive and smoother than relying on computer programmes. He adds that it makes a difference to actually see the data in their original form and it is essential in identifying patterns and themes. Therefore, for coding purposes in this study, the researcher used manual coding and did not rely on software programmes. However, computers were used to work on, store and manage the coding process.

Interviews were translated where needed and transcribed. The transcriptions were divided into two pools (i.e. lecturers and students). Then each group was coded/analysed holistically rather than individually. Next, data in the pool of each group was coded based on principles relating to AfL Assessment for Learning Theory (such as summative vs. formative assessment, anxiety, feedback, etc.) as well as Bandura's Social Learning (cognitive) Theory (such as self-regulation, self-efficacy, confidence, etc.) from a power-related perspective. The latter includes notions of power dynamics in pair work activities, imposition of course materials, learner autonomy, punishment and reward to name but a few. Each theory-related topic, say anxiety from fear of peer judgement, was searched across each pool of data. For comparison purposes, contexts in which topics are repeatedly experienced were noted. These contexts were examined to identify different ways a topic was experienced within the same pool. For instance, the number of participants who showed anxiety were counted and categorised where possible (i.e. low, mild, or high). Also, similarities and differences in experiences were compared across pools where comparisons are

valid in order to create categories and eventually make general assertion about the data.

3.8 Validity, Reliability, Bias and Limitations

Reliability and validity are two major aspects of scientific research. Reliability is referred to as the extent to which findings of a particular piece of research can be found again when the inquiry is replicated in the same settings by another researcher (Merriam, 1995). According to Drost (2011), validity is concerned with how meaningful the research components are. That is, the researchers are urged to assure that they are measuring the variable they intended to measure, and that they are using the proper instrument which is supposed to do so accurately. According to Oppenheim (1992), validity in interviews is contingent upon honesty, depth and richness of the responses as well as commitment from the interviewee's end. Several researchers have claimed that reliability and validity are pertinent to quantitative research as being closely linked to the positivist view, thus they are unrelated to qualitative research (Rolfe, 2006). However, as far as qualitative research is concerned, many researchers assert that rigour encompasses the aspects of reliability and validity and the three concepts are essential to ensure the quality of any research (Cypress, 2017). Cypress (*ibid.*) further defines rigour as the state of being meticulous, highly precise, and careful or the quality of showing a great deal of accuracy and thoroughness.

Lincoln and Guba (1985), who were the pioneers to address the importance of rigour in qualitative research, used the concept "trustworthiness" instead of reliability and validity. They further add that in order for researchers to attain trustworthiness in any naturalistic paradigm, inquirers need to meet the requirements of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability in each stage of their research. However, Morse (2016) suggests that it is a burden on researchers to be obliged to follow checklists to ensure these criteria are met. Moreover, Morse (2015) proposes to return to use the traditional term 'rigour'

whose main criteria are validity, reliability and generalisability.

Similarly, Golafshani (2003) argues that,

If the issues of reliability, validity, trustworthiness, quality and rigor are meant differentiating ‘good’ from ‘bad’ research then testing and increasing the reliability, validity, trustworthiness, quality and rigor will be important to the research in any paradigm (p. 602).

Norris (1997) states that a practical way to measure the validity of a study is to consider error and bias. He also adds that being a human activity, research is unlikely to be immune of any source of errors or bias. In the current study, the researcher has constantly endeavoured to eliminate any act of bias, specifically as far as sample selection is concerned. Such that, the 20 participants who took part in the current study were arbitrarily selected. Additionally, the researcher has ceaselessly striven to avoid any errors from the outset, particularly pertaining data coding and analysis. Yet, the current study is no exception of any form of research and it has its own limitations.

An additional aspect worth mentioning is that of *positionality* of the researcher and how this may affect their bias towards the study results and data collection and/or analysis. According to Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018), positionality is an ethical issue. It is about relationships between the researcher and the participants. Parties in this relationship hold different levels of power, where the researcher usually has more power over the researched (Hammersley and Traianou, 2012). How a researcher views him/herself and others as a result of one’s beliefs, cultural values, social, status, gender, race, religion and insider and outsider status can affect research knowledge and how it is carried out, evaluated and utilised (Bettez, 2015). According to Kanuha (2000, p. 439) “insider research” refers to when a scholar “conducts studies with populations, communities, and identity groups of which they are also members”, usually sharing identity, language, or the professional experience. Rose (1985, p. 77) posits that, “there is no neutrality. There is only greater or less awareness of one’s biases. And if you do not appreciate the force of what you’re leaving out,

you are not fully in command of what you're doing". Moreover, Chavez (2008, p. 475) echoes Rose's position stating that, "qualitative researchers, outsiders or insiders, cannot be assured that their observations, interpretations, and representations are not affected by their various identities or positionalities". As an insider to the study population, sharing a Libyan, Arabic identity, first language, and professional experience of teaching English as a foreign language in Libya, being aware of my position, although bias is inevitable as Rose and Chavez suggest, it can be kept to a minimum. Asselin (2003) recommends that for the insider researcher, it is best to collect data with open eyes whilst at the same time assuming minimum knowledge of the phenomenon under investigation. Being aware of the cultural context under investigation does not entail awareness of the subculture involved, she adds. In addition, Tilley, Chambers, and Mackenzie (1996) recommend carrying out self-reflection continuously and reliability checks carried out by another researcher to review data and conclusions. The latter recommendation helps in keeping the analysis and interpretation of data less biased and helps in establishing integrity.

The scope of the study covers only private language teaching centres and its results cannot be extended to any other institutions where English language is taught such as schools or universities. The study was conducted in the city of Misrata, thus results cannot be generalised to include private language teaching centres in other Libyan cities. Nonetheless, (Gaskell, 2000) argues that provided that all things being equal in a study, conducting more interviews does not really indicate that a better and detailed understanding of the situation will be provided. Thus, the researcher believes that the sample tested for the purpose of this study, which forms 16% of the targeted population in Misrata, could potentially represent most private language teaching centres in Libya. This is because private language teaching centres in Libya in general tend to provide high quality teaching-learning environment – compared with government-led institutions - in order to attract students to enrol and consequently make the

business prosper. High quality teaching-learning environment entails the existence of fully equipped classrooms, proficient teachers and a pedagogically sound curriculum among other things. Many of such characteristics of reliable teaching environment were witnessed in the language teaching centres that were visited but not selected for this study. Therefore, the cohort recruited from the centres with the most registered students in Misrata is believed to be representative of all language centres in Libya.

Another limitation of this study, as its title indicates, is that it encompasses oral practice and assessment in the targeted population. This means that the findings which this study will yield are not applicable to any other forms of classroom assessment or practice (i.e. teaching and assessing written tasks such as essay writing or grammar).

3.9 Conclusion

This chapter has detailed the methodology that was adopted in this study and has emphasized the ways in which both methodology and methods were carefully constructed to address the questions of the study. It introduced, first, research design and methodology and compared approaches to the differing paradigms that can be employed in the Social Sciences, by setting out some significant ideas and notions of research philosophy in general and how data were analysed, most notably in the positivist paradigm vs. the phenomenological paradigm. Furthermore, this chapter discussed the general theory of deductive reasoning and inductive reasoning and its bearing on quantitative research vs. qualitative research. The theoretical background that encompasses the current study was elaborated on; shedding light on the two main theories related to the current study, namely, Assessment for Learning (AfL) and Bandura's Social Cognitive Learning Theory (SCLT). I have also introduced the study's primary questions and detailed on the methods I followed in order to answer them. This included discussing the questions that were asked during the interviews and how

they help in addressing the research questions. Then data coding was presented in broad brushstrokes. Also, the sample was thoroughly described, the procedure of conducting each interview was illustrated and the ethical considerations pertinent to the current study were carefully presented. Finally, the possible limitations of the current study were touched upon.

Chapter 4: Results and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

It is important to reiterate that 20 interviews were translated where appropriate and transcribed. Although the interviewer used English, participants were not pressured to respond in English. They were allowed to respond in either English, Arabic or code switch between both languages in response to any question. According to Richards (2009), the presentation of events or thoughts may vary considerably depending on the language used. To solve this issue, Mackey and Guss (2005, p. 174) suggest that,

...depending on the research question and resources available, interviews can be conducted in the [interviewee]'s L1, thus removing concerns about the proficiency of the [interviewee] impacting quality and quantity of the data provided.

The interviewees were nine teachers and eleven students who were teaching/studying English at private language centres in the city of Misrata, Libya. The participants were individually interviewed and they responded to a list of questions concerning English language oral assessment and practice in the centres where they were teaching/studying³. The list of questions were divided into three main parts; a) Part one: rapport-building questions, b) Part two: 11 main interview questions, and c) Part three: follow up questions. The researcher has thoroughly read and scrutinised the transcripts in order to detect any striking similarities and differences between participants' responses in relation to the literature discussed in Chapter 2. Finding these aspects of disparity and likeness in the interview scripts will help capture the essence of the data in hand (Saldaña, 2013).

Following an exhaustive coding process (see Chapter 3 for details), subthemes (i.e. similar perspectives pertinent to a particular issue (Bernard, 2011)) have been extracted from the interview scripts. These subthemes have been grouped together to form themes (i.e. an overarching topic that is supported by a number

³For a full list of questions, see Appendix A

of subthemes) based on relatedness and directionality (Saldaña, 2013). For subthemes to be assembled together, they need to be related to the same point (for example, anxiety before assessment) and show the same direction of perspective (i.e. either with or against). Eventually, three themes have been generated: *Essential Areas for Development*, *Obstacles to Improvement*, and *Overcoming the Obstacles*.

In response to interview questions, teacher and student participants discussed several areas that they thought were essential for the development of English language oral skills such as practising spoken English regularly in the classroom. Participants elaborated on various elements that they seemingly believed to be necessary for the improvement of listening and speaking skills in English language centres in Libya. Some of these areas were highlighted more frequently than others, but they were all characterised as crucial. Each of these repeatedly mentioned areas has been considered as a subtheme and they have been grouped together as a single theme: *Essential Areas for Development*.

Similarly, both groups of participants addressed a variety of obstacles that hinder the development of the students' English oral skills. Student and teacher participants discussed several sensitive issues that negatively influenced the teaching-learning process of speaking and listening such as large classroom size. Despite the variation in both groups' perspectives regarding these issues and their intensity, the researcher believes that these subthemes underpin a single theme referred to as *Obstacles to Improvement*.

In order to overcome these obstacles that they encounter in teaching/learning English oral skills, teacher and student participants have introduced a variety of techniques that could be adopted. Different methods were suggested by both groups some of which have been regularly implemented, whereas others are rarely practised. This is because these techniques require substantial efforts by the teachers and students to implement them. For instance, practising oral English outside classroom seems to be achievable in theory, yet it is hardly possible to

have a chance to converse with native English speakers in Libya because English is not the native language. This is consistent with the findings of Farooqui (2007) in the Bangladeshi context. Her teacher participants expressed the same concern about students not having the opportunity to speak English outside the classroom given that Bangladesh is a monolingual country. However, such frequently mentioned attempts to improve the outcome of the teaching-learning process from both teacher and student participants were coded into subthemes which gathered to form the theme of *Overcoming the Obstacles*.

Next, the formulated themes, subthemes and quotations from the interviews' scripts will be used to address this study's research questions. This means that teacher and student participants' viewpoints congruent to English oral assessment and practice in private language centres in Libya will be discussed, and any striking similarities and differences between both groups of informants will be highlighted. The discussion will be in line with the theoretical framework of the current study⁴, which relates to Bandura's Social Cognitive Learning Theory (SCLT), Assessment for Learning (AfL) and various perspectives on power relations namely Foucault (1970, et seq.), MacLure (2006), Biesta (2009), and Crossouard (2012)

4.2 Essential Areas for Development

In order to investigate the role and effectiveness of oral practice and assessment on the development of authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya, teacher and student participants were asked about the current practices of oral assessment and practice in target centres. Both groups of participants thoroughly indulged in conversations during the interviews to discuss the issues of oral practice and assessment. Their perspectives and subthemes relevant to the first theme *Essential Areas for Development* will be presented.

⁴As discussed in Chapter 2

4.2.1 Oral Practice

Nine teacher participants emphasised the importance of practising oral skills to enable the development of students' listening and speaking abilities. Teacher participants provided various reasons to support their argument some of which were more frequently mentioned than others. Specifically, the first subtheme, which was outlined by seven teacher participants, of the theme *Essential Areas for Development* was that oral practice promotes students' self-confidence. One teacher participant, Farage, states that,

That is why practising oral skills is important. You teach a student how to deliver public speech and boost their courage even when mistakes are committed, don't worry. It's OK. Try once, twice and again until the learner gets used to it and learns how to speak publicly with self-confidence.

Another teacher participant, Alia, addresses the importance of listening and speaking as the springboard to self-confidence. She states that,

The student must listen first and then practise speaking throughout the course... this is to reduce anxiety in conversations and develop self-confidence.

These perspectives are echoed by students in the same way. Haifa indicates that oral/aural skills are the foundation skills necessary to hold conversations and gain self-confidence in speaking. She states that,

The most important skills in a classroom are speaking and listening. This is to support self-confidence and to eliminate fear and anxiety. Without being able to actively use the language, a student can never acquire self-confidence in holding conversations in that new language.

This is all in line with the assertion made by Bandura (2006) and Bandura (2010) that learners' recognition of their role as an agent in their learning process instigates/boosts their self-confidence, which is a prerequisite for action planning to achieve their learning goals. This self-belief in personal efficacy, as he explains,

is the incentive to act/learn and to persevere in the face of adversary. This is rooted in the belief in the power to effect change using actions.

A second subtheme that arose during the coding process was related to students' motivation. Half of the language educators interviewed argued that oral practice enhances students' motivation. The third repeatedly mentioned subtheme was the importance of oral practice in language learning. Four teacher participants talked about how oral practice contributes to effective language learning. In particular, they said that it develops speaking skills, pronunciation, vocabulary knowledge and eventually leads to successful language learning. There is a long-standing debate on the role of language practice in the ESL/EFL classroom. Ellis (1992; 1993), VanPatten and Cadierno (1993) and VanPatten (1996) hold the view that input(aural) practice is what leads to successful language learning, whereby output(oral) practice solely improves fluency. However, a study by Dekeyser and Sokalski (1996) shows no clear link between input (receptive) and output (productive) skills. Krashen (1982; 1985; 1994) strongly holds the view of the importance of comprehensible input and non-interference position in language acquisition arguing that pressure to perform may have undesirable effects by raising anxiety among the learners. Empirical evidence indicates raising the amount of explicit grammatical information, whilst at the same time introducing them strategically at given points during input processing can increase the likelihood of acquiring generalisable knowledge from the limited input data (Rosa and Leow, 2004). Additionally, the importance of attention and awareness has been asserted to assist the role of aural practice on learning by second language scholars such as Leow (2007) and social learning theorists such as Bandura (1977). Other researchers have argued for the importance of output (oral) practice suggesting that it is a means of creating novel linguistic knowledge (Swain, 1985; Swain, 1995; Swain, 1998; Swain, 2005). Output (oral) practice promotes cognitive processes in second language learning. Of these processes specified by Swain

(1985; 1995; 1998; 2005) are noticing (see also Jacknick and Thornbury, 2013; Leow, 2019), formulating hypotheses and testing them, metalinguistic function and syntactic processing. de Bot (1996) proposes an additional role for oral practice vis-a-vis enhancing fluency (see also Derwing, 2017; Thornbury, 2017). de Bot (1996) argues that it accelerates speed of delivery and allows the utilisation of the learner's attentional resources on a higher level processing. He adds that fluency then transforms knowledge from *declarative* to *procedural*.

In a similar vein, one of the teacher participants, Adam, reported – in answer to the question as to why he believes oral practice is important – that,

Because it builds self-confidence during conversations... also develops the student's vocabulary bank and learns... give them positive feedback... a simple example is when a student speaks in front of a larger audience, s/he is afraid and does not have literary courage... thus language skills develops the student's self-esteem... *it allows the students to speak better without being shy...* therefore, the more the student speaks, the less mistakes s/he makes... that's why oral practice is really important.

Adam's view was echoed by one of his colleagues, Salem, who states that,

...by encouraging the student and adding a novel piece of knowledge to their repertoire .. *oral practice helps the student to use words even outside the classroom...* several spoken classroom vocabulary can be directly transferable outside the classroom unlike the written word, which can be challenging to read.

Moreover, individual teacher participants underlined some supporting points that indicate the positive effects of oral practice has on different aspects of English language learning such as reducing anxiety. Also, it was mentioned that English oral practice helps in communication. Finally, one teacher participant argued that oral practice can benefit both students as well as teachers. Having been raised by individual teachers only, the issues reported in this paragraph were not considered as subthemes. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) assert that all data must fit into such grouping invariably and without negative cases for them to be considered a homogeneous part of it. Different units of analysis, they argue,

have varying reliability issues. To achieve semantic validity, such units must be classifiable within the same subtheme with similar meaning of the text's context (Krippendorp, 2004). They were counted as further supporting evidence of the theme under discussion.

As far as student participants are concerned, a common subtheme highlighted by seven student participants was that oral practice boosts their self-confidence. In addition, half of the student participants indicated that at private language centres they are given more opportunity to practise authentic language oral skills given that more time is allocated by teachers for oral activities. This issue of having the opportunity to practice counts as another subtheme. The third subtheme that emerged in student participants' responses was that private centres offer better teaching methods. Four student participants reported that teachers at private centres follow more effective teaching techniques, which provides better teaching. Specifically, one student participant, Haifa, mentioned that,

It is the first time I feel I am truly learning English ... [in] the private centre, we are taught how to say the words properly... in the private centre, it is the first time I ever hear of phonetics.

Arabic orthography is different from that of the English Language. The feature of symbol-sound correspondence that the phonemic symbols provide for the learners helps raise phonemic awareness and thus facilitate learners' independent learning. Knowing that the Libyan teacher's accent is quite probably foreign-accented, this system also allows access for those learners on how words are pronounced in the English language. Rajab (2013) showed that not only learning the International Phonetic Alphabet improves learners' speaking and writing skills but also, with the help of monolingual dictionaries, develop a sense of autonomy and competence. Further, another learner, Ismail, stated that there is a variety of activities in private language centres and the tasks tend to be more challenging which enhances the learning process. He explains,

First of all, pronunciation... at universities, teachers' pronunciation is different from that of teachers at language schools... this is of course my personal experience... this has had a negative impact especially at the outset of having courses... I find it difficult sometimes to pronounce some words. Also at universities, there were no listening or speaking activities due to the big classroom size, very limited time and potentially other issues that we are not aware of. Of course these issues have affected us students but I speak for myself as it has affected me immensely and that's the reason I have resorted to private language schools... I tell the language school head about these issues so we don't have to deal with what we dealt with in universities here again.

Another student participant, Samah, was pleased with the fact that teachers more often motivate students to work hard. She states, "...if the teacher tells me that I have improved I will be more motivated and I will be more willing to learn." One of the roles of teachers as facilitators in the foreign language classroom is motivating students and one of the channels of socialisation is to provide informational feedback (Dörnyei, 1994). According to Dörnyei, this type of feedback should be the dominant one in a foreign language classroom. The idea rests on assessing competence using praise which makes a connection between success and the learner's effort and ability. This, it is argued, stems from the learner's internal abilities making him/her believe that such success is achievable many times in the future. Bandura (2006) explains that motivation is an intrinsic attribute of agency. Self-regulation and understanding the purpose of a course, leads to goal-setting and activates intrinsic motivation. This supports the proposal of (Dörnyei and Taguchi, 2009), who argue that an ideal L2-self reflects the beliefs of the learner in terms of how s/he view his/her future-self on the basis of aspirations and goals of language learning. For some Libyan EFL students, English is perceived as a means for securing a future career (Asker, 2012). Subsequently motivation leads to better utilisation of cognitive strategies and enhanced learning habits, which essentially lead to improved learning and achievement (Simons, Dewitte, and Lens, 2004).

4.2.2 Oral Assessment

When it comes to oral assessment, the first subtheme was that the aim of assessment is to motivate students to learn. Six teacher participants emphasised that learning is the ultimate goal of assessment, not passing the exams or getting high grades. Thus, assessment should be designed to encourage students to practise oral skills. Likewise, three teacher participants mentioned that assessment motivates students to work hard, so this could be the second subtheme. This supports the proposal by Bandura and Schunk (1981), that exams and tests are strong *proximal* motivators in language learning, because they mark progress, which consequently give learners instant incentive, unprompted motivation, and feedback, which help students invest and maintain an effort in learning. Moreover, half of the teacher participants indicated that formative assessment is more effective than summative assessment. As discussed in Chapter 2, assessment for formative purposes has been frequently described to yield positive results not only on student motivation, involvement, but also self-confidence (Hayward and Spencer, 2010; Black, Harrison, and Lee, 2003). According to Ramaprasad (1983), establishing the student's current level serves as the foundation to goal-setting and negotiating means to reach such goals.

Two of the teacher participants indicated that formative assessment caters for individual differences. Applying formative assessment is the third extracted subtheme from educators' interviews. Teacher participants who preferred applying formative assessment when teaching oral skills also indicated that continuous feedback on students' performance is necessary. In answer to the question whether he thinks oral assessment was necessary and why, a lecturer participant, Ali stated,

Firstly, because [as a teacher] I need to know whether my teaching has an effect or not. It is not merely teaching a lesson. That's part of the job description but I need to assess their performance to correct mistakes and provide feedback.

Another lecturer participant, Farage, answered,

...by listening to an extract and then trying to explain what has been heard and the rest of the students are given the chance to correct mistakes and give feedback in case the speaker made any mistakes.

However, insight as to why feedback is necessary was not supplied by any of the lecturer participants who viewed feedback as such. According to Scrivener (2011), providing instant feedback depends on whether the focus of the activity is accuracy or fluency. If the aim is accuracy, then instant corrective feedback is more appropriate. However, if the focus of the activity is on fluency, instant corrective feedback may not be the most appropriate option as it hinders the main purpose of the activity in question. Additionally, three teacher participants highlighted that oral assessment enhances students' self-regulation. This means that they can assess themselves to see what their weaknesses are and try to improve their performance. A participant lecturer, Salem, explains,

I've noticed that upon graduation, graduates lack fluency... thus oral assessment helps them to develop themselves and also helps them to self-assess themselves outside the classroom and use the language because they know they will be assessed during the course and they develop based on this knowledge throughout the course and acquire courage and self-confidence.

One teacher participant, Omar, mentioned that students should be aware of assessment criteria beforehand so that they expect what they will face during exams. He states,

Student should be made aware especially if you tell them that I will examine you in speaking and I will focus on speaking, pronunciation, vocabulary use and that I will focus on fluency... the student should be made aware of these I provide that knowledge so that the student focuses on these criteria especially in exams.

Another teacher participant, Rania, suggests that it is important to vary the assessment techniques in order to cater for individual difference among learners. She indicates that,

There is assessment throughout the course because it is about individual skills based on the student... some learn quicker than others who need more time... that's why assessment starts from beginning to end... in fact the course's contents form different tasks from the beginning and these contents assess students from start to end to assess each student's attainment throughout. If it is restricted to the end, it would not reflect the student's real knowledge as s/he might be going through circumstances that affect their performance at a given stage.

A third teacher participant, Alaa, said that assessment can help in developing students' self-confidence. He explains,

The student must listen first and then practise speaking throughout the course... this is to reduce anxiety in conversations and develop self-confidence.

Therefore, these points were considered as supporting evidence, but did not count as subthemes.

Student participants as well seemed to favour formative assessment over summative assessment, considering that nine of the interviewed learners stated that continuous/formative assessment should be adopted in English language classrooms. Most of these student participants highlighted that continuous feedback from teachers helps students correct their mistakes, hence improve their English oral skills. Therefore, it can be argued that applying formative assessment and giving continuous feedback from teachers as well as students' self-regulation are three subthemes presented by student participants to support the theme under discussion (that is *Essential Areas for Development*).

Student participants raised few other points which they thought were essential to develop authentic English oral skills. These issues were individually broached, thus they were not frequent enough to be regarded as subthemes. One of these topics was that oral assessment should be based on conversations in which students eventually assess each other; in other words, peer assessment ought to be implemented in English classes. It was further added that students should be informed about the nature of the assessment and how it would be like

which, according to that particular learner, helps reduce anxiety. The third argument centred around how oral assessment would raise self-confidence. One student participant argued that securing high marks in oral assessment can enhance the learners' confidence in themselves and their skills and encourage them to work harder. Samar states,

...assessment induces feedback from the teacher... it informs the student about any learning or gain from the course... this assessment motivates you if you get good results to take up further a second, third, and fourth course... even parents get happy when they pay for improving language and other language skills.

The proposal put forward by Bandura and Schunk (1981) is yet again supported by the data. Exams and tests can be *proximal* motivators, because the feedback provided by the teacher informs the students of their progress, which instantly motivates them to put more effort into learning and to maintain that effort as Samar explains. Informational feedback, according to Dörnyei (1994), promotes the learner's self-efficacy making him/her believe that if they were able to improve their competence, they have the ability to continue to do so in the future. However, the second half of this quotation, where the student participant mentions how parents are pleased that they are getting their money's worth may indicate an influence of performativity by either the student or the teacher (Brown, 2015; Ball, 2001).

4.3 Obstacles to Improvement

Having discussed the essential areas required for the development of authentic English oral skills, both groups of participants explored some fundamental issues that hinder their progress. The researcher coded these topics into a theme titled *Obstacles to Improvement*. Teacher and student participants talked about several topics some of which were raised more frequently than others. These issues, in relation to oral practice and oral assessment, will be presented in this section, and the repeatedly mentioned issues were regarded as subthemes.

4.3.1 Oral Practice

Five teacher participants discussed the first subtheme of authentic oral practice barriers which is logistic barriers. The group of teacher participants considered that lack of facilities and equipment are the major hindrances that students encounter when they practise English, even in private language centres in Libya. Omar, a teacher participant explains,

Lack of facilities... there aren't enough equipment that help carry out the oral practice and help students to speak...

Another teacher participant, Ali, clarifies

...there are issues and problems... to begin with that there is a lack of teaching aids there aren't enough... of course this is in the private sector. For example, the main office in the private language centre... this one. The one I teach in. They try to provide a great environment for the students in terms of teaching aids and facilities. But some things right now are due to the current situation of the country... for example power cuts... frankly these have a negative impact on the student but this is only a temporary issue.

Another teacher participant, Alaa improvises. He indicates,

I try to use the facilities available... If they are unavailable, I try to provide them myself for listening for example... I can use body language for example to convey knowledge in an effective and contemporary way... also, based on the level of the student... If the speaking task is too difficult, I try to provide something simpler. One of the strategies I also implement in class is to get students listen to a dialogue and then they role play it in the classroom.

These findings that not having adequate facilities for practice is one of the demotivators supports the findings discussed in Dörnyei (1998a). The second subtheme that another group of five teacher participants touched upon was that students have problems with their oral skills which prevent them from progressing. Particularly, one teacher participant mentioned that students sometimes can be inactive learners, while another said that they rely heavily on memorisation. Three teacher participants attributed students' lack of progress to

their low level of oral skills, claiming that students' oral skills are far below their written language abilities and that they fear speaking. This is consistent with the findings reported in Farooqui (2007) in the Bangladeshi context, particularly in private universities. The fact that the country's population is monolingual, like Libya, and that these two contexts are part of the Expanding Circle (Kachru, 1985; Kachru and Nelson, 2006), in which English is spoken as a Lingua Franca (Graddol, 2006), makes it hard to see a direct impact outside the English language classroom as it has a very limited role. In the Bangladeshi context, just like the Libyan one, students rely on rote memorisation and are used to written tests only, which makes it challenging to switch to an environment which emphasises oral practice. The teacher participant Sara states,

The biggest thing is pronunciation and that students rely on memorising structures in their sentences. For example, they say 'drink water' instead of 'I want to drink water'.

The most frequently discussed subtheme was concerning the effect and power of parents on students' achievement. Foucault (1980, p. 198) recognises such "power means relations... organized, hierarchical, coordinated cluster of relations". Especially relevant here is the power of the *gaze* that those higher up in the hierarchy have over those lower in this structure (Foucault, 1977). This shift in power of surveillance (*ibid.*) is evident throughout the results and it will be discussed more fully once all the relevant themes are introduced.⁵ Seven teacher participants reported that certain authoritative parties have negative influence on the development of students' oral skills. Specifically, parents may exert pressure on their student children, which demotivates them. One teacher participant, Sara, says,

The most challenging thing I face is timing... The duration of a course... one month only... Students have high expectations and think they would speak perfectly at the end of a course... I tell them from the outset that in order to develop their oral skills, they need to have

⁵See page 156.

fulfilled all levels of a set of coursebooks as each subsequent level complements the preceding one... However, the financial capability of the students plays an important role... parents (probably those who pay for their sons and daughters' courses) expect them to learn everything during one month only... this creates extra pressure on the student as well.

Pressure to achieve high goals relating to oral skills within a short period of time indicates the lack of understanding from the parents' and sometimes the learners' part as to what learning a foreign language entails and how the curriculum is designed. High expectations may stem from a lack of communication. This lack of communication is twofold. First EFL course designers essentially come from a different cultural background to learners and teachers. MacLure (2006) emphasises the view of education workers as "mere conduits for the transmission of packages of knowledge into learners' heads, and assume that the knowledge thus conveyed can be assimilated uniformly, without delay or detour." This disempowers both students and teachers. The discourse of practice dictated in such curriculum packages deprives it of "flexibility and sensitivity to context and local needs" (*ibid.*, p. 7). It leaves little room for reflection, debilitates teacher agency and compromises learner autonomy (*ibid.*). Additionally, there seems to be a lack of adequate communication between parents and educators at the level of language centres. Ali, another teacher participant, reiterates this concern. He points out that,

There's an important point and that is some students lack the motivation because their parents pressure them into taking the course.

In terms of teacher-student relationships, Ali, a teacher participant strongly states, "I don't like to be strict when I'm teaching. I like to create a warm atmosphere... a friendly relationship not a limited [one]." Furthermore, four teacher participants talked about the negative effect that anxiety has on students' performance, which was the fourth subtheme under discussion. There is a plethora of literature on the effect of anxiety on language teaching and learning

(Cheng, Horwitz, and Schallert, 1999; Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, 1986; Horwitz, 1995). Anxiety is defined as “the subjective feeling of tension, apprehension, nervousness, and worry associated with an arousal of the autonomic nervous system” (Spielberger, 1983 cited in Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, 1986, p. 125). Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (*ibid.*) argue that foreign language anxiety is a conceptually distinct factor in language learning not to be confused with general anxiety. Foreign language anxiety is “the feeling of tension and apprehension specifically associated with second language contexts, including speaking, listening and learning” (MacIntyre and Gardner, 1994, p. 284). Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) ascertain three elements of foreign language anxiety. The first is communication apprehension. The immature mastery of a foreign language relative to the native language creates problems for authentic communication (*ibid.*). Pertinent to foreign learning, anxiety stems from learners’ fear that they will not comprehend *all* language input. The second is assessment anxiety. Learners fear that they are constantly tested and associate correction with failure (*ibid.*). The third component is fear of negative evaluation. Learners fear that they would appear less competent than their peers and being judged negatively by them, that they will make mistakes in the foreign language and that the teacher will correct their mistakes (*ibid.*). The propositions of Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (*ibid.*) are echoed in the current interview data. For some student participants, they stated that although they have the skills and ability to speak, they do not tend to participate because they feel anxious about making mistakes. A similar finding was demonstrated in a study in the Kazakhstani context. A study by Ziash (2013) showed that Kazakhstani EFL learners in Kazakhstan had high levels of anxiety relating to speaking activities whereby they worried about embarrassment, especially the anxiety brought about performing worse and teachers’ corrective feedback. Similarly von Wörde (2003) found that fear of making mistakes during speaking activities was a major source of anxiety on foreign language learners from a

myriad of L2 backgrounds in her study. Her students explained that especially error correction involved a reprimanding tone from the teacher and not having a sufficient opportunity to form their answer, which subsequently disrupted the focus of their thoughts and induced anxiety. However, several student participants showed a positive attitude to making mistakes. They reiterated the importance of knowing their mistakes in order to be able to avoid them in subsequent practice. A student participant, Fady stated,

I think oral assessment should be modified. It should be carried out weekly so the student continues to correct his/her mistakes throughout the course in order to avoid committing the same mistake over and over again.

This supports the argument put forth by Bandura and Schunk (1981) that assessments can be progress markers which serves a motivating purpose. It also shows how different learner vary in how they view/feel about classroom activities further consolidating the individual differences caused by factors of affect, that is motivation and anxiety. Another student participant, Reda asserted,

Feedback ought to be provided instantly as well as the following day where mistakes should be clarified further in addition to further practice. This is my perspective on this, of course this should be implemented throughout the lessons of the course not in the form of a test.

Teacher participants brought a few more issues into attention, but they were mentioned once only. The first was regarding using technology in teaching. One of the educators claimed that students are not good enough with utilising technology in learning because they had not used advanced equipment before. A second minor point – but pertinent to anxiety associated with foreign language learning – was about punishing students for making mistakes. A teacher participant, Alaa argued that punishing students for making mistakes will inhibit them from learning and discourage them from trying again. In answer to why he thinks oral practice is essential, he says,

...the more the student speaks, the less mistakes s/he makes... that is why oral practice is really important... but some teachers do not utilise this method of teaching and they punish the student for making language mistakes.. that's why the student is constantly afraid and refrains from speaking even though at times s/he knows the answer or is knowledgeable of the subject matter at hand.

This statement illustrates the teacher participant's awareness of language learning-related anxiety and the recommendations scholars posit to minimise its effects (for example Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, 1986; Young, 1992). Student participants on the other hand, expressed their concerns regarding various obstacles that impede the development of their authentic English oral skills. The first subtheme comprises the most reiterated issue that nine student participants tackled during the interviews regarding the opportunity to practice oral skills. Student participants nearly unanimously criticised the fact that they did not have time to practice authentic English whether inside or outside the classroom. Some of these learners highlighted that it was necessary for teachers to provide versatile settings where everyday English is spoken. The second subtheme which four of the student participants focused on was their low level of oral proficiency. The third subtheme which was stressed by three student participants who shed light on exposure to high quality naturalistic and authentic language input. These learners reported that they did not have the opportunity to practice their oral skills with genuine speakers of the target language (native speakers).

4.3.2 Oral Assessment

When obstacles of authentic oral assessment were discussed, teacher participants did not seem to have many common subthemes. The most repeatedly mentioned subtheme, which was highlighted by three teacher participants, was that students become anxious when they know they will be assessed. This stems from a chain of events taking place regularly in classrooms. Students are constantly and informally being assessed in classrooms and are given feedback on such assessments. According to Evans and Engelberg (1988),

most of the time learners are unaware of the complex grading systems and the experience of being graded or labelled with little knowledge as to what it entails or means seems to be associated with a feeling of helplessness. Lower-achieving students seem to feel constantly reminded of their lower worth instead of receiving help in making progress. Pollard and Triggs (2001) found that assessment results are viewed by learners as a form of official judgement that affect self-confidence, social status and some form of social stigma. Even in cases where teachers intended class assessment to be formative, it was viewed by students as summative in purpose (*ibid.*). The anxiety that students experienced was the result of students exposure to greater risks when teachers prioritised performance over learning processes (*ibid.*). In a culture where individuals are conditioned to perceive assessment as high stakes for a very long time, it becomes very difficult to see it otherwise. The official judgement referred to as normalised gaze by Foucault (1977) is a facet of what he calls ‘modern indoctrinated institutions’ such as schools and universities. Foucault (1984, p. 197) explains, “the examination... a normalizing gaze, a surveillance that makes it possible to qualify, to classify, and to punish”. In the process of such judgements, students are faced with assessment processes that reflect value judgements dependent on specific cultures or a historical time point rather than being, according to Crossouard (2012, p. 189), “‘objective’ neutral processes that allow a ‘true’ reflection of individual ability”. These institutions make use of carefully accumulated data from individuals and as a result, establishing norms from each case, which are later used by whomever has control (Foucault, 1977). Consequently, the examination candidate is viewed as a ‘case’ and is compared with others “in his very own individuality” (*ibid.*, p. 191). Such assessment according to Foucault (1984, p. 197), not only “makes it possible to qualify, to classify, and to punish”, but also diminishes reflection and creativity.

Two subthemes relevant to obstacles of oral assessment appeared in student participants’ interviews; the first was about the need for constant feedback and

formative assessment, and the second was concerning the anxiety and fear student participants suffer from before exams. Three student participants expressed their annoyance that teachers did not provide constant feedback during classes for assessment, rather teachers tend to use end of term exams in order to assess students' performance. Further, two student participants indicated that fear and anxiety before exams were the stumbling stones to that hampered them from achieving high marks.

4.4 Overcoming the Obstacles

Having identified the obstacles that hinder the development of student participants' authentic English oral skills, teacher and student participants discussed a variety of techniques and methods they used in order to overcome these difficulties. The major subthemes which were extracted from the interviews with both groups of informants will be listed next. These subthemes are about oral practice and assessment, and they form the third theme in this study which is *Overcoming the Obstacles*.

4.4.1 Oral Practice

The first subtheme in teacher participants' interview scripts was to encourage students to practice oral skills in classrooms. Six teacher participants talked about the techniques they follow in order to encourage students to get involved in oral practice. In particular, four language experts mentioned that they ask learners to role-play and get engaged in conversations by asking and answering questions. Alia uses a model conversation and then engages students in a role-play activity. She points out,

I give them a written version of a model conversation... after reading, I ask them to role-play in pairs without looking at the book and using their own words.

Farage also uses models as his contingency plan when students have difficulty engaging in a speaking activity. He specifies,

If the speaking task is too difficult, I try to provide something simpler. One of the strategies I also implement in class is to get students listen to a dialogue and then they role-play it in the classroom.

Alaa seems to be passionate about role-play and speaks extensively about the topic. He responds,

...they[learners] need to be placed in different situations... So for example in a restaurant, I would be the restaurant manager or one of the students is the restaurant manager. Another one is a waiter or waitress and another is a customer. This creates a situation where everybody has a role and speaks accordingly... sometimes we do role-play of the situation where we are in court... one is the judge and the other is a lawyer etc. and you get the idea... So I would give them some vocabularies and phrases relevant to these situations and students would try to use those new words in that situation and there is a competition between them.

Bandura (1977) puts forward that self-regulation can be acquired through observing modelled behaviours. This notion of modelling and how it helps learners incorporate new strategies has been attested to by research (Wood and Bandura, 1989; Caprara et al., 2008). However, for observational learning to be effective, it requires the support of attention and retention proposed by Bandura (1977). Attention refers to the extent of exposure and notice dedicated to an observed behaviour -- not all observable behaviours are noticed (*ibid.*). This depends on the EFL learner's characteristics, features of the modelled activity/oral practice (salience, complexity, intrinsically rewarding or not), structural arrangement of interactions, and most importantly, the associational patterns (*ibid.*). When EFL learners regularly associate with native speakers or speakers of English either through imposition or preference, it regulates quality and quantity of observational experience (*ibid.*) be it inside or outside the EFL classroom. Retention on the other hand, relates to mentally storing modelled behaviours relying on imaginal or verbal representations (*ibid.*). The learner

needs to remember a language behaviour/practice from the EFL classroom through visual or verbal representations in order to be able to imitate it when the occasion arises, for example when they are faced with native speakers, in an exam or in real life situations. If a learner observes a modelled behaviour, and notices it but cannot recall it days or weeks later, then s/he will fail to imitate it. Oral rehearsal can also assist long-term retention (*ibid.*, p. 26). In language schools, teacher participants seem to find this process helpful for learning and thus apply it in their classroom.

Sasaki (1997) compared students' second language responses from production questionnaires and role-plays and he found out that role plays induced longer responses and entailed a larger variation of strategies compared to production questionnaires. She attributed this difference to the interactive nature of role plays. Yen, Hou, and Chang (2015) also demonstrated that learners improved their speaking and writing skills through role-plays by using interactive speaking and listening on Facebook and Skype.

In addition, two teacher participants said that they support and help students to speak even if they make mistakes. A teacher participant embraces learner mistakes as part of the learning process and asserts avoiding punishment. Rania states,

...sometimes I make a mistake on purpose and I ask the students to spot it and to give the student the opportunity to speak with me without being harsh.. also without any consequences (punishment) if they answer wrongly because they are still in the process of learning... thus mistakes are expected.

Another teacher participant, indicated that he caters for individual differences by varying the task difficulty according to the student level. Farage puts forward,

Students have different abilities... some are shy than others... some are cleverer than others... some don't care... some learn quicker than others who need more time... that's why assessment starts from beginning to end.

Furthermore, the second major subtheme that six teacher participants highlighted was regarding giving students the opportunity to practice. Three teacher participants expressed their way of applying this subtheme by stating that they allow extra time for free oral practice in classroom. Adam explains that,

By giving the student more opportunities and be more informed... and given plenty of preparation time ahead of the assessment... giving the student plenty of choices during the assessment .. most importantly, the student should have had practice in the specific assessment tasks during the course

Another teacher participant mentioned that he gives away extra marks for oral participation. Ali states,

More marks should be allocated to oral assessment than written assessment. Written assessment has always been allocated more marks and this is why students focus more on written assessment.

This seems to be a practice reflecting the deep-rooted societal belief in the power of evaluation. A practice that is transferred from the public education sector. One teacher participant, Alia, seems to be against the focus on marks and grades and the whole practice of the ability to accurately measure learning. Alia contends,

Sometimes the criteria do not suit the student... the centre bases assessment outcome on marks and grades and not on skills learnt... Some skills are allocated a low proportion of the total grade.

This view reflects the beliefs of Biesta (2009, p. 35) who disputes reliance on marks and scores and the educational discussion that embraces statistical measurements which, according to him, do not “measure what we value” rather than value what we (can) measure. In such a discourse, success is based on students’ performance in tests instead of genuine, thoughtful, and individualistic learning. It is worth-mentioning that gatekeepers in many private language centres do not necessarily come from an educational background. Most are

simply businessmen/women, who mainly focus on supply and demand. Measuring success through test scores is not an alien notion in the Libyan context.

In addition, some teacher participants suggest giving the students the opportunity to select a topic they see fit. Sara says, “the student picks a topic and talks about it freely.” Two other teacher participants reported that they supply students with the vocabulary required to perform the oral task before the learners start to practise,⁶ or gives them a reading task beforehand about the same topic to refresh their word bank. Scrivener (2011) recommends that one of the techniques to get students talking is to allow students to pick a topic and a *cue*. This cue can be in the form of a provocative question or a newspaper article, both of which would instigate a discussion among learners.

Three teacher participants referred to the better learning-teaching environment that private language centres provide which counted as the third subtheme. These language educator participants underlined that teachers in private centres tend to be approachable. Alia states “The first thing is that I must make a student comfortable with me... I try every means to get the student to talk.” They also mentioned that students (or their families) pay money in the private sector in order to get more effective teaching and be more prepared to pass some international exams. Rania puts forward,

...some students choose a private centre to be prepared for assessment relating to international tests... they do courses because they had failed courses from the public sector. There are other students on the other hand who do other courses because they don't feel they benefited that much from public sector courses and so they pay to learn general English language skills.

One teacher participant indicated that she tries hard to be more patient than she normally is so that students can follow with her and gradually benefit from the course. She also states that she tends to simplify oral tasks to guarantee more student engagement. Sara clarifies,

⁶See quotations on page 130

When you talk about speaking, there is feeling of pressure to be perfect in English language. For this reason, speaking practice should start from very early stages and every stage has its own tasks that suits the level of student... step-by-step, the student will find him/herself with the ability to overcome all the problems that he/she faces in speaking. We as teachers need to be more patient and more tolerant in teaching speaking. The first thing I've noticed when I teach speaking is that the student asks me to be patient and allow them to take baby steps... because they are not accustomed to it that much... when it comes to speaking they find themselves in a situation... so it's the teacher's role to help the students overcome this situation.

Teacher participants mentioned two more procedures they tend to follow, aiming to help improve students oral skills. These two points were mentioned individually by two different teacher participants, thus the researcher did not consider them as subthemes. The first point was that mentioning future jobs and careers are likely to motivate students to work harder, particularly to improve their oral skills. The teachers view goal setting, studying abroad or for career advancement, as an instrumental motivation for students, which is a goal they share as expressed in Chapter 3. Although the majority of demotivators for foreign language learners are found to be teacher-induced (Zhang, 2007; Falout and Maruyama, 2004; Arai, 2004; Oxford, 2001), here we see that the teachers serve a motivating role for their students. The second technique that may help in motivating students to speak, according to one of the teacher participants, was to set a time limit for students when they do a speaking task in order to pressurise them to speak spontaneously. Salem suggests,

...it's best to give them a limited amount of time, and the student teaches him/herself to stick to a limited amount of time... so he/she makes the effort, because if time was unlimited he/she will delay answering and will not take matters seriously and thinking and focus decrease... of course in oral activities there are important aspects and that for example you allow one minute where the topic is presented and the student has a minute to prepare and then tell them that you have another minute to speak non-stop and then you observe whether he/she can manage in one minute. I tried this technique and I felt that it encourages students to speak and especially knowing that there is a time limit the student will speak out because in his mind there is pressure to say what they think of but without worrying

about grammar. Therefore time limiting is excellent because if you allow more time, the student will feel overly comfortable, whereas in less time the student is bound to make mistakes and learn from them because speech is supposed to be spontaneous.

4.4.2 Oral Assessment

The first subtheme was highlighted by half of the teacher participants who clearly indicated that they endeavour to use formative assessment methods, not summative assessment where students are tested at the end of the course. Omar states, “[i]n my opinion, assessment throughout the course is better than the end”. The second subtheme, which is quite related to the first one, was about varying assessment techniques and providing constant feedback. Three teacher participants underlined the importance of these points and said that they tend to differentiate their assessment methods and give instant feedback on students’ oral performance. Salem proposes,

Giving students plenty of opportunities to speak in any topic they choose. Alternatively, they can deliver a presentation about the preparation of a topic

The last subtheme about assessment was pertinent to using assessment for learning. Three teacher participants stated that they utilise assessment techniques to monitor students’ performance and modify their teaching methods when they feel students are not progressing. Haifa explains,

...[as a teacher,] I need to know whether my teaching has an effect or not... I need to assess their performance to correct mistakes and provide feedback.

Scrivener (2011) encourages teachers to reflect on their teaching process and be open to the possibility of change should it be required. He argues for a cycle of reflection not only forward but also backwards. A teacher, he (*ibid.*, p. 386) asserts that instead of assuming that teachers “know it all”. He further explains that teachers ought to reflect on past learning experiences alongside a willingness to experiment new and different techniques moving forward.

One of the teacher participants reported that he provided language learners with the assessment criteria in order for them to prepare themselves for any form of assessment. He added that this helped in promoting students' self-confidence during assessment. Omar argues,

Because it will be like training preparation... they are made aware of assessment criteria in order to reduce anxiety and develop self-confidence.

Student participants did not discuss much when it comes to their efforts to develop their oral assessment. The first subtheme that six student participants highlighted was about their attempts to prepare themselves when they are informed that they will have oral assessment. Half of these student participants mentioned that being prepared for assessment reduces anxiety and fear. Reda, a student participant declares,

...[W]e are made aware of the assessment criteria prior to assessment... for example dialogues, vocabulary, etc.... this helps me overcome my fears... it helps me feel less anxious and more confident by knowing what I'm up against...

Surprisingly, the second subtheme was that assessment results do not really matter. Three learner participants indicated that assessment results do not affect their proficiency level, whereas practice and having the initiative to speak the target language is what genuinely helps them improve, and what they care about. Hind argues that, "performance in tests does not necessarily reflect their [learners'] true skills." Finally, one student participant emphasised that he is always ready for all types of assessment and he simply does nothing extra to deal with tests and exams. Fady states, "...from the outset of the course, the teacher preps us for this... we do a lot of listening, reading and speaking and activities inside the classroom."

4.5 Discussion

This subsection presents an in-depth discussion of student and teacher participants' perspectives by presenting the subthemes and the participants view in relation to oral practice and assessment. Student participants' perspectives are presented first followed by teacher participants' perspective. The last subsection presents a comparison between both groups where relevant.

4.5.1 Student Participant Perspectives

When student participants discussed authentic English oral practice and assessment in private centres in Libya, they referred to various issues that they think were essential to the development of learners' speaking and listening skills. Student participants' most frequently mentioned subtheme was the importance of self-confidence and its effect on improving their oral skills. Language learners indicated that self-confidence is the spark for their development. This means that being more self-confident, they attempt to practise oral skills more frequently, and the more they practise, the better their oral skills are likely to become. In other words, the situation is comparable to a triangle where the point on each head (confidence, practice and improvement) leads to the other. This is well-aligned with the mediational processes proposed by Bandura (1977). He argues that human beings tend to associate behaviours to consequences through agentic dynamics which effect the learning process (*ibid.*). One such mediational process he proposes is *motor reproduction* where the learner converts mental representations to actions (*ibid.*). Such process involves organising cognitive responses, initiation, monitoring and refinement based on feedback (*ibid.*, p. 27). Feedback is bi-directional: learners' performance in classroom activities allows teachers to revise instruction and teachers' feedback, in turn, helps learners revise their performance. For this reason, it is vital to enact oral practice as it helps teachers and learners alike. Observational learning through modelled behaviour

then requires motivation, which in turn depends on the consequences and whether they are valued and promoted or otherwise punished (Bandura, 1977). In language schools, students usually pay to be in those courses for personal reasons such as career advancement. Whenever self-confidence is brought into attention in formal instruction, self-efficacy and how it helps learners in setting goals and achieving them comes into play (Bandura, 1994). Showing confidence and courage to take part in classroom activities is certainly a manifestation of self-efficacy. It has been argued that successes establish a robust sense of self-efficacy, whereas failure is likely to diminish it. Therefore, it is not surprising that student participants emphasised the positive impact of self-confidence on their development, and how it stimulates their desire to participate in classroom oral practice activities. This is consistent with the evidence from Orafi and Borg (2009) who reports that students do not believe that they can perform oral tasks in classrooms. Consequently, self-confidence is a crucial factor in students' oral proficiency enhancement and it improves with extra practice.

The second major subtheme student participants highlighted was the extra time that ought to be allocated for oral practice in classrooms. Apparently, the more time is allotted to oral practice, the better opportunity is likely to be given to students to get involved in oral tasks. Learners participating in the current study realise the importance of oral practice in classrooms and note that it has been sidelined by teachers.

The fundamental question, however, is whether teachers deliberately ignore practising oral skills in classrooms, or whether it is a hurdle they cannot circumvent? It is undoubtedly known to language experts and educators that oral practice is extremely essential to help learners progress and improve their oral skills. There is certainly a school of thought that opposes the pressure to practice speaking and hinges acquisition mainly on comprehensible input. Krashen (1982, pp. 6–7) claims that,

...real language acquisition develops slowly, and speaking skills

emerge significantly later than listening skills, even when conditions are perfect. The best methods are therefore those that supply 'comprehensible input' in low anxiety situations, containing messages that students really want to hear. These methods do not force early production in the second language but allow students to produce when they are 'ready', recognizing that improvement comes from supplying communicative and comprehensible input, and not from forcing and correcting production.

However, several scholars attest to the importance of practice in learning in general and language learning in particular. Bandura (1977) asserts the importance of motor reproduction. His assertion stems from the requirement of converting mental representations to actions in order for learning to be fulfilled. In terms of foreign language learning, Mackey (2007) puts forward that,

...producing language gives learners opportunities to notice the difference between their interlanguage and the target, to test their hypotheses about how the target language works, and to consciously reflect on their learning.

Furthermore, Mackey (*ibid.*) puts forward that classroom practice helps create learning opportunities through negotiating meaning (McDonough, 2005), noticing the gap through feedback (Mackey and Oliver, 2002; Swain and Lapkin, 2002; Black, Harrison, and Lee, 2003), testing hypotheses and automatising speaking through modifying language outputs. The latter view on the importance of oral practice for language learning is reflected by a student participant, Haifa, who states that,

I try to communicate and speak with them [teachers and other students] correctly so I can get used to correct pronunciation from the start... so my tongue gets used to pronunciation... I try to speak inside the classroom... making mistakes is essential and in such situations, it is the teacher's role to correct... and this is when the student benefits... whereas being silent in the classroom and not talking, to exacerbate the situation at home when you are not talking to anyone [in English], pronunciation will be wrong... within time pronunciation will improve if you speak but if you are quiet in the classroom and out, it is not good because speaking a lot and even making mistakes will be detected by the teacher, who will know you have made a mistake and will give feedback on the aspects you need to work and focus on.

Student participants indicate that they enrol in private language centres to receive more effective language teaching. One student participant, Adel states,

...the opportunity to practice speaking in private language centres is bigger than that in universities due to a smaller number of students and frankly a larger benefit in practising speaking English.

Another student participant, Samah explains,

I hope the government or the university administration would introduce the subject of oral skills throughout the eight undergraduate academic terms so that students wouldn't have to go to private centres as it can be costly for some families who cannot afford it.

The third subtheme that student participants agreed it should be available is effective teaching methods and better classroom techniques. Student participants stated that they find these effective pedagogical strategies in private centres, hence they enrol to benefit from them. One student participant, Haifa said “in the private centre, it is the first time I ever hear of phonetics”. Learner participants mentioned that teachers use better teaching techniques, but they did not particularly elaborate on that in detail. However, it can be argued that teachers' teaching strategies in private centres encourage students to get involved more constantly in oral practice, thus learner participants describe teachers' methods as more effective. Two student participants praised the variety of activities teachers offer in private centres and the student participants highlighted they are constantly challenged when they are involved in doing activities. It has been argued that varying classroom activities can be more effective (Baecher et al., 2012) and caters for individual differences such as memory and intelligence (Dörnyei and Skehan, 2003b). Including classroom tasks that involve various levels of difficulty is likely to warrant challenging activities for students of various abilities. In addition, one student participant reported that teacher's praising statements and supportive words keep him constantly motivated to pay more effort and work harder. Ibrahim, a student participant stated that, “...if the teacher tells me that I have improved, I will be more

motivated and I will be more willing to learn.” This is a form of extrinsic motivation when the learner is motivated due to external factors and teacher’s praise can be one of these factors (Al Kaboody, 2013). In this regard, Bandura (1989) argues that motivation can be gauged by how much effort an individual pays to achieve a set goal and the amount of perseverance in the face of impediments. However, despite the fact that teachers can positively affect learners and encourage them to multiply the effort they invest to fulfil their aims, this improvement may only be temporary if subsequent efforts prove to be unsuccessful (Schunk, 1995).

The first subtheme student participants discussed congruent to oral assessment was the need to adopt formative assessment. This assessment approach was granted a substantial amount of support by Black and Wiliam (1998) in their seminal work on Assessment for Learning. Formative assessment guarantees integrating ongoing assessment throughout the learning-teaching process not only to evaluate and monitor the learning progress of each learner, but also to reflect on and modify instruction according to the learner’s needs. Additionally, Katz (2012) asserts that by linking assessment to learning one can determine how accountable a course is. The second subtheme underscored the student participants’ need for constant feedback throughout the course. Learners expressed their need to be corrected or supported in every stage of their English oral skills development. This assessment requirement is based on supporting the learning process through providing effective feedback (Black and Wiliam, 1998). Several studies (Crooks, 1988; Kluger and DeNisi, 1996; Nyquist, 2003) provide further evidence to advocate and support Black and Wiliam’s arguments for formative assessment.

Self-regulation is the third subtheme that student participants emphasised during the interviews. Self-regulation is a process in which learners set a particular goal and strive to achieve it while adjusting their behaviour and plans to do so (Erlich and Russ-Eft, 2011). Self-regulation is a fundamental concept in

Bandura's theory. Bandura argues that learners develop self-regulatory functions by observing models (Bandura, 1989; Caprara et al., 2008). It seems that student participants in private language centres find the opportunity to self-regulate and adjust their aims according to their needs as well as the teaching environment. Fady, a student participant, said that,

...some teachers assess throughout the course and this is much better for me as a student to be able to know my general level and what I gained from the lessons and most importantly not to repeat the same mistakes again.

Furthermore, one of the student participants who suggested that oral assessment needs to be based on conversations after which assessment takers assess each other deemed peer assessment helpful. Black and Wiliam (2009) posit five key practices of AfL one of which is peer assessment. However, peer assessment was criticised by Crossouard (2012) whose observations revealed that high-achievers may contemptuously disparage low-achievers, and language learners are vulnerable to this type of criticism. She argues that derision towards low-attaining students can be viewed as a form of power (*ibid.*). In a Libyan context and as a result of socio-historically induced attitude towards foreign languages, this extends further to the opposite direction. When practising English language communicatively – be it inside or outside the language classroom – Libyan learners are subject to peer derision (Aloreibi and Carey, 2017). Libyan students complain that they are not taken seriously by their peers and are accused of being egotists (*ibid.*). Outside the classroom, it can be socially taboo to use English language in public (*ibid.*).

In addition, one of the student participants suggested that language learners are supposed to be aware of the nature of the assessment and how/what it would be like in order to reduce fear and anxiety among learners. This point was broached by an individual student participant albeit it sounds vital and its application is likely to positively influence students' achievement. Ismail, a student participant states that,

...we are made aware of the assessment criteria prior to assessment... this helps me overcome my fears... it [assessment criteria] helps me feel less anxious and more confident by knowing what I am up against... In comparison to universities, I have no idea what I will be facing and so the students get very anxious... this rarely happens in universities and the student is assessed based on written work only and without any feedback.

However, it can be said that a form of assessment that students need to be informed about is expected to be a type of summative assessment which counts for a considerable part of pass or fail decision, unlike ongoing formative assessment which aims to assess and monitor students' progress. People in charge (for example, teachers or curriculum designers) impose this type of summative assessment to serve as a controlling tool in order for these authorities to sustain power and dominate the educational process (Broadfoot, 1996; Gipps, 1999). Finally, one student postulated that oral assessment plays a role in raising learners' self-confidence. This student argued that performing well or obtaining high marks on oral tests can boost self-efficacy in learners and consequently encourage them to invest more effort in classroom activities. In answer to the question enquiring whether oral assessment has added to their learning experience, Samah, a student participant explains that,

...Yes, first and foremost confidence and courage towards the end of the course especially if the assessment results were great and I felt that I have improved... this is a great incentive for me... outside the classroom or at work... I feel like it has added a positive aspect to my life and motivates me to take up more courses especially that the methods followed in courses are different from government-led institutes and universities... this is the most important thing about assessment... it is the attainment, self-confidence, the experience in learning... dealing with language during conversations with fluent and competent speakers of English...

Another student participant, Hind, demonstrates an awareness of the differences between summative and formative assessments in terms of their impact on self-confidence. She indicates that,

...Oral assessment is better than a test... The word test makes the student afraid and lack self-confidence especially in foreign language

learning... it is scary for the students learning a foreign language... so it should be based on a conversation between two of the students and at the end the teacher provides feedback and then each student tries to assess the other and the teacher listens and then gives his/her own feedback.

Student participants raised several impediments that obstruct their oral English language progress, and they were coded as a theme (*Obstacles to Improvement*). The first subtheme that nine out of eleven student respondents emphasised was the fact that they did not have the opportunity to practice oral/aural skills in classrooms before they enrolled in courses in private language centres, hence having poor oral skills. This group of students attributed the lack of opportunity to practise oral skills to factors such as not having adequate time during lessons or not being given opportunities by teachers. For instance, a couple of students said that oral practice depends on the teacher, indicating that teachers did not vary their techniques to include oral practice activities. In fact, some teachers tend to ignore oral/aural practice activities in Libyan schools (Orafi and Borg, 2009; Shihiba, 2011). Also, it can be said that teachers did not plan well to allocate time for oral practice, or they did not enhance students' talking time on the account of teachers' talking time.

Moreover, a group of students complained about not being engaged in life-like situations where they need to produce everyday language such as doing shopping or seeing a doctor. Using authentic materials and doing authentic activities has a huge advantage for the EFL classroom. Authentic materials can motivate learners because they convey that the target language is used by real people in everyday life (Nuttall, 1996). Exposure to authentic language provides profuse language input, which enables learners to cope in real life communications (Nunan, 1997). It bridges the gap between classroom learning and real world (Kelly et al., 2002). Authentic materials and activities are inherently active, engaging and stimulating (Little, Devitt, and Singleton, 1988; Lee, 1995; Peacock, 1997). They help the learners in bootstrapping the target language more effectively (Weyers, 1999). Studies have demonstrated their positive effect

on learners' attainment. For example, a study by Otte (2006) examined the effect of real aural materials on listening comprehension skills on adult ESL learners enrolled in an advanced listening course. His results showed that the materials had a positive impact in that it improved the participants' performance and their motivation to learn better. According to Harmer (1994), positive effects of authentic materials and language use are evident in that they help learners improve their target language output, they increase the rate of learning, and increase learners' confidence to deal with real life communication.

In addition, other students even went further and said they needed to be in natural settings where authentic target language is spoken (i.e. being in an English-speaking country and/or engaging in conversations with native speakers). Some of these students indicated that they try to indulge in conversations with their friends/relatives who have lived abroad in order to be exposed to high quality target language and have the chance to practise authentic spoken English. This point was raised by Omar (2014) and Orafi and Borg (2009) who claim that English teachers in the Libyan context lack proficiency in English oral skills which makes them use their L1 to give instructions. This was said by a student participant, Ibrahim, who explains that

Most students don't know how to distinguish between when to ask *do* and when to ask *are*. A lot of mistakes are corrected by friends who live abroad, for example, *I will didn't*. I say this phrase and my friend from abroad says, *say again. I don't understand!*. This is what helps in practising English language. This is why conversation practice is considered an important factor to improve one's English language.

Two other subthemes emerged in students' interviews. Three language learner participants expressed their annoyance that teachers did not provide constant feedback to assess and evaluate students' performance, contrary to that teachers relied more on end of term exams to check students' progress. It seems that these concerned students are opponents of summative assessment and prefer assessment to be ongoing over the course period. Bandura (1977) stresses the learners' need to adjust their actions according to their mental representations so

that learners can refine their responses based on the feedback and environment monitoring. It can be argued that constant feedback assists students to alter their actions and adjust their behaviour, which eventually reflects on better learning outcomes. Similarly, teachers may modify their instruction to meet the level and progress of students that teachers receive from providing ongoing feedback. Additionally, Wiliam (2011) illustrates that formative assessment is a more valid form of assessment compared to summative assessment. Wiliam adds that decision makers exploit assessment to exercise power over learners and even teachers and this might be in a form one assessment session. However, formative assessment in the shape of constant feedback aims at helping students perform more effectively. A student participant, Samah, elucidates this aspect. She explains,

...because through oral assessment, one can measure if you'd made any progress .. whether you need additional courses... you try to listen more and learn about your shortcomings in order to fix them so that's why oral assessment is important because the teacher gives you feedback which informs you of the weaknesses that you have.

It seems that Samah is very keen on constantly setting-goals based on her teacher's feedback of her performance in oral practice. She perceives this type of assessment as a tool to progress and develop her learning and speak/listen more effectively. Another student, Ismail, reiterates Samah's perspective on formative assessment and feedback. Ismail believes that,

Within time, pronunciation will improve if you speak but if you're quiet in the classroom and outside, it is not good because speaking a lot and even making mistakes will be detected by the teacher, who will know you've made a mistake and will give feedback on the aspects you need to work and focus on.

Further evidence to support the need for formative assessment comes from students' second subtheme relevant to this matter. Learners indicated that they tend to feel fearful and anxious when they are informed that they will be assessed. Perhaps, students realise that assessment counts hugely towards their passing or

failing the course, hence the feeling of fear and anxiety. It can be assumed that the form of assessment that makes students exhibit a negative feeling tend to be a harsh and unpleasant experience. In the Libyan context, Saleh and Zakaria (2013) note that students' poor results might be related to the type of assessment used and how students prepare for it. Also, it has been widely reported that language testing can cause fear and anxiety among learners (for example Azher, Anwar, and Naz, 2010; Arabai, 2014). The following quotation was from one of the students, Ibrahim, who indicates that

...and at that point (test time) there is a lot of fear and dispersion of thoughts... you cannot speak... information is lost... even pronunciation is lost... there is some sort of dread compared to a situation where you are abroad (in the L2 country) and speak the language normally without fear... but when you are told that you are being assessed .. tested... you are afraid and your thoughts are dispersed.

Having identified some obstacles that students have encountered in Libya, it is sensible to think of solutions to overcome these hindrances. Some of these problems do not require considerable efforts to avoid. However, teachers probably do not tend to do that for several reasons including their lack of proficiency to lead conversations in English (Omar, 2014), Teachers are constantly monitored by higher authorities who impose strict bureaucracies on their inferiors. Foucault (1980) explains that such type of organised hierarchical relations indicate presence of power. Also, this sort of censorship on teachers in public schools is comparable to prisoners being observed by guards within a restricted facility (Foucault, 1977). The notion of the *panopticon* developed by Foucault (*ibid.*) portrays the current situation in Libyan educational institutions. Foucault postulates that knowledge is one form of power, which can in turn be acquired from power, resulting in it, though not thwarting it. New knowledge can be produced through the power of the gaze and observation. His theory (*ibid.*, p. 27) asserts that knowledge is power,

Knowledge linked to power, not only assumes the authority of 'the truth' but has the power to make itself true. All knowledge, once

applied in the real world, has effects, and in that sense at least, 'becomes true.' Knowledge, once used to regulate the conduct of others, entails constraint, regulation and the disciplining of practice. Thus, 'there is no power relation without the correlative constitution of a field of knowledge, nor any knowledge that does not presuppose and constitute at the same time, power relations.

Foucault chose the *panopticon*, which is an architectural setting designed in the 19th century by Jeremy Bentham, as a system of regulation in prisons but was also extended to hospitals, factories and schools. The *panopticon* provided a powerful form of enforcement established through incessant observation of subjects/prisoners. This would enable guards (those higher up in the system hierarchy) to incessantly gaze inside each cell (or in this case classroom) from their standpoint in a high central tower, without being seen by their subjects. The continuous gaze gave them power, that is the power of *observation*, a technique that was used to control prisoners/subjects (teachers, students, education workers). Such control is gained by the internalisation that prisoners/subjects are being constantly observed. The analogy made using the *panopticon* enabled Foucault to examine the relationship between social control systems and subjects in a disciplinary situation such as the relationship between educational institutions/ministry and education workers. According to Foucault (1977), power can be derived by observing others. His perspective extends to the disciplinary nature of examination, which makes reference to "the examination... a normalizing gaze, a surveillance that makes it possible to qualify, to classify, and to punish" (Foucault, 1984, p. 197).

MacLure (2006) further supports this notion by asserting that powerful figures in the educational field coerce other workers in the same field to adopt their rigid guidelines and regulations when it comes to reporting and evaluating everyone's performance. She points out that those in higher authorities impose firm criteria. Education workers from students, teachers, education inspectors and many others, each would have to report their activities and have their work assessed by those higher in authority. Students are monitored by teachers –

especially in exams –, who are in turn monitored by headteachers or education inspectors. The Ministry appoints specialists to prepare curricula for teachers. Such curricula includes teacher's book, which inform teachers of what exercise to do at what time and what to say in doing so (*ibid.*). Foucault (1970) and MacLure (2006) emphasise the role of discourse in power. It is embodied in words such as *criteria* and *measures* listed on the Ministry of Education website in specifying the role of the pedagogical inspector. Such terms have a diminishing impact on the role of the teacher in addition to a normalised and standardised judgement Foucault (1977). Biesta (2009) on the other hand shares similar views with regards to student examinations as he challenges the educational practice and discourse especially that which relies on statistics that fail to measure what is valued and rather values what is measurable. Specifically oral proficiency, argues Madsen (1983) is harder to measure compared to form which is why policy makers and teachers tend to focus on it. Biesta (2009) argues that we live in a culture that values scores. Success, he (*ibid.*) argues, is based on how students perform in tests compared nationally and/or internationally minimising the importance of true, reflective, and democratic learning. Seven teacher participants reported that such authoritative parties have negative influence on development of students' oral skills. Specifically, parents may exert pressure on their student children, which demotivates them. This is consistent with the previous findings that a learner's 'affiliative drive' (Ausubel, Novak, and Hanesian, 1978 cited in Dörnyei, 1994, p. 278) is a key motivator and pressure to do well may result in reduced self-confidence, which subsequently can frustrate a learner's confidence to acquire their parents' approval and demotivate him/her (Falout and Maruyama, 2004). Therefore, it can be said that these obstacles students face to develop their oral/aural skills in public schools are the results of harsh bureaucracies imposed on teachers and learners.

4.5.2 Teacher Participant Perspectives

Teacher participants' discussion of several essential elements for the development of students' English oral skills lead to generate the theme *Essential Areas for Development*. The first subtheme teacher participant almost unanimously brought into attention was that oral practice enhances students' self-confidence. The same subtheme was discussed in the previous section when students' views were under investigation. Self-confidence is a crucial factor in developing learners' self-efficacy (Bandura, 1986) which, if kept high, can encourage students to be more actively involved in the learning-teaching process. The positive impact of practice on self-confidence has been highlighted in several studies (for example Fauzan, 2016; Meng, 2010). One of the teacher participants, Sara, stated that,

At the end of the course I felt the student has built self-confidence and a learning experience and is capable of dealing with this language during conversations, you feel s/he is comfortable and has courage and with this confidence s/he has the ability to hold up a conversation anytime, anywhere.

Most language educator participants understand that oral practice can be a source of motivation for learners to work harder. The more students practise the target language in the classroom, the higher their desire to improve becomes. Learners' motivation is a key concept in Bandura's theory as well as AfL. Language teacher participants believe that practising English can enhance learners' motivation and improve their learning outcomes. The following quotation is taken from the script of a teacher participant, Rania who states "when the student is allowed to practise the language, this gives them the motivation to speak and the desire to learn". Additionally, student participants have expressed their desire to learn English for a plethora of reasons. Adel, a student participant says, "The motive is the passion for learning the English language in addition to academic aspects as I am an engineer. Also, travelling a lot. But the main motive is the love for languages and the love for learning."

This is consistent with the findings of Asker (2012) who showed that Libyan EFL learners fall into one of two categories: one which sees English as an opportunity to improve future prospects, for example career-wise, and another which sees English as an obstacle to educational success (Khalid, 2017). The majority of the sample of this study falls into the former. It also supports the proposal by Hirschi (2017), who argue that individuals make decisions which align with their personally-perceived benefit or outcome. The type of motivation these students have is instrumental motivation (Gardner and Lambert, 1959), which has been found to have a great impact on foreign language learning (Castillo, 1972).

The second theme that underpins a number of subthemes discussed by teacher participants is obstacles to improvement. Teacher participants during the interviews underlined several obstacles that hinder students from practising authentic spoken English in classrooms in private language centres. The first subtheme relevant to the obstacles to improvement was that students' foundation in oral skills was critically weak. Half of the teacher participants mentioned that students who come to study English in private centres lack the basic English speaking skills (Diaab, 2016), such as correct pronunciation of common words or basic sentence structure, which makes them extremely reluctant to speak in classrooms. Adam states, "...their foundations in English are so weak... some students who have issues with pronunciation, they would be very good at writing but orally weak." This reluctance inhibits teachers from ideally implementing communicative approaches in which teaching/learning is typically learner-centred rather than teacher-centred. Again, this lack of engagement in conversations is likely to negatively influence learners' self-efficacy, particularly when teachers' disbelief in students' inability escalates, students will hardly be given extra chances to get involved in classroom tasks and progress ceases (Orafi and Borg, 2009).

In a related vein, a few teacher participants highlighted that students' shyness prevents them from getting engaged in oral activities in classrooms

(Khalid, 2017) despite having the ability and skills to participate. Salem argues, “The problem I face most frequently is shyness. Sometimes the student refuses to answer orally and suggests writing it on a piece of paper and then his face gets red.” Ali also explains, “sometimes the student knows the answer but s/he is shy and is afraid that classmates would laugh at him and thus gets ridiculed... so encouraging the student to speak boosts his/her self-confidence.” Some students tend to avoid classroom discussion and participation for several reasons. It could be that they are quiet in nature and do not have enough courage or presentation skills (Yang and Chen, 2007), as in the example provided by Salem above, or they are afraid of embarrassment if they give wrong information (Hamouda, 2013) which is compatible with Ali’s statement above (see 4.5.2). Alternatively, learners might be under the effect of the *Affective Filter* (Krashen, 1981). Krashen (1982) proposes that learners might be negatively influenced by an emotional state that impedes their language learning process. Hind, a student participant, states, “sometimes I get confused and anxious when I know the word but I couldn’t say it... perhaps with more practice, I can overcome this problem.”. Reda, another student participant echoes the same issue. He states, “I tend to forget vocabulary when I need it, even though I know the words.” Krashen adds that the higher the affective filter for these learners, the more the language learning process is delayed. Affective Filter Hypothesis resides on the concept that aspects of *affect* such as motivation and personality have an impact on second/foreign language acquisition (Krashen, 1981). For example, according to the Affective Filter Hypothesis, the affective variable ‘anxiety’ has a negative correlation with second/ foreign language acquisition: the lower the anxiety, the better the acquisition and vice versa (*ibid.*). Additionally, the affective variable ‘motivation’ has a positive correlation with second/ foreign language acquisition; higher motivation leads to more second/ foreign language acquisition (*ibid.*). The Affective Filter Hypothesis distinguishes multiple types of motivation, each of which has different degrees of impact depending on the situation (*ibid.*). One

type of motivation is *instrumental* (Gardner and Lambert, 1959): a practical necessity is connected to second/ foreign language learning (Krashen, 1981). This type of motivation stems from the need to acquire a language for a practical reason such as career advancement (Gardner and Lambert, 1972). However, another type is *integrative* motivation: in cases where second/ foreign language acquisition is considered non-essential, this type of motivation leads to successful language acquisition (Krashen, 1981). Integrative motivation stems from a feeling of identifying and wanting to be associated with another entity (Gardner and Lambert, 1972). A third type of affect variable the hypothesis integrates is ‘self-confidence’, which correlates positively with second/ foreign language acquisition (Krashen, 1981). Krashen (*ibid.*) argues that affective variables operate on a subconscious level and their impact is most evident in communicative tests. Krashen (*ibid.*) postulates that,

According to the Affective Filter Hypothesis, acquirers in a less than optimal affective state will have a filter, or mental block, preventing them from utilizing input fully for further language acquisition. If they are anxious, “on the defensive,” or not motivated, they may understand the input, but the input will not enter the “language acquisition device.”

He demonstrates the function of the affective filter in figure 4.1.

When the filter is “up,” input may be understood but will not reach the language acquisition device; it will not strike “deeply” (Stevick, 1976).

Figure 4.1: The Affective Filter by Krashen (1981).

Moreover, some teacher participants mentioned that time constraints bar them from getting all students involved in oral practice. These teacher participants

indicated that time is a crucial factor and if teachers are not given sufficient time to vary their classroom activities, high quality teaching-learning process is likely to be inhibited.

The creativity of Alaa, a teacher participant who had taught younger language learners, does not seem to be phased by any external impositions in the context of a private language centre. He explains,

I like to get off-track and not stick to the lesson in a very light mood in a way to make my students like English language... We used to carry out crossword puzzles and I would draw a face on the whiteboard and point to the eyes and say 'where are the eyes? Where's the mouth? And the pupils are very happy... they would leave their desk all the way to the whiteboard and point to the face and the eyes. Sometimes we have a lesson outside and we play hide and seek... this is a way to make them like English language... so for example during the lesson or during the game they would count from 1 to 10... this way, they will be able to memorise the numbers.

Further evidence on the pressure which educators in general receive, was reported by some teacher participants who are subject to management and parents' complaints. On one hand, the centre's management urges teachers to finish the courses within a certain period of time in order to account for students, who pay money and to encourage them to enrol in other courses. Natale and Doran (2012) indicate that making money has become the major endeavour of private educational businesses on the account of the quality of education they offer. This shows that certain aspects of performativity culture extend beyond the bounds of education policy from the public sector. Only in this case, the gains are financial and for marketing profit. Teachers in the private sector are pressured into meeting their 'customers' and employer's criteria for success, even when they conflict with their professionalism and beliefs in quality teaching. As teacher participants explained, this time pressure shortens the time the teachers allocate for oral activities in particular which reduces the opportunity that students have to practice oral skills. On the other hand, parents, who pay the fees for their children, have high expectations about their children's progress.

The parents' hopes and expectations are likely to render the students under huge pressure which might affect their performance negatively. The pressure extends to the teachers who are expected by parents to boost their children's English oral skills within a short period of time. Rania, a teacher participant states,

First of all, when a student is signed up for course and has no prior knowledge of English, his/her parents demand that in 45 days their son/daughter should learn to speak English. And this is of course, impossible, but parents are informed that more than one course are required. Some parents nonetheless, point out that that is costly... parents always shift their focus on teachers and disregard the overall weakness in learning.

Crossouard (2012) argues that this type of pressure placed on students may affect the mentality of a whole generation. Instead of creating a group of independent thinkers who can construct knowledge and build on it, this system yields only docile subjects who lack creativity. Foucault (1977) in his analysis of power also referred to this as *nation state* in which students are regarded as productive machines and pressurising them makes them more productive. Such process inhibits agency and reflectiveness. According to Bandura (2006), a lack in confidence is a lack of agency. Bandura (*ibid.*, p. 169) demonstrates that personal agency is not available at birth and that it is a property which is acquired gradually after birth by means of social interactions with the ambient surroundings and repeated observation. Self-agency, he proposes, progresses through three consequential stages; a stage of perceiving one event from the ambient social environment, leading to another; a stage in which one action leads to/can change another event within environment; and finally a stage in which a child recognises his/her ability to impact the consequences of an action (*ibid.*). Such development of psychological stages – which extends to learners in the educational field – requires not only the ability to affect change through actions, but also the ability to believe in the ability to affect outcomes through one's actions, leading him/her to essentially consider themselves as agents of their actions. Inside an EFL classroom, it is crucial that a learner identifies his/her

role as an agent in their learning. This will help build the self-confidence necessary to set an action plan in motion in order to the objectives set by the learner.

It was shown throughout the results that there is a shift in the gaze and surveillance (Foucault, 1984). Inside educational institutions, the tradition is that normally the student – the lowest in the power hierarchy – who is *watched* by those higher above in the hierarchy, such as the teacher, not only in regular classes but also in examinations (Foucault, 1977). The teacher on the other hand is normally watched by the school’s headteacher or the inspector, for example. In the case of private centres, it is expected to be the gatekeeper. However, the results above show that in private language centres, we can see a change in the scenery. There is a displacement in the panoptic surveillance, which is twofold: one is the teacher who is being watched by those who were traditionally lower in the power hierarchy, the students as well as the parents, and two is the student – who is pressured by the parent – but then also pressures the teacher. The pressure from parents and students on the teachers thus seems to change the direction of the gaze and complicates the nature of power relations between teachers and learners. This may affect the teachers’ panoptic performativity. It was shown earlier that parents are happy when they see improvement because they pay for the courses, they have high expectations of teachers and their children, who in turn, have high expectations from their teachers. Parents exercise pressure on teachers and their children asking for the impossible, that is that their children learn English proficiently in a short period of time without sufficient background knowledge of what language learning entails, all because they hold the power of paying their children’s tuition fees. Teacher participants complained that they are being expected to perform miracles in a short period of time, not only by parents and students, but also by the language centres’ gatekeepers. The latter are in the business of ‘knowledge production’ (Ball, 2012, p. 18). This is all part of what can be referred to as the neo-liberal reform, which

is,

a complex, often incoherent, unstable and even contradictory set of practices that are organized around a certain imagination of the “market” as a basis for the universalisation of market-based social relations, with the corresponding penetration in almost every single aspect of our lives. (Shamir, 2008, p. 3)

The parents here consider their children what Foucault (1977) describes, ‘as machines’ except in Foucault’s analysis it was the ‘disciplinary institutions’ which did that. Here it is the parents. They expect teachers to ‘optimise’ the students’ performance (*ibid.*) and pass on the product of knowledge from teachers to students (MacLure, 2006). Parents do not consider the individualistic nature of humans, their uniqueness, or their readiness to learn Crossouard (2012). The expectation of teachers to work by the rules of parents undermines the role teachers play in the EFL classroom and puts them under what Foucault (1977) refers to as normalised, standardised judgements by parents.

4.6 Summary of findings

Table 4.1: Summary of findings: Essential Areas for Development

1. Essential Areas for Development	
Teachers	Students
Oral Practice	
Oral/aural practice promotes students' self-confidence	Oral/aural skills are the foundation skills necessary to hold conversations and gain self-confidence in speaking
Oral practice enhances students' motivation	They have better opportunities to practice
Oral practice contributes to effective language learning	Teachers follow more effective teaching techniques
Oral Assessment	
The aim of assessment is to motivate students to learn not to pass exams	Applying formative assessment
Assessment motivates students to work hard	Continuous/formative assessment should be adopted in English language classrooms. Continuous feedback from teachers helps students correct their mistakes, improve their English oral skills
Formative assessment is more effective than summative assessment, it caters for individual differences, it provides continuous feedback necessary, and it helps develop self-confidence	

Table 4.2: Summary of findings: Obstacles to Improvement

2. Obstacles to Improvement	
teachers	students
Oral Practice	
Lack of access to facilities and/or equipment due to power cuts and/or Internet connection	Lack of opportunity to practice authentic English whether inside or outside the classroom.
Students have problems with oral skills which prevent them from progressing: student inertia	Low level of oral proficiency
The effect and power of parents on students' achievement.	Lack of opportunity to practise with native speakers of English
The effect and power of school management on teachers' timeline.	
Anxiety has a negative impact on student performance	
Oral Assessment	
Anxiety surrounding assessment	Anxiety and fear before exams
	Lack of constant feedback and formative assessment

Table 4.3: Summary of findings: Overcoming the Obstacles

3. Overcoming the obstacles	
teachers	students
Oral Practice	
Encourage students to practice oral skills by practising role-play, modelling, and without punishment	
Allowing students more opportunity to practice by allowing extra time for free oral practice, power over topics of practice, and support with required vocabulary	
Being more approachable	
Oral Assessment	
More focus on formative than summative assessment	Preparation for assessment reduces anxiety
Varying assessment techniques and providing instant feedback	Assessment results should not matter too much: they do not affect level of proficiency: Practice and initiative to speak helps improve skills
Applying assessment with the purpose of regulating teaching methods	

Chapter 5: Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

This study set out to explore lecturers' and students' standpoints on English language oral practice and assessment in private language centres. The goal was first to understand the role and effectiveness of oral assessment practice in developing authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya. Second, the aim was to examine and compare lecturers' and students' perspectives towards the strategies used in the development of authentic spoken language assessment in private language centres. Thirdly, the thesis set out to engage in the implication of these findings in relation to English language oral assessment practice in private language schools in Libya.

In the following sections, I will summarise the findings from the previous chapter in relation to the research questions and discuss these findings in the light of *AfL* approach and SCLT theoretical framework. The findings will also be discussed in relation to power from a Foucauldian perspective. I will additionally consider the implications of the findings for the teaching and learning of oral language skills and assessment. As with the majority of studies, the design of the current study was subject to limitations. The limitations of the study which may potentially affect the generalisation of the findings will be acknowledged. An autobiographical reflection is then presented. The chapter concludes by presenting recommendations and areas for further research.

Chapter 2 discussed the theoretical framework of the study. It also examined the notion of assessment in ESOL in relation to the Libyan context using a lens of power. The chapter examined literature on the relation between the learners' and teachers' perspectives towards assessment and its impact on learning with a specific focus on oral and aural assessment practice in the presence of power relations. The chapter identified the gap, that is the perspective towards oral assessment practice in an absence of such power relations in private language centres. This does not by any means imply an absolute absence of other potential power dynamics.

Chapter 3 developed an exhaustive account of the methodology adopted in the study. It focused on how the methodology and methods were meticulously defined to answer the research questions. It presented the research design and methodology and demonstrated its suitability by comparing competing approaches to various paradigms in the Social Sciences. It outlined several concepts of research philosophy and data analysis method in the positivist vs. phenomenological paradigms. The chapter also addressed the general theory of deductive vs. inductive reasoning in relation to quantitative vs. qualitative research methods. The theoretical framework that guides the study was elaborated on by examining Bandura's Social Cognitive Learning Theory and the Assessment *for* Learning approach. The methods used to address the research questions are also introduced. The data analysis technique, vis-a-vis the coding scheme was presented along with a description of the study sample, sampling procedure, the interviewing procedure, the ethical considerations relevant to the current study and finally some potential limitations.

In Chapter 4, the main themes and subthemes emerging from the data were presented. The main themes discussed in relation to oral practice and assessment were *Essential Areas for Development*, *Obstacles to Improvement*, and *Overcoming the Obstacles*. The findings and discussion were combined in one chapter because I felt it would better integrate the results to the previous literature on language learning and assessment as well as power relations and that it would make it more coherent.

It seems that the role and effectiveness of the practice of oral language assessment in developing authentic spoken English in private language centres in Libya can be said to tentatively reflect a rather more successful version of English language teaching in the Libyan context in the light of principles of AfL and SCLT. Some issues however, remain to be developed. The following subsections answer the research questions posed in chapter 3. The summary of teachers' and learners' perspectives is presented by theme, that is *Essential Areas*

for Development in section 5.2, *Obstacles to Improvement* in section 5.3, and finally *Overcoming the Obstacles* in section 5.4.

5.2 Essential Areas for Development

In terms of the essential components for development, teachers generally expressed what they thought was beneficial for the learners with regards to developing their listening and speaking skills. Learners agree that in language centres they have more opportunities to practise authentic language oral skills because teachers allocate more time to oral skills compared to their experience in schools. This is understandable given the sole dedication of language schools to language teaching and learning.

Learners also state that in private centres, they get better teaching methods and more effective teaching techniques. Learners furthermore, generally convey a more positive learning experience in private centres. For example the IPA they state, helps with pronunciation and develops a sense of learner autonomy. Moreover, they believe that private centre courses challenge learners and develops learning process. One interesting statement they communicate is that the pronunciation of teachers in private centres is relatively good. Some language centres – from my personal experience either with friends who teach in private language centres or having had my own private centre – however, focus more on experience but more so on language proficiency in order to hire someone to deliver English language courses. In fact, in my experience as an insider of the Libyan community, a language centre's reputation is built on the successful communication proficiency of its teaching staff.

The lecturers' and learners' perspective on the importance of oral practice were generally aligned most of the time. Both groups agreed that oral practice promotes self-efficacy, reduces anxiety, motivates them to learn, develops their fluency, vocabulary repertoire and ultimately leads to effective language learning and more successful communication. Students believe that teachers in language centres motivate them by telling them they have improved. Motivation is an

essential attribute of agency (Bandura, 2006).

However, neither students nor lecturers complained about being straight-jacketed into a preset curriculum for example. Neither group of participants complained about power dynamics in the classroom either by teachers or other learners or from external power hierarchies such as the language centre gatekeeper. In fact, learners felt very comfortable expressing their needs to the language school head to make sure they are met. Some teachers argued for leniency with mistakes expressing the need to focus on use rather than form. This is in line with the principles of the Communicative Teaching Approach (Brumfit and Johnson, 1979; Harmer, 2001) although learners were eager to have that kind of feedback. What was also striking is the mention from the teachers' part of the importance of formative assessment in informing the effectiveness of the teaching practice. They assert that not only does it serve students but also teachers. Teachers believed that formative assessment (via oral practice) allowed them to reflect on the effectiveness of their teaching methods and practice. Thus, this serves as a self-regulation technique not only for learners but also for teachers (Bandura, 1994). Some teachers were well aware of the aspect of the lack of attainment upon graduating university level.

However, not all teachers viewed the benefits of formative assessment in the same way as the literature on formative assessment proposes (for example Crooks, 1988; Kluger and DeNisi, 1996; Natriello, 1987; Nyquist, 2003). The main advantage deduced from the teachers' perspectives was that formative assessment or more precisely assessment throughout the course in comparison to summative assessment caters for individual differences and is thus fair unlike summative assessment. The student participants also favoured formative assessment but for slightly different reasons. They say that feedback from teachers allows them to reflect on their language and correct their mistakes and hence lead to improved oral skills. Individual cases of students also differed from their teachers in that they call for the implementation for peer assessment,

raising awareness of assessment criteria to reduce assessment anxiety, and finally considering that achieving high scores essentially leads to better self-confidence and encourages them to work even harder.

One teacher also emphasised the importance of listening practice preceding speaking practice. This lends support to Bandura's SCLT (Bandura, 1977) in terms of the importance of modelling behaviours and motor reproduction. It also reflects proposals by Krashen (for example 1982) of the importance of input and that premature pressure to perform can inhibit language learning.

5.3 Obstacles to Improvement

The second theme discussed was obstacles which impede improvement of oral practice and assessment. In private language centres, they believe that there is however a lack of accessibility to teaching aids, which can be partly due to power cuts or black outs as a result of the instability of the infrastructure and the political tension in the country. They also state that in private language centres, they deal with a smaller classroom size and thus have more time to practice various language skills. One of the obstacles relating to learners is believed to be learners' inertia. This is referable to the long-standing tradition of relying heavily on memorisation (Alloreibi and Carey, 2017; Asker, 2012; Orafi and Borg, 2009). Teachers argue that they put special effort to overcome this aspect. Relevant to the context of language centres during interviews was the pressure from parents and students on teachers. According to the teacher participants, students and parents hold high expectations from courses. Specifically students believe that it takes only one course for them to speak English fluently and competently. Teacher participants believed that parents who most likely pay for the course fees expect that the teachers will enable their children to speak fluently, exerted extra pressure not only on the teacher but also on their children, who are enrolled for these courses. Teachers believed that parents forcing their children into taking up English courses can inhibit their children's motivation to learn. This may well be the result of a lack

of communication between parents and educators (Shim, 2013). However, in terms of the power hierarchies between the teachers and students, it was demonstrated by the majority of the teacher participants that they did not want their students to feel that type of power relation and that instead they work hard to make sure their students have a comfortable experience and felt that their teachers were approachable.

Another barrier emerging from the analysis is that of anxiety. The fear of making mistakes as teachers and students call it, or anxiety around new technology which was not previously made available in public schools. The third barrier is the fear of punishment. Whilst some participants acknowledge the severe impact of intolerance for language mistakes, others view mistakes as a vehicle or a precursor to learning.

From the students' perspective the most significant barrier was not having enough time for authentic practice be it inside or outside of the classroom. The poor level of oral performance was echoed by the students. However, it can be argued that this is to be expected from learners since their goal from attending language courses is to improve their oral proficiency. Students further expressed their concerns relating to the lack of opportunities to practise authentic language use with native speakers of the language.

As for barriers to oral assessment, the teachers almost unanimously and some students believe that assessment-related anxiety is the major obstacle in oral assessment. Additionally, shyness seems to be another impediment for some types of learner participants. Another obstacle relating to oral assessment expressed in the learners' view is that there is a scarcity in oral assessment practice for formative purposes and that when oral assessment does take place, they do not receive sufficient or instant feedback. In fact, some students state they do not receive any feedback at all. Feedback was perceived by these learners as critical to their language development in general and oral skills in particular which lends support to the Assessment for Learning approach (Black and Wiliam,

1998). As far as obstacles relating to oral assessment, there does not seem to be power-related barriers in private language centres in the views of teachers or students. However, the layers of power found between parents and teachers does create pressure on teachers and students. The pressure to perform under a short period of time changes traditional power dynamics and may create a desirable panoptic performativity among teachers and consequently demotivate students by decreasing their self-confidence and their affiliative drive (Ausubel, Novak, and Hanesian, 1978 cited in Dörnyei, 1994, p. 278).

5.4 Overcoming the Obstacles

Teachers follow that it is important to encourage students to practice oral skills in the classroom. One of the techniques they say they used to fulfil this step is through role-play and engaging their students in conversations. Teachers mostly present students with model conversations along with relevant vocabulary to equip learners with the necessary ingredients to carry out such task in line with Bandura's (1977) observational learning perspectives on how humans learn. Additionally, teachers argue that they are tolerant of mistakes and embrace them as an inherent stage in the learning process. Teachers also maintain that they utilise a versatile range of activities to cater for individual differences and diverse learning preferences. Teachers also contend that it is necessary to allow students as much opportunity as possible for oral practice. Some teachers explained that even when teaching aids are not made available, that does not stop them from using their personal equipment for listening practice. Some teachers stated that they did not time oral practice and students were free to use as much time as they felt was needed. However, there remained the motivating students to practice using the power of scores, which is contrary to the AfL approach by Black and Wiliam (1998, et seq.). Teachers also believed that providing a safe and comfortable environment for the learners is essential in motivating learners to participate in oral practice. Other less frequently mentioned techniques include a) motivating

students by discussing future careers, which mostly involve an adequate command of oral and aural skills, b) pressuring students to speak by giving time limits that reflect real life communication.

In terms of overcoming obstacles relating to oral assessment, teachers asserted the importance of varying assessment techniques and providing instant feedback. Moreover, teachers expressed the importance of utilising assessment techniques in closely monitoring students' performance, reflecting on their own teaching and modifying their teaching methods accordingly. This is a self-regulation technique proposed by the Social Cognitive Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977), which not only benefits students but also teachers. Keeping learners informed of the assessment criteria has also been on the agenda of many teachers, who argue that it helps students regulate their anxiety and boost their self-efficacy.

Students on the other hand, echoed the teachers' perspectives on the importance of being informed about the assessment criteria and its role in reducing their anxiety. However, another group of students contended the irrelevance of assessment results to their level of proficiency, which supports the views of Biesta (2009). These learners assert that in their view, oral practice and the opportunity to speak English is what indeed culminates in learning and that is what they value more than scores or results.

The second research question addresses similarities and differences between lecturers' and students' perspectives towards the strategies used in the development of authentic spoken language assessment in private language centres in Libya. Teachers seem to have expressed a wider variety of techniques regarding overcoming the barriers than learners. Despite the teachers' tolerance for mistakes and assertion of the importance of *through-out-the-course* assessment, they mainly, though not exclusively, see its benefits in terms of fairness rather than its informative purposes. Moreover, for those teachers who view formative assessment as crucial to inform students and their own teaching methods, unlike students, they do not put much weight on the importance of

feedback. Learners seem more eager to receive feedback as they express its crucial benefits to helping them develop their language. They also emphasised the crucial role of self-confidence, observational learning through modelled behaviours and enacting oral practice which supports the concept of motor reproduction in Social Cognitive Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977).

5.5 Implications

The third research question addresses the implication of the findings for teaching and learning oral language skills. The study has drawn attention to the significant role oral assessment practice plays in developing authentic speaking skills in private language centres in Libya. These findings have a number of important implications for future practice. The first recommendation is to recognise the impact of private language centres on developing learners' oral skills. The research study shows that the motivation for learning and teaching English language in private language schools was different from those found in study populations in government-led schools and universities. The strategies and dynamics taken by private language centres in Libya have been effective in helping Libyan foreign language learners to develop authentic spoken English. There is arguably more time dedicated to authentic language practice albeit the complaint that students wanted to practise English with native speakers. Teachers promoted autonomous learning and students value this, they were approachable, which motivates students to ask questions, be more interactive, and essentially more involved in and in control of their own learning. Teachers motivated their learners by telling them they have improved and by helping them visualise their goals beyond the classroom. Teachers have reduced the learners' anxiety by using formative assessment, which helped them in return to reflect on their teaching practices. Students welcomed peer assessment. Teachers understood the importance of modelling behaviours, such as using listening practice, introducing related vocabulary to the topic, for example, and in the

importance motor production, that is oral practice to consolidate learning. This not only helped students but teachers as well in maintaining their proficiency using practice with their students. With better communicative skills, the students stand a better chance at fulfilling their goals. However, this deprives the less fortunate, those who cannot afford to study English in private language centres, to have an equal opportunity to quality foreign language teaching. The Ministry of Education in Libya should consider recruiting trained teachers or provide periodical teacher training programmes tailored for the Libyan context. Such training programmes should also focus on training teachers to use new classroom technologies and make them more comfortable and less anxious around it. It should also consider the benefits of integrating oral practice assessment in schools and universities and providing the appropriate teaching aids and facilities to allow learners to practise and develop authentic aural skills. This study has helped to raise awareness to the myriad of issues surrounding English language teaching and learning in the Libyan context. As part of the Expanding Circle, opportunities to speak English outside the classroom are slim. The chances of interacting with native speakers are minimal. English is spoken as a *Lingua Franca* and by a minority of people. It is unfair that English Language International tests do not consider varieties of English spoken outside the Inner Circle. The implications for the foreign language teaching discipline is that what may be regarded as a motivator for one learner (feedback, and error correction for example as it serve as a progress marker and helps students set new goals), may be a source of anxiety for another. Teachers should be more tolerant of mistakes as they are an inherent part of the learning process and focus mainly on fluency rather than accuracy. The layers of power evident in the private sector of the Libyan context demonstrate a significant shift from the traditional views. We saw that there is pressure from parents on their children and teachers to do well in a very short period of time. This shift creates complications for learners and for teachers especially when parents pay tuition fees. The implications for this is

that parents' awareness of foreign language teaching and learning needs to be raised rather than teachers having to resort to performative roles to please both parents and students. This can be done by creating a channel of communication between teachers, language schools, and parents about what and when to expect, and about how individuals vary in their learning journey.

5.6 Limitations of the study

The findings of this study have to be seen in light of some limitations. First, the interview questions were intended to be asked and answered in English. However, the respondents were not pressured to answer in English and as a result they chose to answer in Arabic. It could be the case that they either felt more comfortable answering in their mother tongue or given that the participants and the interviewer share the same L1 background, it felt natural to converse in that language. Whilst answering in the interviewee's L1 has its advantages, it is considered a limitation. A limitation to this is that data require translation and that translation entails its own problems. Temple and Young (2004, p. 164) argue that,

methodological and epistemological challenges arise from the recognition that people using different languages may construct different ways of seeing social life. The relationships between languages and researchers, translators and the people they seek to represent are as crucial as issues of which word is best in a sentence in a language. Many writers with an interest in the power of the written word and the process by which it is produced, have argued that there is no single correct translation of a text.

The cultural bearings of a text are what a translation ought to reflect (Simon, 1996).

The solutions to many of the translator's dilemmas are not to be found in dictionaries, but rather in an understanding of the way language is tied to local realities, to literary forms and to changing identities. Translators must constantly make decisions about the

cultural meanings which language carries, and evaluate the degree to which the two different worlds they inhabit are ‘the same’. These are not technical difficulties, they are not the domain of specialists in obscure or quaint vocabularies. ... In fact the process of meaning transfer has less to do with *finding* the cultural inscription of a term than in reconstructing its value. (*ibid.*, 137–8, emphasis original)

For the current study, the researcher and the participants share the same language and cultural background. However, according to Liu (2002), there remains issues other than those relating to cultural differences. These are issues of psychological equivalence, where there could be a potential mismatch in psychological connotations between the referents of the translated and original text. Banville, Desrosiers, and Genet-Volet (2000) explains that having translations of the original text into the target language by other translators eliminates bias and thus warrants considerable validity and reliability of the translated text. They suggest that translators compare their translations and resolve disagreements in meaning and language should they appear. One of the advantages of allowing participants to answer in their L1 is reducing the impact of low proficiency on the amount and quality of the produced data (Mackey and Guss, 2005). In order to overcome the limitation of translated interviews, the translations of the interviews were scrutinised by a bilingual linguist who is also a native Libyan and speaks English as a second language. The participants, the interviewer and the translator all share the same language and cultural background.

This leads to the second limitation, that is *positionality* of the researcher, which could have potentially resulted in bias in interpreting the findings. Positionality is an ethical matter affecting the researcher and participants, who are situated in different levels of a power hierarchy. According to Hammersley and Traianou (2012) the researcher holds a higher power status compared to the participants. Bettez (2015) argues that the researcher’s beliefs, socio-cultural background, gender, race, religious values and his/her status as an outsider or insider affect his/her perception of him/herself and that of others, which in turn

may impact his/her knowledge of the research and how it is conducted, assessed and used. *Insider research* is research that involves a researcher and participants coming from the same population, community and/or identity groups and sharing identity, language, and/or professional experience (Kanuha, 2000). Achieving neutrality in such cases is almost impossible and thus it is best to have greater awareness of possible bias (Rose, 1985; Chavez, 2008). As a researcher who shares a Libyan, Arabic identity, first language, and professional experience of teaching English as a foreign language in Libya, I am considered an insider to the study population. Following recommendations by Rose (1985) and Chavez (2008) I am aware of my positionality as an insider researcher, and despite the inevitable bias and lack of absolute neutrality (Rose, 1985), I make a special effort to be as aware of my positionality and its inherent biases as possible (*ibid.*), critically reflexive, that is by being accountable, ethical and open about the various stages of my research study (Hellowell, 2006). To be specific and following the recommendations of Asselin (2003), data collection was carried out with open eyes and assuming minimum knowledge of the investigated phenomenon. Moreover, following recommendations by Tilley, Chambers, and Mackenzie (1996), having a continuous self-reflection process and reliability checks by the another researcher, vis-a-vis the translator to review the data helps to minimise bias and increase integrity.

A third limitation is the sampling procedure. The sampling was intended to be carried out in a way that participants were to be selected randomly. The plan was to ask each centre's gatekeeper for permission to conduct research in that centre and for lists of the potential participants. I had planned to write each participant's name on a separate slip of paper. Then I would select names at random. Afterwards the selected participants would be notified and their permission to conduct the interviews would be sought (I would send them a participant information sheet and a consent form). Then, I would contact each selected interviewee, who accepted my offer to interview him/her, and we would

conduct the interview, which would be held in each relevant centre. However, the gatekeepers of the private centres upon contact decided that *they* would contact teachers and students enrolled in their centres and ask them whether they would be interested in participating. This has created sample bias that was inevitable. If I had declined, I would have had no access to any of the participants and eventually would not have any data. Additionally, the participants showed a wide range of perspectives and the data did not seem to be skewed.

5.7 Impact and recommendations

The literature review highlighted a paucity of qualitative studies carried out to address lecturers' and students' perspectives towards the strategies used in oral assessment practice in Libya, despite its significant role in understanding issues relating to poor performance in real life communicative skills amongst Libyans. Evidence on this issue from the public sector, despite scarce, suggests that students lack the motivation to learn English owing to the political and historical events the country witnessed. Such events are believed to have caused Libyans to have a negative attitude towards English in particular and foreign languages in general. Evidence also shows that in the public sector, teachers do not teach oral skills for various reasons such as mismatch between curriculum intentions and examination expectations governed by the Ministry of Education, tight time lines, classroom size, teachers generally lacking English language proficiency, and most importantly interference from higher authorities.

We have demonstrated that in private language centres this was not the case. Teachers and learners alike expressed their interest to learn English for a plethora of reasons. Furthermore, they exhibited generally positive attitudes towards learning it.

5.8 Autobiographical reflection

Carrying out this research study has been a rich learning experience for me. I now understand the cyclical nature of qualitative research design, data collection and data analysis. My findings did not always fit efficiently into categories but I have learned how to persevere in the face of such adversaries. This study has given me insight into the English Language Teaching practice in Libya beyond the classroom and has assisted me with reflecting on my own professional values and to provide vital ideas and guidance to those who wish to effect change in the future of English Language Teaching in Libya and other similar contexts. Now that I have a thriving curiosity and awareness of the barriers facing EFL classrooms, I plan to probe further the areas of writing and reading assessment practice and whether the issues surrounding it are viewed in a parallel fashion to those of oral and aural assessment practice. The findings of this research made me question how I and my teaching methods were perceived by my students as an EFL teacher and reminded me of how I viewed EFL classrooms when I was a student. Before commencing this research, I had never consciously thought about the impact of external or internal powers on the education process. However deep down, I did believe that there was something missing from assessment and how it was carried out. I questioned its purpose from a *System's* (the educational system) perspective.

The research journey has inspired me to view education from a wider educational scope and has enabled me to critically examine issues pertaining to classroom practices, assessment and how it relates to teaching and learning. Despite the dissatisfaction of the teacher and learner participants in the present study with the government-led educational system, and how restraining it can be, some of my participants believed that private language centres are valuable platforms which provide sound teaching and learning environments. For them, private language centres have most of the essential ingredients to acquiring successful real life communicative skills in English. I learned from some of my

participants that private language centres' strongest attributes are that there is a high motivation to learn and teach English in them and that teachers and learners alike believed that they were somewhat free to be as creative and as individualistic as they wish. This is reassuring and makes me feel optimistic albeit there is room for refining and improving to achieve excellence.

5.9 Future research areas

Further research is recommended to determine the extent language learning in language centres – in the absence of a number of prominent power relations discussed earlier in this study – correlates with actual improvements in language proficiency compared to that in the public sector. Although, there is prevailing sense from the teachers and the students perspectives that private language centres have the capability of providing authentic oral language assessment practice and thus improving the learners' oral proficiency, further study is required to determine whether the students have actually developed the oral skills which enable them to communicate successfully in real life situations. The fact that the majority of participants replied in their native language is telling in itself. However, this does not entirely rule out the possible oral proficiency of the teacher and learner participants. In situations where the interlocutors share the same L1 background, it would be a more convenient language to communicate.

Further research should also build on the current qualitative research and investigate the actual classroom assessment practices relating to the development of oral skills in private language centres and the day-to-day interactions within their classrooms.

Finally, it would also be beneficial to investigate parent perspectives and their role in assisting or hindering their children's language learning process and to compare self-funding learners with those financially supported by external sources including their parents. We have seen the influence of parent pressure from the participants point of view but we do not know much about how parents view their

role in assisting their children in the learning process.

Appendix A: Interview questions for students and teachers

**Study Title: Lecturers' and students' perspectives towards strategies
used in oral practice and assessment in Libyan language schools**

A Research Project by: Mohamed Remali

Interview questions for students and teachers

Part one:

Questions that build rapport and break the ice:

1. How long have you been learning/teaching English?
2. What drives you to learn/teach it?
3. Do you enjoy it?

Part two:

Main questions:

1. Tell me something about oral assessment.
2. What is your opinion on oral assessment?
3. How do you practice/teach oral skills in the classroom?
4. How are you assessed/do you assess throughout and/or at the end of a language course?
5. Do you think oral practice is important?
6. Do you think oral assessment is important?
7. Does oral assessment add to your/the students' learning experience?

8. Do you think oral assessment should change?
9. What do you think oral assessment should be like?
10. What issues do you face when practising/teaching oral skills?
11. What issues do you face in oral assessment?

Part three:

Any consequent question that emerges from the above discussion.

Appendix B: Information sheet

University of West of Scotland
School of Education
Paisley Campus
Paisley
PA1 2BE
Scotland

**Study Title: Lecturers' and students' perspectives towards strategies
used in oral practice and assessment**

A Research Project by: Mohamed Remali

You are invited to take part in a research study. This letter has important information about the reason for doing this study, what I will ask you to do, and the way I would like to use the information about you if you choose to be in the study. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish.

What is the purpose of the study?

The aim of the study is to explore the perspectives of teachers and learners on the strategies used and should be used in oral practice and assessment. The findings of this study will be an important piece of new knowledge about the current state of oral practice and assessment in Libyan language centres. The study is being undertaken by the researcher in completion of his PhD. It will be written up as a PhD thesis and the findings will be submitted for publication in journals and/or conferences.

What will I be asked to do in this study?

Should you decide to take part in this research study, and all your questions have been answered to your satisfaction, you will be asked to sign a consent form and take part in an interview with the researcher. The interview will last approximately 30 minutes. During the interview, you will be asked questions relating to oral practice and assessment. Your interview will be audio-recorded. The interview will take place in the language centre.

How will you protect the information you collect about me?

I will ensure that your name and recordings are confidential. You will be identified in the research records by a code, for instance, as (S1 or L2). All data will be kept confidentially in a password-protected personal external drive. Only the researcher can access the data.

What are my rights as a research participant?

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You are free to choose not to participate. Should you choose to participate, you can withdraw at any time without consequences of any kind.

Who is conducting the research?

The researcher is Mohamed Remali. He is from Libya.

Who can I contact if I have questions or concerns about this study?

If you have questions or concerns during the time of your participation in this study, please contact:

Mohamed Remali (researcher)
Email: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Professor Jeannie Daniels (supervisor) Dr Margaret Allan (supervisor)
Email: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]
[REDACTED] [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking the time to read this letter. We hope you will take part in this important and exciting study.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix C: Consent form

University of West of Scotland
School of Education
Paisley Campus
Paisley
PA1 2BE
Scotland

**Study Title: Lecturers' and students' perspectives towards strategies
used in oral practice and assessment**

A Research Project by: Mohamed Remali

Please, indicate that you have read and agree with the statement by providing your name and signing below:

I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and have asked any questions I wanted to.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason.

I understand that all information collected

1. will be labelled with a code and not my name to maintain anonymity.
2. will be stored in a secure place.

Participant:....., Signature:....., Date:..... .

Researcher: Mohamed Remali, Signature:..... .

Please give the form to Mohamed Remali. You will be given a copy of this consent form to keep.

Appendix D: The Panopticon and the Libyan Scholarship Mandate

Foucault's Panopticon

Figure D.1: The architecture of the PANOPTICON by Foucault ([1977](#))

Figure D.2: First/three-page Ministry of Education scholarship mandate (Ministry of Education, [2018](#))

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Appendix E: Participants' Background

Table E.1: Teacher participants' demographics

Teacher	Age	Gender	Experience	Motivation for teaching
Adam	45	Male	since 1992	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To earn a living - A sense of fulfilment - International language - Means of communicating with the outside world - language of the Internet
Omar	28	Male	since 2011	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It's a new language - I love teaching and English: This combines the two - I can improve my language with practice and I can gain experience, which helps my career advancement
Salem	34	Male	since 2004	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To maintain my own language through continued practice
Sara	31	Female	8 – 9 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial reasons: to improve a living - A personal challenge - It's fun
Alia	30	Female	8 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It's a foreign language and culture - I enjoy teaching it to students
Rania	25	Female	3 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ability to do what my English teachers couldn't
Farage	24	Male	~ 1.5 year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I love teaching it - It requires skills, which I have - It is a second language
Ali	24	Male	~ 2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Career advancement - To gain teaching experience - It stimulates my language

Alaa	24	Male	~ 2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is a passion to teach and learn - It is very close to Arabic in being courteous - I love it since I was a child - It was my dream to learn it and speak it - The ability to communicate with the world - Because English is a global language - It's the most spoken language after Mandarin
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Table E.2: Student participants' demographics

Student	Age	Gender	Learning	motivation for learning
Abdallah	23	Male	3 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Passion for English and learning - For academic reasons; I am an engineer - I travel a lot
Haifa	21	Female	1 year [private] 5th grade [public]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am a dentistry major - I should be competent and fluent abroad - I will likely do higher studies - I haven't learned a lot from school or university - Peer competition
Samah	24	Female	6 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is number one language in the world - It also adds to my education and my culture
Sammy	21	Male	<1 year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It's an international language - It's useful for reading labels/ instruction manuals on products - The Internet is mainly English; most of the web information is in English
Reda	25	Male	>8 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I love it - There has been an increase in English-speaking TV channels: when I watch with no subtitles, I don't understand anything - To be able to communicate with the rest of the world.

Inaas	22	Female	8 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I have joined the postgraduate academy - Out of love for English - I've always wished I could speak English - It is an international language - Everything is in English nowadays
Muna	19	Female	3 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job hunting after graduation - Employment requirements and a competitive market
Ibrahim	27	Male	1.5 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I used to be in Britain as a kid and I returned to Libya. But unfortunately, I forgot it
Fady	24	Male	1 year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I enjoy it - My father always gives me the opportunity to take up English courses
Adel	22	Male	<1 year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It allows me to connect with the world - It opens door of possibilities for me career-wise
Ismail	21	Male	2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It's fun: I meet new people online and get to know them - The language carries new meanings - I feel like a new person! - I learn new skills - I can communicate with the world - I can understand everything - I can reach everything

References

- Abdulali, A.J. (1987) Changing the Role of Inspector in the Libyan Educational System (Supervision, Training). Doctoral thesis. University of Pittsburgh.
- Abu Srewel, F. (2002) The Use of the Learner's Mother Tongue in Teaching English as a Foreign Language in Some Libyan Secondary Schools in Tripoli. Masters thesis. The Academy of Graduate Studies.
- Abuklaish, A. (2014) Investigating the Language Needs of Undergraduate Science Students in Libya. Doctoral thesis. University of Southampton.
- Ahmad, M.A. (2001) A Critical Evaluation of the Error Correction Techniques Used by Libyan Teachers of English at the Secondary Schools. Masters thesis. The Academy of Graduate Studies.
- Ahmed, K.M. (2015) Perceptions of Libyan English language teachers towards teaching the target culture. *Arab World English Journal* Vol.6(2), pp. 154–161. DOI: [10.2139/ssrn.2834385](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2834385).
- Akbari, Omid and Razavi, Azam (2016) Using authentic materials in the foreign language classrooms: Teachers' perspectives in EFL classes. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education* Vol.5(2), pp. 105–116.
- Al Kaboody, M. (2013) Second language motivation; the role of teachers in learners' motivation. *Journal of Academic and Applied Studies* Vol.3(4), pp. 45–54.
- Alhmali, R. (2007) Student Attitudes in the Context of the Curriculum in Libyan Education in Middle and High Schools. Doctoral thesis. University of Glasgow.
- Alhojailan, M.I. (2012) Thematic analysis: a critical review of its process and evaluation. *West East Journal of Social Sciences* Vol.1(1), pp. 39–47.

- Aloreibi, A. and Carey, M.D. (2017) English language teaching in Libya after Gaddafi. In: R. Kirkpatrick ([ed.]), *English Language Education Policy in the Middle East and North Africa*. Kuwait: Springer, pp. 93–114.
- Arabai, F. (2014) A model of foreign language anxiety in the Saudi EFL context. *English Language Teaching* Vol.7(7), pp. 82–101.
- Arai, K. (2004) What 'demotivates' language learners? Qualitative study on demotivational factors and learners' reactions. *Bulletin of Toyo Gakuen University* Vol.12(3), pp. 39–47.
- Arthur, W.B. (1994) Inductive reasoning and bounded rationality. *The American Economic Review* Vol.84(2), pp. 406–411.
- Asker, A. (2012) Future Self-Guides and Language Learning Engagement of English-Major Secondary School Students in Libya: Understanding the Interplay Between Possible Selves and the L2 Learning Situation. Doctoral thesis. University of Birmingham.
- Asselin, M.E. (2003) Insider research: issues to consider when doing qualitative research in your own setting. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development* Vol.19(2), pp. 99–103.
- Ausubel, D.P., Novak, J.D., and Hanesian, H. (1978) *Educational psychology: A cognitive view*. 2nd ed. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Azher, M., Anwar, M.N., and Naz, A. (2010) An investigation of foreign language classroom anxiety and its relationship with students achievement. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning (TLC)* Vol.7(11), pp. 33–40.
- Bacon, S. and Finneman, M. (1990) A study of attitudes, motives, and strategies of university foreign language students and their disposition to authentic oral and written input. *Modern Language Journal* Vol.74(4), pp. 459–73. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1990.tb05338.x>.
- Baecher, L., Artigliere, M., Patterson, D.K., and Spatzer, A. (2012) Differentiated instruction for English language learners as “variations on a

- theme” teachers can differentiate instruction to support English language learners. *Middle School Journal* Vol.43(3), pp. 14–21.
- Bagigni, A. (2016) The Role of English in Libya and its Implications for Syllabus Design in Libyan Higher Education. Doctoral thesis. University of Huddersfield.
- Ball, S.J. (2001) Performativities and fabrications in the education economy: Towards the performative society. In: *The Performing School: Managing, Teaching and Learning in a Performance Culture*. D. Gleeson and C. Husbands ([eds.]). London: Routledge Falmer, pp. 210–226.
- (2012) Performativity, commodification and commitment: An i-spy guide to the neoliberal university. *British Journal of Educational Studies* Vol.60(1), pp. 17–28. DOI: [10.1080/00071005.2011.650940](https://doi.org/10.1080/00071005.2011.650940).
- Ball, S.J., Maguire, M., Braun, A., and Hoskins, K. (2011) Policy subjects and policy actors in schools: Some necessary but insufficient analyses. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education* Vol.32(4), pp. 611–624. DOI: [10.1080/01596306.2011.601564](https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2011.601564).
- Bandura, A. (1977) Self-efficacy: toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review* Vol.84(2), pp. 191–215.
- (1986) *Social Foundations of Thought and Action: a Social Cognitive Theory*. Prentice-Hall Series in Social Learning Theory. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall.
- (1989) Human agency in social cognitive theory. *American Psychologist* Vol.44(9), pp. 1175–1184.
- (1991) Self-regulation of motivation through anticipatory and self-reactive mechanisms. In: R.A. Dienstbier ([ed.]), *Perspectives on Motivation*. Vol. 38. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, pp. 69–164.
- (1994) Regulative function of perceived self-efficacy. In: M. Rumsey, C. Walker, and J. Harris ([eds.]), *Personnel Selection and Classification*. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, pp. 261–271.

- Bandura, A. (2000) Exercise of human agency through collective efficacy. *Current Directions in Psychological Science* Vol.9(3), pp. 75–78. DOI: [10.1111/1467-8721.00064](https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.00064).
- (2006) Toward a psychology of human agency. *Perspectives on Psychological Science* Vol.1(2), pp. 164–180. DOI: [10.1111/j.1745-6916.2006.00011.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6916.2006.00011.x).
- (2010) Self-efficacy. In: *The Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology*. American Cancer Society, pp. 1–3. DOI: [10.1002/9780470479216.corpsy0836](https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470479216.corpsy0836).
- Bandura, A. and Schunk, D.H. (1981) Cultivating competence, self-efficacy, and intrinsic interest through proximal self-motivation. *Journal of personality and social psychology* Vol.41(30), pp. 586–598. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.41.3.586>.
- Banville, D., Desrosiers, P., and Genet-Volet, Y. (2000) Translating questionnaires and inventories using a cross-cultural translation technique. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education* Vol.19(3), pp. 374–97. DOI: [10.1123/jtpe.19.3.374](https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.19.3.374).
- Bayoud, M.N.S. (2013) How the Libyan context can shape corporate social responsibility disclosure in Libya. *Journal of Accounting and Marketing* Vol.2(3), pp. 1–5. DOI: [10.4172/2168-9601.1000105](https://doi.org/10.4172/2168-9601.1000105).
- Becker, H. and Geer, B. (1957) Participant observation and interviewing: a comparison. *Human Organisation* Vol.16(3), pp. 28–35.
- Benton, T. and Craib, I. (2010) *Philosophy of social science: The philosophical foundations of social thought*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- Bernard, H.R. (2006) Interviewing: unstructured and semistructured. In: *Research Methods in Anthropology: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*, pp. 210–250.
- (2011) *Research Methods in Anthropology: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. 5th ed. Rowman & Littlefield.
- (2013) *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE.

- (2018) *Research Methods in Anthropology: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. 6th ed. London: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Bettez, S.C. (2015) Navigating the complexity of qualitative research in postmodern contexts: assemblage, critical reflexivity, and communion as guides. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education* Vol.28(8), pp. 932–954. DOI: [10.1080/09518398.2014.948096](https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2014.948096).
- Biesta, G. (2009) Good education in an age of measurement: on the need to reconnect with the question of purpose in education. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability* Vol.21(1), pp. 33–46. DOI: [10.1007/s11092-008-9064-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-008-9064-9).
- Biggs, J.B. (1989) Approaches to the enhancement of tertiary teaching. *Higher Education Research & Development* Vol.8(1), pp. 7–25. DOI: [10.1080/0729436890080102](https://doi.org/10.1080/0729436890080102).
- Biggs, J.B. and Tang, C. (2011) *Teaching for Quality Learning at University: What the Student Does*. 4th ed. McGraw-hill Education.
- Black, P., Harrison, C., and Lee, C. (2003) *Assessment for Learning: Putting it into Practice*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Black, P., Harrison, C., Lee, C., Marshall, B., and Wiliam, D. (2004) Working inside the black box: Assessment for Learning in the classroom. *Phi Delta Kappan* Vol.86(1), pp. 8–21.
- Black, P. and Wiliam, D. (1998) Assessment and classroom learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* Vol.5(1), pp. 7–74. DOI: [10.1080/0969595980050102](https://doi.org/10.1080/0969595980050102).
- (2006) Developing a theory of formative assessment. In: J. Gardner ([ed.]), *Assessment and Learning*. London: SAGE.
- (2009) Developing the theory of formative assessment. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability* Vol.21(1), pp. 5–31.
- Blanchard, C.M. (May 2016) *Libya: Transition and US policy*. CRS-RL33142. Washington United States: Congressional Research Service.

- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology* Vol.3(2), pp. 77–101. DOI: [10.1191/1478088706qp0630a](https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a).
- Breen, M.P. (1985) Authenticity in the language classroom. *Applied linguistics* Vol.6(1), pp. 60–70.
- Brindley, G. (2001) Assessment. In: R. Carter and D. Nunan ([eds.]), *The Cambridge Guide to Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 137–143.
- Broadfoot, P. (1996) *Education, Assessment and Society: a Sociological Analysis*. Open University Pres.
- Brown, G.T.L. (2004) Teachers' conceptions of assessment: implications for policy and professional development. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* Vol.11(3), pp. 301–318. DOI: [10.1080/0969594042000304609](https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594042000304609).
- Brown, H.D (2000) *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. 4th ed. New York: Longman.
- (1990) M & Ms for language classrooms? Another look at motivation. In: *Georgetown University round table on language and linguistics*. J.E. Alatis ([ed.]). Georgetown University Press, pp. 383–393.
- (2001a) *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy*. 2nd ed. New York: Pearson Education.
- (2007) *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. 5th ed. New York: Longman.
- Brown, J.D. (1993) Language test hysteria in Japan. *The Language Teacher* Vol.17(12), pp. 41–43.
- (2001b) *Using Surveys in Language Programs*. Cambridge: Cambridge university press.
- (2005) *Testing in Language Programs: a Comprehensive Guide to English Language Assessment*. McGraw-Hill College.

- (2012) EIL curriculum development. In: L. Alsagoff, S.L. McKay, G. Hu, and W.A. Renandya ([eds.]), *Principles and Practices for Teaching English as an International Language*. New York: Routledge, pp. 153–173.
- Brown, S. (July 2014) *The Big Issues and ELT 1: Globalisation*. *The Steve Brown Blog*. [Online] Available: <https://stevebrown70.wordpress.com/2014/07/19/the-big-issues-and-elt-1-globalisation/>. [Accessed: 17 January 2020].
- (Aug. 2015) *Performativity: how measurement, evidence-gathering and accountability are wrecking education*. *The Steve Brown Blog*. [Online] Available: <https://stevebrown70.wordpress.com/2015/08/04/performativity-how-measurement-evidence-gathering-and-accountability-are-wrecking-education/>. [Accessed: 01 January 2021].
- Brumfit, C.J. and Johnson, K. (1979) *The Communicative Approach to Language Teaching*. Oxford University Press Oxford.
- Bygate, M. (1987) *Speaking*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Canagarajah, S. (1999) *Resisting Linguistic Imperialism in English Teaching*. Oxford University Press.
- (2006) Changing communicative needs, revised assessment objectives: testing English as an international language. *Language Assessment Quarterly* Vol.3(3), pp. 229–242. DOI: [10.1207/s15434311laq0303_1](https://doi.org/10.1207/s15434311laq0303_1).
- Candlin, C.N. and Edelhoff, C. (1982) *Challenges: Teacher's handbook*. Harlow: Longman.
- Caprara, G.V., Fida, R., Vecchione, M., Del Bove, G., Vecchio, G.M., Barbaranelli, C., and Bandura, A. (2008) Longitudinal analysis of the role of perceived self-efficacy for self-regulated learning in academic continuance and achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology* Vol.100(3), pp. 525–534.
- Cassady, J.C. (2010) *Anxiety in schools: The causes, consequences, and solutions for academic anxieties*. Peter Lang.
- Castillo, E.S. (1972) Motivational variables in second language acquisition. *Philippine Journal of Linguistics* Vol.3(2), pp. 94–124.

- Charmaz, K. (2014) *Constructing Grounded Theory*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE.
- Chavez, C. (2008) Conceptualizing from the inside: advantages, complications, and demands on insider positionality. *The Qualitative Report* Vol.13(3), pp. 474–494.
- Cheng, Y., Horwitz, E.K., and Schallert, D.L. (1999) Language anxiety: Differentiating writing and speaking components. *Language Learning* Vol.49(3), pp. 417–446.
- Clark, A., Holland, C., Katz, J., and Peace, S. (2009) Learning to see: lessons from a participatory observation research project in public spaces. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* Vol.12(4), pp. 345–60.
- Codo, E. (2008) Interviews and questionnaires. In: L. Wei and M.G. Moyer ([eds.]), *The Blackwell Guide to Research Methods in Bilingualism and Multilingualism*. Malden, MA: Blackwell, pp. 158–176.
- Cohen, A.D. (1994) *Assessing Language Ability in the Classroom*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K. (2018) *Research Methods in Education*. 8th ed. Routledge.
- Collis, J. and Hussey, R. (2013) *Business Research: a Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students*. 4th ed. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- Corbin, J. and Strauss, A. (2015) *Basics of Qualitative Research: Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory*. 4th ed. London: SAGE.
- Creswell, J. (2014) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 4th ed. London: SAGE.
- Crooks, T.J. (1988) Impact of classroom assessment on students. *Review of Educational Research* Vol.58(4), pp. 438–481. DOI: [10.3102/00346543058004438](https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543058004438).

- Crossouard, B. (2012) Classroom assessment and education: Challenging the assumptions of socialisation and instrumentality. *Education Inquiry* Vol.3(2), pp. 187–199.
- Cypress, B.S. (2017) Rigor or reliability and validity in qualitative research: perspectives, strategies, reconceptualization, and recommendations. *Dimensions of Critical Care Nursing* Vol.36(4), pp. 253–263. DOI: [10.1097/DCC.0000000000000253](https://doi.org/10.1097/DCC.0000000000000253).
- Davies, A., Hamp-Lyons, L., and Kemp, C. (2003) Whose norms? International proficiency tests in English. *World Englishes* Vol.22(4), pp. 571–584. DOI: [10.1111/j.1467-971X.2003.00324.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-971X.2003.00324.x).
- de Bot, K. (1996) The psycholinguistics of the output hypothesis. *Language Learning* Vol.46(3), pp. 529–55.
- de la Campa, J. and Nassaji, H. (2009) The amount, purpose, and reasons for using L1 in L2 classrooms. *Foreign Language Annals* Vol.42(4), pp. 742–759.
- Dekeyser, R.M. and Sokalski, K.J. (1996) The differential role of comprehension and production practice. *Language Learning* Vol.46(4), pp. 613–642. DOI: [10.1111/j.1467-1770.1996.tb01354.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-1770.1996.tb01354.x).
- Denscombe, M. (2014) *The Good Research Guide for Small-Scale Social Projects*. 6th ed. Maidenhead, England: Open University Press.
- Derwing, T.M. (2017) L2 fluency development. In: T.M. Derwing, S. Loewen, and M. Sato ([eds.]), *The Routledge Handbook of Second Language Acquisition*, pp. 246–259.
- Diaab, S. (2016) Role of faulty instructional methods in Libyan EFL learners' speaking difficulties. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* Vol.232, pp. 338–345.
- Diamond, I. and Quinby, L. (1988) *Feminism & Foucault: Reflections on Resistance*. Boston: Northeastern University Press.
- Diaz Larenas, C.H., Rodriguez Moran, A.V., and Poblete Rivera, K.J. (2011) Comparing teaching styles and personality types of EFL instructors in the

- public and private sectors. *Profile Issues in Teachers Professional Development* Vol.13(1), pp. 111–127.
- DiCicco-Bloom, B. and Crabtree, B.F. (2006) The qualitative research interview. *Medical Education* Vol.40(4), pp. 314–321.
- Dörnyei, Z. (1994) Motivation and motivating in the foreign language classroom. *The Modern Language Journal* Vol.78, pp. 273–284. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/330107>.
- (1998a) *Demotivation in foreign language learning: Paper presented at TESOL 98' Congress*. Seattle, WA.
- (1998b) Motivation in second and foreign language learning. *Language Teaching* Vol.31(3), pp. 117–135.
- (2001a) New themes and approaches in second language motivation research. *Annual review of applied linguistics* Vol.21(1), pp. 43–59.
- (2001b) *Teaching and researching Motivation*. Harlow: Longman.
- (2005) *The psychology of the language learner: Individual differences in second language acquisition*. Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Dörnyei, Z. and Skehan, P. (2003a) Individual differences in second language learning. In: *The handbook of second language acquisition*. C.J. Doughty and M.H. Long ([eds.]). Blackwell Publishing, pp. 589–630.
- (2003b) Individual differences in second language learning. In: *The Handbook of Second Language Acquisition*. Wiley Online Library, pp. 589–630.
- Dörnyei, Z. and Taguchi, T. (2009) *Questionnaires in Second Language Research: Construction, Administration, and Processing*. 2nd ed. Oxen: Taylor & Francis.
- Dörnyei, Z. and Ushioda, E. (2011) *Teaching and Researching Motivation*. Applied linguistics in action. Routledge.
- Drost, E.A. (2011) Validity and reliability in social science research. *Education Research and Perspectives* Vol.38(1), pp. 105–123.

- Duff, P. (2001) Language, literacy, content, and (pop) culture: challenges for ESL students in mainstream courses. *Canadian Modern Language Review* Vol.58(1), pp. 103–132. DOI: [10.3138/cmlr.58.1.103](https://doi.org/10.3138/cmlr.58.1.103).
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R., and Lowe, A. (2002) *Management Research: an Introduction*. 2nd ed. SAGE series in management research. London: SAGE.
- Edwards, R. and Holland, J. (2013) *What is Qualitative Interviewing?* A&C Black.
- Ehrman, M.E. (1996) *Understanding second language learning difficulties*. Sage.
- Elabbar, A.A. (2011) An Investigation of Influences Affecting Libyan English as Foreign Language University Teachers (LEFLUTs), Teaching Approaches in the Language Classrooms. Doctoral thesis. University of Glasgow.
- Ellis, R. (1992) *Second Language Acquisition and Language Pedagogy*. Multilingual Matters.
- (1993) The structural syllabus and second language acquisition. *TESOL Quarterly* Vol.27(1), pp. 91–113. DOI: [10.2307/3586953](https://doi.org/10.2307/3586953).
- (1999) *Retrospect and prospect*. R. Ellis ([ed.]). Amsterdam: John Benjamins, pp. 233–258.
- (2003) *Task-Based Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- (2006) Researching the effects of form-focused instruction on L2 acquisition. *AILA Review: Themes in SLA Research* Vol.19, pp. 18–41.
- Entwistle, N. (1991) Approaches to learning and perceptions of the learning environment - Introduction to the special issue. *Higher Education* Vol.22(3), pp. 201–204.
- Entwistle, N. and Ramsden, P. (2015) *Understanding Student Learning (Routledge Revivals)*. Routledge.
- Erlich, R.J. and Russ-Eft, D. (2011) Applying social cognitive theory to academic advising to assess student learning outcomes. *NACADA Journal* Vol.31(2), pp. 5–15.

- Errihani, M. (2017) English education policy and practice in Morocco. In: R. Kirkpatrick ([ed.]), *English Language Education Policy in the Middle East and North Africa*. Kuwait: Springer, pp. 115–131.
- Evans, E. and Engelberg, R. (1988) Pupils' perception of school grading. *Journal of Research and Development in Education* Vol.21, pp. 44–54.
- Falout, J. and Maruyama, M. (2004) A comparative study of proficiency and learner demotivation. *The Language Teacher* Vol.28(8), pp. 3–10.
- Farooqui, S. (2007) Developing speaking skills of adult learners in private universities in Bangladesh: Problems and solutions. *Australian Journal of Adult Learning* (1), pp. 94–110.
- Farzin-nia, S. (1964) French influences on the educational system of Iran. Masters thesis. The American University of Beirut.
- Fauzan, U. (2016) Enhancing speaking ability of EFL students through debate and peer assessment. *EFL Journal* Vol.1(1), pp. 49–57.
- Firth, A. (1996) The discursive accomplishment of normality: On 'lingua franca' English and conversation analysis. *Journal of Pragmatics* Vol.26(2), pp. 237–259. DOI: [10.1016/0378-2166\(96\)00014-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-2166(96)00014-8).
- Forde, C., McMahon, M., McPhee, A.D., and Patrick, F. (2006) *Professional development, reflection and enquiry*. Sage.
- Foucault, M. (1970) *The Order of Things*. London: Routledge.
- (1977) *Discipline and Punish: the Birth of the Prison*. London: Allen Lane.
- (1980) *Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings, 1972-1977*. Vintage.
- (1984) *The Foucault Reader*. Pantheon.
- (1998) *The Will to Knowledge: the History of Sexuality: Vol.1*. Trans. by R. Hurley. London: Penguin.
- Frankfort-Nachmias, C. and Nachmias, D. (1992) *Research Methods in the Social Sciences*. 4th ed. London: Edward Arnold.

- Frey, J.H. and Oishi, S.M. (1995) *How to Conduct Interviews by Telephone and in Person. The Survey Kit*. Vol. 4. Thousand Oaks: SAGE.
- Gadour, A. (2006) Libyan children's views on the importance of school factors which contributed to their emotional and behavioural difficulties. *School Psychology International* Vol.27(2), pp. 171–191.
- Gardner, R. C. and MacIntyre, P. D. (1993) On the measurement of affective variables in second language learning. *Language Learning* Vol.43(2), pp. 157–194.
- Gardner, R.C. (1985) *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. Arnold.
- Gardner, R.C. and Lambert, W.E. (1959) Motivational variables in second-language acquisition. *Canadian Journal of Psychology* Vol.13(4), pp. 266–272.
- (1972) *Attitudes and Motivation in Second-Language Learning*. Rowley, MA: Newbury House.
- Gardner, R.C. and MacIntyre, P.D. (1991) An instrumental motivation in language study: Who says it isn't effective? *Studies in Second Language Acquisition* Vol.13(1), pp. 57–72.
- Gardner, R.C., Moorcroft, R., and Metforda, J. (1989) Second language learning in an immersion programme: Factors influencing acquisition and retention. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology* Vol.8(5), pp. 287–305.
- Gardner, R.C., Tremblay, P.F., and Masgoret, A.-M. (1997) Towards a full model of second language learning: an empirical investigation. *Towards a full model of second language learning: an empirical investigation* Vol. 81(3), pp. 344–362.
- Gaskell, G. (2000) Individual and group interviewing. In: M.A. Baur and G. Gaskell ([eds.]), *Qualitative Researching with Text, Image and Sound: a Practical Handbook*. London: SAGE, pp. 39–56.
- Gass, S.M., Selinker, L., and Plonsky, L. (2013) *Second language acquisition: An introductory course*. 4th ed. Taylor & Francis Group.

- Gee, J.P. (2004) *An Introduction to Discourse Analysis: Theory and Method*. 2nd ed. London and New York: Routledge.
- Ghanizadeh, A. and Rostami, S. (2015) A Dörnyei-inspired study on second language motivation: A cross-comparison analysis in public and private contexts. *Psychol Stud* Vol.60, pp. 292–301. DOI: <https://doi-org.libproxy.ncl.ac.uk/10.1007/s12646-015-0328-4>.
- Gheblawi, G. (2011) Libyan re-independence and reclaiming the revolution. *Perspectives* Vol.2, pp. 176–179.
- Gholami, J., Sarkhosh, M., and Abdi, H. (2016) An exploration of teaching practices of private, public, and public-private EFL teachers in Iran. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability* Vol.18(1), pp. 16–33.
- Gillham, B. (2000) *Research Interview*. London: Continuum.
- Gipps, C. (1999) Socio-cultural aspects of assessment. *Review of Research in Education* Vol.24(1), pp. 355–392.
- Glaser, B.G. and Strauss, A.L. (1967) *The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research*. Chicago: Aldine Publishers.
- Goel, V. (2007) Anatomy of deductive reasoning. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* Vol.11(10), pp. 435–441.
- Golafshani, N. (2003) Understanding reliability and validity in qualitative research. *The Qualitative Report* Vol.8(4), pp. 597–606. URL: <https://nsuworks.nova.edu/tqr/vol8/iss4/6>.
- Gorham, J. and Christophel, D.M. (1992) Students' perception of teacher behaviors as motivating and demotivating factors in college classes. *Communication Quarterly* Vol.40, pp. 239–252. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01463379209369839>.
- Graddol, D. (2006) *English next: Why global English may mean the end of 'English as a foreign language'*. London, England: The British Council.
- Griffie, D.T. (2005) Research tips: interview data collection. *Journal of Developmental Education* Vol.28(3), pp. 36–37.

- Hajjaji, S.A. (1967) *The New Libya: a Geographical, Social, Economic and Political Study*. Tripoli: Government Print. Press.
- Hammersley, M. and Traianou, A. (2012) *Ethics in Qualitative Research: Controversies and Contexts*. London: SAGE.
- Hamouda, A. (2013) An exploration of causes of Saudi students' reluctance to participate in the English language classroom. *International Journal of English Language Education* Vol.1(1), pp. 17–34.
- Hancock, C.R. (1994) *Alternative assessment and second language study: What and why?* ERIC Digest ED376695. [Online] Available: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED376695.pdf>. [Accessed: 20 May 2017].
- Hanrahan, S.J. and Isaacs, G. (2001) Assessing self- and peer-assessment: the students' views. *Higher Education Research & Development* Vol.20(1), pp. 53–70. DOI: [10.1080/07294360123776](https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360123776).
- Harlen, W. and Deakin Crick, R. (2003) Testing and motivation for learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* Vol.10(2), pp. 169–207. DOI: [10.1080/0969594032000121270](https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594032000121270).
- Harmer, J. (1994) *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. London: Longman.
- (2001) *The Practice of Communicative Language Teaching*. 3rd ed. London: Longman.
- (2006) *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. Pearson: Longman.
- Hayward, L. and Spencer, E. (2010) The complexities of change: formative assessment in Scotland. *The Curriculum Journal* Vol.21(2), pp. 161–177. DOI: [10.1080/09585176.2010.480827](https://doi.org/10.1080/09585176.2010.480827).
- Hedman, C. and Magnusson, U. (2019) Performative functions of multilingual policy in second language education in Sweden. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, pp. 1–15. DOI: [10.1080/13670050.2019.1693956](https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2019.1693956).
- Heit, E. (2000) Properties of inductive reasoning. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review* Vol.7(4), pp. 569–592.

- Hellawell, D. (2006) Inside–out: analysis of the insider–outsider concept as a heuristic device to develop reflexivity in students doing qualitative research. *Teaching in Higher Education* Vol.11(4), pp. 483–494. DOI: [10.1080/13562510600874292](https://doi.org/10.1080/13562510600874292).
- Hentschell, E. (2009) Translation as an inevitable part of foreign language acquisition. In: A. Witte, T. Harden, and A.R.O. Harden ([eds.]), *Translation in Second Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford: Peter Lang AG, International Academic Publishers, pp. 15–29.
- Higson, A. and Blake, J. (1993) The true and fair view concept – a formula for international disharmony: some empirical evidence. *International Journal of Accounting* Vol.28(2), pp. 104–115.
- Hirschi, T. (2017) *Causes of Delinquency*. London: Routledge.
- Hodkinson, P., Biesta, G., and James, D. (2007) Learning cultures and a cultural theory of learning. In: D. James and G. Biesta ([eds.]), *Improving Learning Cultures in Further Education*. London: Routledge, pp. 41–58. DOI: [10.4324/9780203940099](https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203940099).
- Horwitz, E.K. (1995) Student affective reactions and the teaching and learning of foreign languages. *International Journal of Educational Research* Vol.23(7), pp. 573–579.
- (2001) Language anxiety and achievement. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics* Vol.21, pp. 112–126. DOI: [10.1017/S0267190501000071](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190501000071).
- Horwitz, E.K., Horwitz, M.B., and Cope, J. (1986) Foreign language classroom anxiety. *The Modern Language Journal* Vol.70(2), pp. 125–132.
- Hughes, A. (2003) *Testing for Language Teachers*. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hussy, J. and Hussy, R. (1997) *Business Research: a Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students*. Basingstock: Macmillan Business.
- Ibrahim, A. (2015) Teaching and Learning of English in Libyan Universities. A Case Study Investigating the English Language Teaching Knowledge of Libyan

- Pre-Service Teachers of English in the University of Benghazi - Agdabia Faculty of Arts and Sciences in Libya. Doctoral thesis. University of the Sunshine Coast.
- Imhoof, M. (1977) The English language in Egypt. *English around the World* Vol.17, p. 3.
- Jacknick, C.M. and Thornbury, S. (2013) The task at hand: noticing as a mind-body-world phenomenon. In: J. Bergsleithner, S. Frota, and J.K. Yoshioka ([eds.]), *Noticing and Second Language Acquisition: Studies in Honor of Dick Schmidt*. Manoa: University of Hawai'i Press. Chap. 18, pp. 309–329.
- Järvelä, S. and Järvenoja, H. (2011) Socially constructed self-regulated learning and motivation regulation in collaborative learning groups. *Teachers College Record* Vol.113(2), pp. 350–374.
- Joughin, G.R. (2003) Oral Assessment from the Learner's Perspective: the Experience of Oral Assessment in Post-Compulsory Education. Doctoral thesis. Griffith University.
- Kachru, B. (1985) Standards, codification and sociolinguistic realism: The English language in the outer circle. In: *English in the world: Teaching and learning the language and literatures*. R. Quirk and H. Widdowson ([eds.]). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 11–36.
- Kachru, Y. and Nelson, C.L. (2006) *World Englishes in Asian contexts*. Hong Kong University Press.
- Kanuha, V.K. (2000) “Being native” versus “going native”: conducting social work research as an insider. *National Association of Social Workers* Vol.45(5), pp. 439–447.
- Katz, A. (2012) Linking assessment with instructional aims and learning. In: C. Coombe, P. Davidson, B. O'Sullivan, and S. Stoyhoff ([eds.]), *The Cambridge Guide to Second Language Assessment*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 66–73.

- Kawulich, B.B (2005) Participant observation as a data collection method. In: *Forum qualitative sozialforschung/forum: Qualitative social research*. Vol. Vol.6. (2).
- Kelly, C., Kelly, L., Offner, M., and Vorland, B. (2002) Effective ways to use authentic materials with ESL/EFL students. *The Internet TESL Journal* Vol.8(11), pp. 1–5.
- Ketabi, S. and Ketabi, S. (2014) Classroom and formative assessment in second/foreign language teaching and learning. *Theory & Practice in Language Studies* Vol.4(2), pp. 435–440. DOI: [10.4304/tpls.4.2.435-440](https://doi.org/10.4304/tpls.4.2.435-440).
- Khalid, K.A.A. (2017) Learning and Teaching in English: a Case Study of Higher Education in Libya. Doctoral thesis. Liverpool John Moores University.
- Khan, R. (2006) The IELTS speaking test: analysing culture bias. *Malaysian Journal of ELT Research* Vol.2(1), pp. 60–79.
- Kirkpatrick, A. (2010) *English as a lingua franca in ASEAN: A multilingual model*. Hong Kong, China: Hong Kong University Press.
- Kirkpatrick, R. and Barnawi, O.Z. (2017) English language education policy in MENA. In: R. Kirkpatrick ([ed.]), *English Language Education Policy in the Middle East and North Africa*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 1–8. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-46778-8_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46778-8_1).
- Kissling, E.M. and O'Donnell, M.E. (2015) Increasing language awareness and self-efficacy of FL students using self-assessment and the ACTFL proficiency guidelines. *Language Awareness* Vol.24(4), pp. 283–302. DOI: [10.1080/09658416.2015.1099659](https://doi.org/10.1080/09658416.2015.1099659).
- Klenowski, V. (2009) Assessment for Learning revisited: an Asia-Pacific perspective. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* Vol.16(3), pp. 263–268. DOI: [10.1080/09695940903319646](https://doi.org/10.1080/09695940903319646).
- Kluger, A.N. and DeNisi, A. (1996) The effects of feedback interventions on performance: a historical review, a meta-analysis, and a preliminary feedback intervention theory. *Psychological Bulletin* Vol.119(2), pp. 254–284.

- Krashen, S.D. (1981) Bilingual education and second language acquisition theory. In: *Schooling and Language Minority Students: a Theoretical Framework*. Los Angeles, California: National Dissemination and Assessment Center, California State University, pp. 51–79.
- (1982) *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. Oxford Pergamon.
- (1985) *The Input Hypothesis: Issues and Implications*. Longman.
- (1994) The Input Hypothesis and its rivals. In: N.C. Ellis ([ed.]), *Implicit and Explicit Learning of Languages*. Academic Press, pp. 45–77.
- Krippendorp, K. (2004) *Content Analysis: an Introduction to its Methodology*. SAGE.
- Larsen-Freeman, D. (1997) Chaos/complexity science and second language acquisition. *Applied linguistics* Vol.18(2), pp. 141–165. DOI: [10.1093/applin/18.2.141](https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/18.2.141).
- Lealy, S., Lyon, C., Thompson, M., and Wiliam, D. (2005) Classroom assessment: minute-by-minute and day-by-day. *Educational Leadership* Vol.63(3), pp. 18–24.
- Lee, W.Y. (1995) Authenticity revisited: text authenticity and learner authenticity. *ELT Journal* Vol.49(4), pp. 323–328.
- Leow, R.P. (2007) Input in the L2 classroom: an attentional perspective on receptive practice. In: R.M. DeKeyser ([ed.]), *Practice in a Second Language: Perspectives from Applied Linguistics and Cognitive Psychology*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- (2019) Noticing hypothesis. In: J.I. Lontas, International Association, and M. DelliCarpini ([eds.]), *The TESOL Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching*. American Cancer Society, pp. 1–6. DOI: [10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0086.pub2](https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0086.pub2).
- Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (1985) *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, California: SAGE.

- Lindblom-ylänne, S., Pihlajamäki, H., and Kotkas, T. (2006) Self-, peer-and teacher-assessment of student essays. *Active Learning in Higher Education* Vol.7(1), pp. 51–62. DOI: [10.1177/1469787406061148](https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787406061148).
- Lindorff, M. (2010) Ethics, ethical human research and human research ethics committees. *Australian Universities' Review* Vol.52(1), pp. 51–59.
- Little, D., Devitt, S., and Singleton, D.M. (1988) *Authentic Texts in Foreign Language Teaching: Theory and Practice*. Authentik.
- Liu, H-J.C. (2002) Translation of instruments for cross-cultural research. *Journal of the Da-Yeh University* Vol.11(2), pp. 79–88. DOI: [10.7119/JDYU.200212.0079](https://doi.org/10.7119/JDYU.200212.0079).
- Liu, M. and Huang, W. (2011) An exploration of foreign language anxiety and English learning motivation. *Education Research International* Vol.2011, pp. 1–8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/493167>.
- Lladó, A.P., Soley, L.F., Sansbelló, R.M., Pujolras, G.A., Planella, J.P., Roura-Pascual, N., Martínez, J.J.S., and Moreno, L.M. (2014) Student perceptions of peer assessment: an interdisciplinary study. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education* Vol.39(5), pp. 592–610. DOI: [10.1080/02602938.2013.860077](https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2013.860077).
- Long, M.H. and Norris, J.M. (2000) Task-based teaching and assessment. In: M. Byram ([ed.]), *Encyclopedia of Language Teaching*. London: Routledge, pp. 597–603.
- Lowenberg, P.H. (2002) Assessing English proficiency in the expanding circle. *World Englishes* Vol.21(3), pp. 431–435.
- Lune, H. and Berg, B.L. (2017) *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences*. 9 Global Edition. Essex: Pearson Education Ltd.
- MacIntyre, P.D. (1999) Language anxiety: A review of the research for language teachers. In: *Affect in foreign language and second language learning: A practical guide to creating a low-anxiety classroom atmosphere*. D.J. Young ([ed.]). Boston: McGraw-Hill College, pp. 24–45.

- (2002) Motivation, anxiety and emotion in second language acquisition. In: *Individual differences and instructed language learning*. P. Robinson ([ed.]). Amsterdam: John Benjamins, pp. 45–68.
 - (2007) Willingness to communicate in the second language: Understanding the decision to speak as a volitional process. *The Modern Language Journal* Vol.91(4), pp. 564–576.
- MacIntyre, P.D. and Charos, C. (1996) Personality, attitudes, and affect as predictors of second language communication. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology* Vol.15, pp. 3–26.
- MacIntyre, P.D. and Gardner, R.C. (1991) Methods and results in the study of anxiety and language learning: A review of the literature. *Language Learning* Vol.41(1), pp. 85–117.
- (1994) The subtle effects of language anxiety on cognitive processing in the second language. *Language Learning* Vol.44(2), pp. 283–305.
- Mackenzie, N. and Knipe, S. (2006) Research dilemmas: paradigms, methods and methodology. *Issues in Educational Research* Vol.16(2), pp. 193–205.
- Mackey, A. (2007) *Conversational Interaction in Second Language Acquisition: a Collection of Empirical Studies*. Oxford Applied Linguistics. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Mackey, A. and Guss, S. (2005) *Second Language Research: Methodology and Design*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Mackey, A. and Oliver, R. (2002) Interactional feedback and children’s L2 development. *System* Vol.30(4), pp. 459–477.
- MacLure, M. (2006) Entertaining doubts: on frivolity as resistance. In: J. Satterthwaite, W. Martin, and L. Roberts ([eds.]), *Discourse, Resistance and Identity Formation*. London: Trentham.
- Madsen, H.S. (1983) *Techniques in Testing*. New York: Oxford University Press.

- Maguire, M. and Delahunt, B. (2017) Doing a thematic analysis: a practical, step-by-step guide for learning and teaching scholars. *AISHE-J: The All Ireland Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education* Vol.9(3), pp. 3351–3354.
- Mahboob, A., Uhrig, K., Newman, K., and Hartford, B. S. (2004) Children of a lesser English: Status of nonnative English speakers as college-level English as a second language teachers in the United States. In: *Learning and teaching from experience: Perspectives on nonnative English-speaking professionals*. L. Kamhi-Stein ([ed.]). Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, pp. 100–120.
- Mahjobi, A. (2007) *Teacher Motivation in Secondary Schools: the Case of EFL Teachers in Ghadamas*. Tripoli: Al-Fateh University.
- Maley, A. and Duff, A. (1987) *Sounds Interesting: Resource Material for Teachers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Marczyk, G., De Matteo, D., and Festinger, D. (2005) *Essentials of Research Design and Methodology*. Hoboken: Wiley.
- Marshall, C. and Rossman, G.B. (2016) *Designing Qualitative Research*. 6th ed. Singapore: SAGE.
- Marzano, R.J. (2007) *The Art and Science of Teaching: A Comprehensive Framework for Effective Instruction*. Alexandria, Virginia USA: ASCD.
- McDonough, K. (2005) Identifying the impact of negative feedback and learners' responses on ESL question development. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition* Vol.27(1), pp. 79–103. DOI: [10.1017/S0272263105050047](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263105050047).
- McKay, S.L. (2002) *Teaching English as an International Language: Rethinking Goals and Perspectives*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- McMillan, J.H. and Hearn, J. (2008) Student self-assessment: the key to stronger student motivation and higher achievement. *Educational Horizons* Vol.87(1), pp. 40–49.
- McNamara, T.F. (1996) *Measuring Second Language Performance*. London: Longman.

- (2001) Language assessment as social practice: challenges for research. *Language Testing* Vol.18(4), pp. 333–349. DOI: [10.1177/026553220101800402](https://doi.org/10.1177/026553220101800402).
- Meng, J. (2010) Cooperative learning method in the practice of English reading and speaking. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research* Vol.1(5), pp. 701–703.
- Merriam, S. (1995) What can you tell from an N of 1?: issues of validity and reliability in qualitative research. *PAACE Journal of Lifelong Learning* Vol.4, pp. 51–60.
- Ministry of Education (2018) *Ministry of Education, Libya*. [Online] Available: <https://moe.gov.ly>. [Accessed: 31 November 2018].
- Mishan, F. (2005) *Designing authenticity into language learning materials*. Intellect Books.
- Mizruchi, M.S. (1991) Urgency, motivation, and group performance: The effect of prior success on current success among professional basketball teams. *Social Psychology Quarterly* Vol.52, pp. 181–189.
- Modiano, M. (2001) Linguistic imperialism, cultural integrity, and EIL. *ELT Journal* Vol.55(4), pp. 339–347. DOI: [10.1093/elt/55.4.339](https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/55.4.339).
- Mohamed, J.M.G. (2014) Teaching English in Libya: reflective views. *International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature* Vol.2(8), pp. 32–39.
- Mohsen, A.S. (2014) Teaching English as a foreign language in Libya. *Scientific Research Journal* Vol.2(11), pp. 58–64.
- Moore, N. (2000) *How to Do Research: the Complete Guide to Designing and Managing Research Projects*. London, UK: Library Association Publication.
- Morrow, C.K. (2018) Communicative language testing. In: J.I. Liantas, International Association, and M. DelliCarpini ([eds.]), *The TESOL Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching*. American Cancer Society, pp. 1–7. DOI: [10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0383](https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0383).
- Morse, J.M. (2015) Critical analysis of strategies for determining rigor in qualitative inquiry. *Qualitative Health Research* Vol.25(9), pp. 1212–1222. DOI: [10.1177/1049732315588501](https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732315588501).

- Morse, J.M. (2016) *Qualitative Health Research: Creating a New Discipline*. New York: Routledge.
- Najeeb, S.R. (2013) The business of teaching English as a second language: a Libyan case study. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* Vol.70, pp. 1243–1253. DOI: [10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.01.184](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.01.184).
- Najeeb, S.R. and ELdokali, E. (2012) *English in Libya: The language of development*. [Online] Available: http://www.iairs.org/Abstracts_english/INV.pdf.
- Natale, S.M. and Doran, C. (2012) Marketization of education: an ethical dilemma. *Journal of Business Ethics* Vol.105(2), pp. 187–196.
- Natriello, G. (1987) The impact of evaluation processes on students. *Educational Psychologist* Vol.22(2), pp. 155–175. DOI: [10.1207/s15326985ep2202_4](https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep2202_4).
- Neuman, W.L. (2011) *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. 7th ed. London: Pearson Education.
- Nicol, D.J. and Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006) Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: a model and seven principles of good feedback practice. *Studies in Higher Education* Vol.31(2), pp. 199–218. DOI: [10.1080/03075070600572090](https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070600572090).
- Norris, N. (1997) Error, bias and validity in qualitative research. *Educational Action Research* Vol.5(1), pp. 172–176. DOI: [10.1080/09650799700200020](https://doi.org/10.1080/09650799700200020).
- Nunan, D. (1997) Designing and adapting materials to encourage learner autonomy. In: P. Benson and Voller P. ([eds.]), *Autonomy and Independence in Language Learning*. London: Longman, pp. 192–203.
- Nuttall, C. (1996) *Teaching Reading Skills in a Foreign Language*. ERIC.
- Nyquist, J.B. (2003) The Benefits of Reconstructing Feedback as a Larger System of Formative Assessment: A Meta-Analysis. Masters thesis. Vanderbilt University.
- O'Malley, J.M. and Pierce, L.V. (1996) *Authentic assessment for English Language Learners: Practical Approaches for Teachers*. Massachusetts: Addison Wesley Publishing Company.

- O'Sullivan, A.V. (1990) The foreign language coursebook: a study of its role in learner motivation. Doctoral thesis. University of London.
- O'Sullivan, B (2012) A brief history of language testing. In: C. Coombe, P. Davidson, B. O'Sullivan, and S. Stoyhoff ([eds.]), *The Cambridge Guide to Second Language Assessment*. New York: Cambridge University Press, pp. 9–19.
- Omar, S. (2013) The relevance of Libyan secondary school materials to the learners and their needs. *Scientific Research Journal* Vol.1(v), pp. 27–40. URL: <http://www.scirj.org/rp/files/original/8e1d43ca4012bc037c227a1835eca7e1.pdf>.
- Omar, Y.Z. (2014) Perceptions of Selected Libyan Teachers of English as a Foreign Language Regarding Teaching of English in Libya. Doctoral thesis. University of Missouri-Columbia.
- Opie, C. (2004) What is educational research? In: C. Opie ([ed.]), *Doing Educational Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, pp. 1–14.
- Oppenheim, A.N. (1992) *Questionnaire Design, Interviewing and Attitude Measurement*. New York: Pinter.
- Or, I.G. and Shohamy, E. (2017) English education policy in Israel. In: R. Kirkpatrick ([ed.]), *English Language Education Policy in the Middle East and North Africa*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 63–75. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-46778-8_5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46778-8_5).
- Orafi, S.M.S. (2008) Investigating Teachers' Practices and Beliefs in Relation to Curriculum Innovation in English Language Teaching in Libya. Doctoral thesis. University of Leeds.
- Orafi, S.M.S. and Borg, S. (2009) Intentions and realities in implementing communicative curriculum reform. *System* Vol.37(2), pp. 243–253. DOI: [10.1016/j.system.2008.11.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2008.11.004).
- Otte, J.L. (2006) Real Language for Real People: a Descriptive and Exploratory Case Study of the Outcomes of Aural Authentic Texts on the Listening Comprehension of Adult English-as-a-Second Language Students Enrolled in

- an Advanced ESL Listening Course. Doctoral thesis. Loyola University Chicago.
- Oxford, R.L. (2001) ‘The bleached bones of a story’: Learners’ constructions of language teachers. In: *Learner contributions to language learning : new directions in research*. M.P. Breen ([ed.]). Applied linguistics and language study. Harlow, England: Longman, pp. 86–111.
- Papi, M. (2010) The L2 motivational self system, L2 anxiety, and motivated behavior: a structural equation modeling approach. *System* Vol. 38(3), pp. 467–479.
- Paris, S.G. and Paris, A.H. (2001) Classroom applications of research on self-regulated learning. *Educational Psychologist* Vol.36(2), pp. 89–101. DOI: [10.1207/S15326985EP3602_4](https://doi.org/10.1207/S15326985EP3602_4).
- Patton, M.Q. (1990) *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods*. 2nd ed. Newbury Park, California: SAGE.
- (2005) Qualitative research. In: B.S. Everitt and D. Howell ([eds.]), *Encyclopedia of Statistics in Behavioral Science*. Chester: John Wiley Sons, Ltd, Non-paginated.
- (2015) *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods: Integrating Theory and Practice*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE.
- Peacock, M. (1997) The effect of authentic materials on the motivation of EFL learners. *ELT Journal* Vol.51(2), pp. 144–156.
- Pennycook, A. (2006) Postmodernism in Language Policy. In: *An introduction to language policy: Theory and method*. T. Ricento ([ed.]). Oxford: Blackwell Publishing, pp. 60–76.
- Perrenoud, P. (1998) From formative evaluation to a controlled regulation of learning processes. Towards a wider conceptual field. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* Vol.5(1), pp. 85–102. DOI: [10.1080/0969595980050105](https://doi.org/10.1080/0969595980050105).

- Pinner, R.S. (2016) *Reconceptualising Authenticity for English as a Global Language*. Multilingual Matters.
- Podolefsky, N.S., Moore, E.B., and Perkins, K.K. (2013) *Implicit scaffolding in interactive simulations: Design strategies to support multiple educational goals*. [Online] Available: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1306.6544.pdf>. [Accessed: 03 August 2017].
- Polit, D.F. and Beck, C.T. (2006) *Essentials of Nursing Research. Methods, Appraisal, and Utilization*. 6th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- Pollard, A. and Triggs, P. (2001) *What Pupils Say: Changing Policy and Practice in Primary Education*. A&C Black.
- Powers, W.T. (1991) Commentary on Bandura's "human agency". *American Psychologist* Vol.46(2), pp. 151–153. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.46.2.151.b>.
- Qu, S.Q. and Dumay, J. (2011) The qualitative research interview. *Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management* Vol.8(3), pp. 238–264.
- Rachman, S. (1998) *Anxiety, Hove, East Sussex*. Psychology Press.
- Rajab, H. (2013) Developing speaking and writing skills of L1 Arabic EFL learners through teaching of IPA phonetic codes. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies* Vol.3(4), p. 653.
- Ramage, K. (1990) Motivational factors and persistence in foreign language study. *Language Learning* Vol.40(2), pp. 189–219.
- Ramaprasad, A. (1983) On the definition of feedback. *Behavioral Science* Vol.28(1), pp. 4–13. DOI: [10.1002/bs.3830280103](https://doi.org/10.1002/bs.3830280103).
- Ramsden, P. (2003) *Learning to Teach in Higher Education*. Routledge.
- Razmjoo, S.A. and Riazi, A.M. (2006) Is communicative language teaching practical in the Expanding Circle? A Case Study of Teachers of Shiraz High Schools and Institutes. *Journal of Language and Learning* Vol.4(2), pp. 144–171.

- Remenyi, D., Williams, B., Money, A., and Swartz, E. (1998) *Research in Business and Management*. London: SAGE.
- Richards L. and Morse, J.M. (2013) *Readme First for a User's Guide to Qualitative Methods*. 3rd ed. SAGE.
- Richards, L. (2009) *Handling Qualitative Data: a Practical Guide*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE.
- Richardson, S. (Apr. 2016) *The 'native factor', the haves and the have-nots. Online coverage of the Annual International IATEFL Conference & Exhibition*. [Online] Available: <https://iatefl.britishcouncil.org/2016/session/plenary-silvana-richardson>. [Accessed: 18 January 2020].
- Rolfe, G. (2006) Validity, trustworthiness and rigour: quality and the idea of qualitative research. *Journal of Advanced Nursing* Vol.53(3), pp. 304–310. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.03727.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.03727.x).
- Rosa, E. and Leow, R.P. (2004) Computerized task-based instruction in the L2 classroom: the effects of explicitness and type of feedback on L2 development. *Modern Language Journal* Vol.88, pp. 192–216.
- Rose, P. (1985) *Writing on Women: Essays in a Renaissance*. Middletown, CT: Wesleyan University Press.
- Rowley, J. (2012) Conducting research interviews. *Management Research Review* Vol.35(3/4), pp. 260–271. DOI: [10.1108/01409171211210154](https://doi.org/10.1108/01409171211210154).
- Rubin, H.J. and Rubin, I. S (2012) *Qualitative Interviewing: The Art of Hearing Data*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Rudnai, Z. (1996) Demotivation in learning English among secondary school students in Budapest. Masters thesis. Eötvös Loránd University.
- Sadeghi, K. and Richards, J.C. (2015) Teaching spoken English in Iran's private language schools: issues and options. *English Teaching* Vol.14(2), pp. 210–234.
- Saldaña, J. (2013) *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE.

- Saleh, N. and Zakaria, N. (2013) Investigating the difficulties faced in understanding, and strategies used in processing, English idioms by the Libyan students. *International Journal of English Language and Translation Studies* Vol.1(2), pp. 69–91.
- Sasaki, T. (1997) *One World English Course 1*. T. Sasaki ([ed.]). Tokyo: Kyoiku Shuppan.
- Sawani, F. (2009) Factors Affecting English Teaching and its Materials Preparation in Libya. Doctoral thesis. University of Essex.
- Schunk, D.H. (1995) Self-efficacy and education and instruction. In: Maddux J.E. ([ed.]), *Self-Efficacy, Adaptation, and Adjustment*. The Plenum Series in Social/Clinical Psychology. Boston, MA: Springer. DOI: [10.1007/978-1-4419-6868-5_10](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-6868-5_10).
- Scrivener, J. (2011) *Learning Teaching: the Essential Guide to English Language Teaching*. 3rd ed. Macmillan Books for Teachers. Oxford: Macmillan Education.
- Shamir, R. (2008) The age of responsabilization: On market-embedded morality. *Economy and Society* Vol.37(1), pp. 1–19. DOI: [10.1080/03085140701760833](https://doi.org/10.1080/03085140701760833).
- Shihiba, S.E.S. (2011) An Investigation of Libyan EFL Teachers' Conceptions of the Communicative Learner-Centred Approach in Relation to their Implementation of an English Language Curriculum Innovation in Secondary Schools. Doctoral thesis. Durham University.
- Shim, J.M. (2013) Involving the parents of English language learners in a rural area: focus on the dynamics of teacher-parent interactions. *Rural Educator* Vol.34(3), pp. 18–26.
- Silverman, D. (2013) *Doing Qualitative Research: a Practical Handbook*. 4th ed. London: SAGE.
- Simon, S. (1996) *Gender in Translation: Cultural Identity and the Politics of Transmission*. London: Routledge.
- Simons, J., Dewitte, S., and Lens, W. (2004) The role of different types of instrumentality in motivation, study strategies, and performance: Know why

- you learn, so you'll know what you learn! *British Journal of Educational Psychology* Vol.74(3), pp. 343–360. DOI: [10.1348/000712600161862](https://doi.org/10.1348/000712600161862).
- Simpson, M. and Tuson, J. (2003) *Using Observations in Small-Scale Research: A Beginner's Guide. Revised edition*. Glasgow: University of Glasgow, the SCRE Centre.
- Sjolie, D. (2002) Mixed level language class: an unlikely formula for success. *Journal of the Imagination in Language Learning and Teaching*, pp. 24–30.
- Sorrell, J.M. and Redmond, G.M. (1995) Interviews in qualitative nursing research: differing approaches for ethnographic and phenomenological studies. *Journal of Advanced Nursing* Vol.21(6), pp. 1117–1122.
- Spielberger, C.D. (1983) *Manual for the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory STAI (Form Y)*. Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press.
- Spolsky, B. (1985) The limits of authenticity in language testing. *Language Testing* Vol.2(1), pp. 31–40. DOI: [10.1177/026553228500200104](https://doi.org/10.1177/026553228500200104).
- Stevick, E.W. (1976) *Memory, Meaning and Method*. Rowley, Massachusetts: Newbury House.
- Stiefel, L. (2009) Translation as a means to intercultural communicative competence. In: A. Witte, T. Harden, and A.R.O. Harden ([eds.]), *Translation in Second Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford: Peter Lang AG, International Academic Publishers, pp. 99–117.
- Stiggins, R.J. (1987) Design and development of performance assessments. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice* Vol.6(3), pp. 33–42. DOI: [10.1111/j.1745-3992.1987.tb00507.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3992.1987.tb00507.x).
- Stobart, G. (2008) *Testing Times: the Uses and Abuses of Assessment*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Struyven, K., Dochy, F., and Janssens, S. (2003) Students' perceptions about new modes of assessment in higher education: a review. In: M. Segers, F. Dochy, and E. Cascallar ([eds.]), *Optimising New Modes of Assessment: in Search of Qualities and Standards*. Netherlands: Springer, pp. 171–223.

- Swain, M. (1985) Communicative competence: some roles of comprehensible input and comprehensible output in its development. In: S. Gass and C. Madden ([eds.]), *Input in Second Language Acquisition*. MA: Newbury House, pp. 235–53.
- (1995) Three functions of output in second language learning. In: G. Cook and B. Seidlhoffer ([eds.]), *Principles and Practice in Applied Linguistics: Studies in Honor of H. G. Widdowson*. Oxford University Press, pp. 125–44.
- (1998) Focus on form through conscious reflection. In: C. Doughty and J. Williams ([eds.]), *Focus on Form in Classroom Second Language Acquisition*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 64–81.
- (2005) The output hypothesis: theory and research. In: E. Hinkel ([ed.]), *Handbook of Research in Second Language Teaching and Learning*. Lawrence Erlbaum, pp. 471–81.
- Swain, M. and Lapkin, S. (2002) Talking it through: two French immersion learners' response to reformulation. *International Journal of Educational Research* Vol.37(3-4), pp. 285–304. DOI: [10.1016/S0883-0355\(03\)00006-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-0355(03)00006-5).
- Taras, M. (2003) To feedback or not to feedback in student self-assessment. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education* Vol.28(5), pp. 549–565. DOI: [10.1080/02602930301678](https://doi.org/10.1080/02602930301678).
- Taylor, S.J., Bogdan, R., and DeVault, M. (2015) *Introduction to Qualitative Research Methods: a Guidebook and Resource*. 4th ed. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
- Temple, B. and Young, A. (2004) Qualitative research and translation dilemmas. *Qualitative Research* Vol.4(2), pp. 161–178. DOI: [10.1177/1468794104044430](https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794104044430).
- Thornbury, S. (2017) *Scott Thornbury's 30 Language Teaching Methods*. Cambridge Handbooks for Language Teachers. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Tilley, S., Chambers, M., and Mackenzie, J.E. (1996) Problems of the researching person: doing insider research with your peer group. *Journal of Psychiatric and*

- Mental Health Nursing* Vol.3(4), pp. 267–268. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2850.1996.tb00121.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2850.1996.tb00121.x).
- Topping, K.J. (2009) Peer assessment. *Theory into Practice* Vol.48(1), pp. 20–27. DOI: [10.1080/00405840802577569](https://doi.org/10.1080/00405840802577569).
- Tsuchiya, M. (2006a) Factors in demotivation of lower proficiency English learners at college. *The Kyushu Academic Society of English Language Education (KASELE)* Vol.34, pp. 87–96.
- (2006b) Profiling of lower achievement English learners at college in terms of demotivating factors. *Annual Review of English Language Education in Japan (ARELE)* Vol.17, pp. 171–180.
- Turki, G.M.A. (1994) Teaching modern physics in developing countries. *Science Education* Vol.33. Sebha, Libya.
- Ur, P. (1999) *A Course in Language Teaching: Trainee Handbook*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Vaismoradi, M., Turunen, H., and Bondas, T. (2013) Content analysis and thematic analysis: implications for conducting a qualitative descriptive study. *Nursing & Health Sciences* Vol.15(3), pp. 398–405.
- VanPatten, B. (1996) *Input Processing and Grammar Instruction: Theory and Research in Second Language Acquisition*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex.
- VanPatten, B. and Cadierno, T. (1993) Input processing and second language acquisition: a role for instruction. *The Modern Language Journal* Vol.77(1), pp. 45–57. DOI: [10.1111/j.1540-4781.1993.tb01944.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1993.tb01944.x).
- von Wörde, R. (2003) Students' Perspectives on Foreign Language Anxiety. *Inquiry* Vol.8(1), pp. 1–15.
- Vygotsky, L.S. (1962) *Thought and Language*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.
- Walliman, N. (2017) *Research Methods: the Basics*. 2nd ed. London: Routledge.
- Watts, J.H. (2011) Ethical and practical challenges of participant observation in sensitive health research. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* Vol.14(4), pp. 301–312. DOI: [10.1080/13645579.2010.517658](https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2010.517658).

- Weedon, C. (1987) *Feminist Practice and Poststructuralist Theory*. New York, USA: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Weir, C.J. (1993) *Understanding and Developing Language Tests*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- (2005) *Language Testing and Validation: an Evidence-Based Approach*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. DOI: [10.1057/9780230514577](https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230514577).
- Wellington, J. (2015) *Educational Research*. 2nd ed. London: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Wertsch, J.V., Tulviste, P., and Hagstrom, F. (1993) A sociocultural approach to agency. In: E.A. Forman, N. Minick, and C.A. Stone ([eds.]), *Contexts for Learning: Sociocultural Dynamics in Children's Development*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 336–356.
- Weyers, J. (1999) The effect of authentic video on communicative competence. *The Modern Language Journal* Vol.83(3), pp. 339–349. DOI: [10.1111/0026-7902.00026](https://doi.org/10.1111/0026-7902.00026).
- Whiting, L.S. (2008) Semi-structured interviews: guidance for novice researchers. *Nursing Standard* Vol.22(23), pp. 35–40.
- Wiggins, G. (2011) A true test: toward more authentic and equitable assessment. *Phi Delta Kappan* Vol.92(7), pp. 81–93. DOI: [10.1177/003172171109200721](https://doi.org/10.1177/003172171109200721).
- Wiliam, D. (2011) What is Assessment for Learning? *Studies in Educational Evaluation* Vol.37(1), pp. 3–14. DOI: [10.1016/j.stueduc.2011.03.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2011.03.001).
- Wiliam, D., Lee, C., Harrison, C., and Black, P. (2004) Teachers developing assessment for learning: impact on student achievement. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* Vol.11(1), pp. 49–65. DOI: [10.1080/0969594042000208994](https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594042000208994).
- Wiliam, D. and Thompson, M. (2007) Integrating assessment with learning: what will it take to make it work? In: C.A. Dwyer ([ed.]), *The Future of Assessment*. New York: Routledge, pp. 53–82. DOI: [10.4324/9781315086545](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315086545).

- Willis, J. (2007) Assessment for learning-Why the theory needs the practice. *International Journal of Pedagogies and Learning* Vol.3(2), pp. 52–59. DOI: [10.5172/ijpl.3.2.52](https://doi.org/10.5172/ijpl.3.2.52).
- (2011) Affiliation, autonomy and Assessment for Learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice* Vol.18(4), pp. 399–415. DOI: [10.1080/0969594X.2011.604305](https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2011.604305).
- Wolcott, H.F. (2002) *Sneaky Kid and its Aftermath: Ethics and Intimacy in Fieldwork*. Oxford: Rowman Altamira Press.
- Wood, K., Linsky, A.S., and Straus, M.A. (1974) Class size and student evaluations of faculty. *The Journal of Higher Education* Vol.45(7), pp. 524–534. DOI: [10.1080/00221546.1974.11776994](https://doi.org/10.1080/00221546.1974.11776994).
- Wood, R. and Bandura, A. (1989) Social Cognitive Theory of organizational management. *Academy of Management Review* Vol.14(3), pp. 361–384.
- Yang, S.C. and Chen, Y. (2007) Technology-enhanced language learning: a case study. *Computers in Human Behavior* Vol.23(1), pp. 860–879.
- Yen, Y-C, Hou, H-T, and Chang, K-E (2015) Applying role-playing strategy to enhance learners' writing and speaking skills in EFL courses using Facebook and Skype as learning tools: a case study in Taiwan. *Computer Assisted Language Learning* Vol.28(5), pp. 383–406. DOI: [10.1080/09588221.2013.839568](https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2013.839568).
- Yin, R.K. (2018) *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods*. 6th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Young, D.J. (1992) Language anxiety from the foreign language specialist's perspective: interviews with Krashen, Omaggio Hadley, Terrell, and Rardin. *Foreign Language Annals* Vol.252, pp. 157–172. DOI: [10.1111/j.1944-9720.1992.tb00524.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1944-9720.1992.tb00524.x).
- Youssef, A.M.S. (2012) Role of motivation and attitude in introduction and learning of English as a foreign language in Libyan high schools. *International Journal of Linguistics* Vol.4(2), pp. 366–375. DOI: [10.5296/ijl.v4i2.1855](https://doi.org/10.5296/ijl.v4i2.1855).

- Zainol Abidin, M.J., Pour-Mohammadi, M., and Alzwari, H. (2012) EFL students' attitudes towards learning English language: the case of Libyan secondary school students. *Asian Social Science* Vol.8(2), pp. 119–134. DOI: [10.5539/ass.v8n2p119](https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v8n2p119).
- Zhang, L.J. and Rahimi, M. (2014) EFL learners' anxiety level and their beliefs about corrective feedback in oral communication classes. *System* Vol.42, pp. 429–439.
- Zhang, Q. (2007) Teacher misbehaviors as learning demotivators in college classrooms: A cross-cultural investigation in China, Germany, Japan, and the United States. *Communication Education* Vol.56(2), pp. 209–227. DOI: [10.1080/03634520601110104](https://doi.org/10.1080/03634520601110104).
- Zheng, Y. (2008) Anxiety and second/foreign language learning revisited. *Canadian Journal for New Scholars in Education/Revue canadienne des jeunes chercheures et chercheurs en education* Vol.1(1), pp. 1–12.
- Ziash, S. (2013) Speaking anxiety in a foreign language classroom in Kazakhstan. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* Vol.93, pp. 1860–1868. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.131>.
- Zojer, H. (2009) The methodological potential of translation in second language acquisition: re-evaluating translation as a teaching tool. In: A. Witte, T. Harden, and A.R.O. Harden ([eds.]), *Translation in Second Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford: Peter Lang AG, International Academic Publishers, pp. 31–51.
- Zumbrunn, S., Tadlock, J., and Roberts, E.D. (2011) *Encouraging Self-Regulated Learning in the Classroom: a Review of the Literature*. Richmond, VA: Metropolitan Educational Research Consortium.